

**Partnership for the Assessment of Risks
from Chemicals**

Additional Deliverable AD6.5

**Development of the strategy for mixture
risk assessment using HBM data and its
application to prioritised mixtures**

WP 6

AD6.5: Development of the strategy for mixture risk assessment using HBM data and its application to prioritised mixtures	Dissemination level: PU
WP6: Innovation in regulatory risk assessment	Version: 1
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Technical References

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¹ PU = Public

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RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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2			
...			

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Mixture risk assessment, co-exposure, cumulative risk assessment, groups (CAGs), real-life mixtures, pesticides, metals, PFAS, mycotoxins, human biomonitoring (HBM), Chemical Strategy for Sustainability (CSS), mixture assessment factor (MAF), PBK model.

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Summary

Exposure to multiple chemicals in real-life situations and the combined effect that this may have generates growing concern among society. Currently in Europe, Agencies and National Authorities perform the risk assessment of chemicals on a substance-to-substance basis, or in a few cases for a limited number of substances from the same chemical family that are expected to have a common effect. People are exposed to a wide range of chemicals through a variety of sources and there is growing consensus that the effect of chemical mixtures needs to be considered in the risk assessment process. In response to this, the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability proposed several ways in which chemical mixtures can be better addressed in the future. The aim of the Real-life mixtures project within the EU funded Partnership for the Risk Assessment of Chemicals (PARC) project, is to develop practical tools, data, methods, and a general strategy to enable an effective mixture risk assessment (MRA) to address policy questions. Currently, the Plant Protection Products Regulation is the most advanced regulatory sector with regards to MRA and implementing the EFSA MRA guidance documents (EFSA et al., 2019b, 2021b). Therefore, this will be considered in the developments within PARC. Additionally, PARC will align with work done in other EU funded projects which collected human biomonitoring (HBM) data. Notably, HBM data plays a fundamental role in the developments of this Real-life mixtures project.

The proposed strategy to perform MRA is based on applying HBM data, knowledge developed for mixtures in regulatory risk assessment and in the field of toxicology, exposome and epidemiology (Section 2). This strategy is organised around three steps: 1) Prioritisation of mixtures, 2) Collection and organisation of HBM and hazard data (including toxicokinetic information), and 3) Mixture risk assessment for prioritised mixtures and effects.

From PARC priorities and discussions with EU Agencies and Commission, four chemical families (pesticides, metals, PFAS and mycotoxins) were prioritised and associated with specific effects of concern. Overall, six case studies were identified and are being addressed in the Real-life mixtures project: 1) Pesticides - Effects on nervous system, motor division (CAG-NAM); 2) Pesticides - Effects on nervous system, brain and/or AChE inhibition (CAG-NAN); 3) PFAS - Effects on Immune system (CAG-INM); 4) Metals - Effects on kidney (CAG-RNL); 5) Mycotoxins - Effects on hematopoietic system (CAG-HAE); and 6) Overarching for all chemical groups - Developmental neurotoxicity (CAG-DNT). More realistic mixtures crossing regulatory silos will be identified from co-exposures of several European HBM surveys using statistical analysis (Section 4).

Data from HBM studies conducted in Europe were compiled. To achieve this, an excel file was created which included questions regarding the meta-data of each study. This file was to be filled out by the owners of HBM data from several European countries such as France, Belgium, Spain, the Netherlands, Greece, Czech Republic, Slovenia, Norway, Denmark, Germany, Finland, Italy, Luxembourg and Croatia. Specific details about each HBM study are provided in Section 3. To improve the comparability between HBM studies and enhance the interoperability for use in the tools of the PARC model network, the data is formatted in a harmonised manner.

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One main challenge to perform the risk assessment is to collect the toxicological value (including or not including uncertainty factors) associated to the selected common effect of the mixture components. As the use of HBM data to perform risk assessments is recent, the establishment and collection of an internal toxicological value (HBM-TV) such as a Human Biomonitoring Guidance Value (HBM-GV) is still at its early stages. Moreover, the HBM-GVs are established from the critical effect which can differ from the selected common effect of the mixture. Thus, approaches such as the use of an internal reference point or conversion of an external reference point into internal dose are proposed in this project to compensate for the absence of HBM-GVs (Section 5). When an HBM-GV is available from one mixture component for the common effect and internal (or external) RPFs are available for the others, risk assessment can be performed using the RPF approach. When no RPFs are available, the ratio between the HBM exposure and the HBM-TV must be calculated for each mixture component. Kinetic models related to the prioritised mixtures were collected to be applied directly or to determine key parameters such as fractions of urinary excretion to convert external to internal hazard or exposure doses and vice-versa (Section 7).

The developed strategy was subsequently applied to the prioritised chemical families and effects to perform risk assessment. The selected case studies well reflect the heterogeneity of available hazard and exposure data that can be used in MRA.

A selection of statistical methods was made to study the link between exposure and health effects. The selected methods will be applied to studies with sufficient information on biomarkers of exposure and biomarkers of effects. Statistical analysis (such as mixture identification), kinetic modelling, link with biomarkers of effect, and risk assessment will be performed in a harmonised way using the Monte Carlo Risk Assessment (MCRA) toolbox. MCRA is a web-based computational environment addressing the full chain for aggregated hazard, exposure and risk assessment for health effects in the general population and in specific populations. In the first year of the Real-life mixtures project, the functionality of the MCRA toolbox was improved to be adapted to HBM data or specific modules of MCRA were newly developed in collaboration with PARC T8.3 (Section 8). The aggregated risk assessment results of the prioritised case studies will be presented in the MCRA Integrated Risk Assessment Dashboard. This dashboard will include examples of how risk can be reduced by risk managers. Work was performed in close cooperation with Work Package 7 (linked to the project and via data champions) and Work Package 4 on exposure data generation.

Overall, this report outlines the progress which has been made in the first year on the strategy to perform MRA in PARC, its practical implementation, and the preliminary results for the prioritised mixtures and their associated effects.

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Glossary

Aggregate Exposure	Exposure to a single substance from multiple sources (i.e., water, air, dust diet, etc.) and/or from multiple routes (ingestion, inhalation, dermal contact). Adapted from OECD (2018a).
AOP (Adverse Outcome Pathway)	A conceptual framework for organizing, synthesizing, and presenting specialized scientific knowledge regarding the linkage between perturbation of a specific biological target, pathway, or process by a stressor, and a consequent adverse outcome(s) considered relevant to risk assessment, regulatory decision-making, and/or environmental management.
Biomarker of Effect	A biomarker that indicates the biochemical, physiological, or behavioural changes produced in the organism due to exposure to exogenous chemicals; they may be associated with an adverse health effect or disease (e.g., circulating hormone levels) (Zare Jeddi et al., 2021; HBM4EU, 2020).
Biomarker of Exposure	A biomarker that measures in biological samples taken from an organism the presence of an exogenous chemical, its metabolite, or the product of interaction between the xenobiotic and a target molecule or cell (e.g., urine levels of bisphenol A and phthalates metabolites or DNA adducts) (Zare Jeddi et al., 2021; HBM4EU, 2020).
Chemical Mixture	Any combination of two or more chemicals to which an individual is exposed regardless of source and spatial or temporal proximity.
Combined Exposure or Co-exposure	Exposure to several chemicals regardless of source and spatial or temporal proximity. Adapted from OECD (2018a).
Common Effect	The adverse effect selected to address several substances.
Critical effect	The adverse effect seen at the lowest dose when a vulnerable population is exposed to a chemical. This effect is generally used to set up HBGV value. Adapted from EFSA (2019b).
CAG (Cumulative assessment group)	Group of compounds considered for a cumulative risk assessment. Grouping can be based on different criteria. Adapted from EFSA (2013b)
Cumulative Exposure See RPF and TEF definition	Exposure to a single exposure dose of a mixture estimated using the dose addition model to cumulate substance exposure converted using relative toxicity/potency factors (RPF, TEF).

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CRA (Cumulative Risk Assessment)	Risk associated with cumulative exposure to several substances sharing the same mechanism of toxic action whose converted doses can be summed up to estimate a single exposure dose of the mixture.
FUE (Fraction of urinary excretion) Synonym: UEF (Urinary Excretion Factor)	Fraction of the amount of a substance eliminated in urine in unchanged form compared to the amount filtered and reabsorbed by the organism. It is also called UEF (Urinary Excretion Factor).
Generic PBK Model	A generic model has a description and compartmentalization of the body and the ADME processes that allow its application to a large panel of chemicals.
HI (Hazard Index)	The sum of the hazard quotients (HQ, Hazard quotient) of the individual components of a mixture. $HI = \sum_{i=1}^n HQ_i$ with $HQ_i = \frac{Exposure_i}{HBGV_i}$
HQ (Hazard Quotient)	The HQ is calculated by dividing the potential exposure by the HBGV of this a substance. $HQ_i = \frac{Exposure_i}{HBGV_i}$
HBGV (Health Based Guidance Values) Synonym: RfD (Reference Dose (USA)) and RV (Reference Value), TRV (Toxicity Reference Value)	Guidance on safe exposure of substances that takes into account current safety data, uncertainties in these data, and the likely duration of exposition. It represents the estimated maximum dose (on a body mass basis) or concentration of an agent to which an individual may be exposed over a specified period without appreciable risk. Reference values are established by applying uncertainty factor(s) to the reference point (a no observed adverse effect level, benchmark dose or benchmark dose lower confidence limit) of the critical effect. Examples in human health include the acceptable daily intake (ADI) for food and feed additives, and pesticides, tolerable upper intake levels (UL) for vitamins and minerals, and tolerable daily intake (TDI) for contaminants and food contact materials, Derived No Effect Levels (DNEL) for industrial chemicals, or Occupational Exposure Limit values (OEL). Examples for acute effects and operators, are the acute reference dose (ARfD) and the acceptable operator exposure level (AOEL). Adapted from EFSA (2019b).
HBGV derivation	Establishing an HBGV from a point of departure (a no observed adverse effect level, benchmark dose or benchmark dose lower confidence limit) divided by a composite uncertainty factor.

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HBGV translation	Establishing an internal HBGV from external HBGV or establishing an external HBGV from internal HBGV.
HBM-GV (Human biomonitoring Guidance Value) Synonym: internal HBGV	Guidance value based on the critical effect that correspond to internal exposure level at and below which there is no appreciable health risk. This includes an uncertainty factor. It represents the concentration of a substance or its specific metabolite(s) in human biological media (e.g., urine, blood, hair) at and below which, according to current knowledge, there is no risk of health impairment anticipated, and consequently no need for action (Apel et al., 2020).
HBM-RP (Human biomonitoring Reference point) Synonym: HBM-POD, BE-POD	The internal reference point HBM-RP is the internal dose corresponding to the reference point, it can be derived from the reference point in applying FUE (Fraction of urinary excretion). It is also called HBM-POD, or Biomonitoring Equivalents BE-POD (animal or human) (Apel et al., 2020; Aylward et al., 2011; Tarazona et al., 2022).
HBM-TV (Human Biomonitoring Toxicological value)	Toxicological value for a common effect that corresponds to internal exposure level at and below which there is no appreciable health risk, including or not uncertainty factors. HBM-TV can be HBM-GV, HBM-RP HBM-POD, BE-POD.
HBM (Human Biomonitoring)	Method for assessing human exposure to chemicals or their effects by measuring these chemicals, their metabolites or reaction products in human specimens (CDC, 2005).
Index compound or reference compound	One of the compounds of the mixture to be assessed or within the CAG that usually has the most reliable data. Its toxicity (reference point) is used to scale the toxicity data of the other components of the mixture.
MCRA (Monte Carlo Risk Assessment) ¹	A web-based platform containing various models that users can use to assess these health risks for specific populations in various scenarios.
MCR (Maximum Cumulative Ratio)	The ratio of the cumulative toxicity received by an individual from exposure to multiple chemical stressors to the largest toxicity from a single chemical stressor (Price and Han, 2011).
Mechanism of Action	Detailed explanation of the individual biochemical and physiological events leading to a toxic effect (EFSA, 2013a).
MIE (Molecular Initiating Event)	A specialised type of key event that represents the initial point of chemical/stressor interaction at the molecular level within the organism that results in a perturbation that starts the AOP (OECD, 2018b).
MoA (Mode of Action)	Biologically plausible sequence of key events in an organism leading to an observed effect, commonly supported by robust experimental

¹ <https://mcra.rivm.nl/Select>

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	observations and mechanistic. It refers to the major steps leading to an adverse health effect following interaction of the chemical with biological targets. It does not imply full understanding of mechanism of action at the molecular level (EFSA, 2013a).
MRA (Mixture Risk Assessment)	Method of assessing risks to health or the environment posed by multiple substances such as chemicals.
mRPI (Modified Reference Point Index)	Sum of the ratio of each chemical component's exposure by the reference point of the common effect divided by the associated uncertainty factor. $mRPI = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{Exposure_i \times UF_i}{RP_i}$ (Vejdovszky et al., 2019)
NAM (Nervous system/ Acute/ Motor)	Active substances causing functional alterations of the motor division of the nervous system (CAG-NAM) (EFSA et al., 2020a).
NAN (Nervous system/ Acute/ Neurochemical)	Active substances causing brain and/or erythrocyte AChE inhibition (CAG-NAN) (EFSA et al., 2020a).
Network Analysis	A visualization tool that can describe the conditional independence between multiple variables. A node in the network represents a biomarker, and an edge reflects conditional dependency given all other variables. The graph estimation can be conducted using for example the graphical lasso, which involves penalized maximum likelihood estimation. This method is a simple and fast algorithm for estimation of a sparse inverse covariance matrix using an L1 penalty. Random walks can be performed across the network to merge separate communities in a bottom-up manner. This statistical method can be applied to combined exposure to graphically represent groups of correlated substances and define mixture (Ottenbros et al., 2021).
PBK parameters	Mathematical values used in PBPK equations to describe characteristics and processes of the body (WHO, 2010; U.S. EPA, 2018).
PODI (Point of Departure Index)	See RPI: Reference Point Index
Prioritisation	First step to define mixtures of interest for risk assessment. Useful when the number of chemicals to be assessed is a priori vast and resources are limited. In project mixture, mixtures are prioritised by two ways: 1/ starting from this chemical families that are already prioritised in PARC WP2 (metals, mycotoxins, PFASs, pesticides- risk drivers for external

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	exposure), 2/ From combined exposure using HBM data (called Real-life Mixture)
Real-Life Mixture	A mixture of substances based on co-exposure and thus revealing the real exposure of individuals. (See also “prioritisation”)
Reference Dose (RfD)	See HBGV
Reference Point (RP) Synonym: POD (Point of Departure)	Defined point on an experimental dose–response relationship for the critical effect (i.e., the biologically relevant effect occurring at the lowest dose level). This term is synonymous to point of departure. Reference points include the lowest or no observed adverse effect level (LOAEL/NOAEL) or benchmark dose lower confidence limit (BDML), used to derive a reference value or Margin of Exposure in human and animal health risk assessment. In the ecological area, these include lethal dose (LD50), effect concentration (EC5/ECx), no (adverse)effect concentration/dose (NOEC/NOAEC/NOAED), and no (adverse) effect level (NEL/NOAEL) (EFSA et al., 2019b).
Risk metric	Method or formula to calculate the risk, it can be Margin of Exposure, Hazard index (see Section 6.2).
RPF (Relative Potency Factor)	Approach uses toxicity data for an index chemical in a group of multiple chemicals “to determine potency-adjusted concentration or exposure data for chemicals in the mixture” assuming dose-addition of the individual chemicals in the mixture (EFSA et al., 2019b).
RPI (Reference Point Index) Synonym: PODI (Point of Departure Index (USA))	Sum of the ratio of each chemical component’s exposure by the reference point (e.g., NOAEL or BMDL) $RPI = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{Exposure_i}{RP_i}$ This differs from the HI based on the HBGV which includes the uncertainty factor. The use of the RPI implies the application of a generalized uncertainty factor (UF). The development of the mRPI overcomes this drawback (EFSA et al., 2019b)
TEF (Toxic Equivalency Factor)	Concept introduced by the World Health Organisation (WHO) to assess the risk of combined exposure to dioxins, dibenzofurans, and dioxin-like PCBs. TEFs are determined using a database of REPs (relative potencies, or RPFs) for each congener compared to the most toxic dioxin 2,3,7,8-TCDD. This

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	REPs database meets WHO established criteria and includes different biological models or endpoints (Van den Berg et al., 2006).
SNMU (Sparse Non-Negative Matrix Underapproximation)	Statistical method to decompose a non-negative data matrix E into a product of two low rank non-negative matrices such as $E = W \times H + \epsilon$ (where W and H are matrices and ϵ , a minimised residual matrix term), taking into account certain constraints. This method can be applied to biomonitoring to identify mixtures based on co-exposure (Crépet et al., 2022).
Specific PBK model	A specific model is developed and evaluated for a compound or a set of compounds. It involves usually the known biological and ADME processes that the compound undergoes. It also can be developed during a specific period of life and/or for a specific population (e.g., elderly, pregnant women or young children).
Toxicological Value (TV)	Generic term for toxicological value associated with a common end point including or not the uncertainty factors. TV can be ADI, TDI, NOAEL, LOAEL, BMDL, etc.
Uncertainty Factor (UF)	Factor applied to a reference point to establish a HBGV to account for sensitivity difference between individuals (intra species variability), animals and humans (interspecies variability), adults and infants, or lack of data, among other factors.
Whole Mixture Approach	An approach used to assess mixture risk where the mixture is treated as a whole, as a single substance. This approach requires toxicological data for the mixture of concern or a sufficiently similar substance using read across methods. It can be used for targeted mixtures such as polluted sites, accidents.

1. Introduction

1.1. Societal and regulatory context of the PARC project Real-life Mixtures

There is growing concern about the exposure to chemicals via dietary intake and the environment. This concern relates to the exposure to multiple chemicals and the combination effect that this may have. Currently, chemical risk assessment within the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), the European Chemical Agency (ECHA) and the EU Member States mainly relies on the assessment of individual substances or in a few cases groups of substances that are expected to occur together. In reality, people are exposed to a wide range of chemicals through a variety of sources.

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According to the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability it is currently not realistic nor economically feasible to specifically assess and regulate an almost infinite number of possible combinations of chemicals, scientific consensus is emerging that the effect of chemical mixtures needs to be considered and integrated more generally into chemical risk assessment². In parallel, targeted methodologies could be further developed and explored for specific policy areas. The Chemical Strategy for Sustainability states that the Commission will:

- Assess how to best introduce in REACH (a) mixture assessment factor(s) for the chemical safety assessment of substances.
- Introduce or reinforce provisions to take account of the combination effects in other relevant legislation, such as legislation on water, food additives, toys, food contact material, detergents and cosmetics.
- Improve the assessments of the mixtures used in the manufacture of tobacco and related products by using where possible existing EU legislation.

Furthermore, the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability also describes the need to continue with the collection of human biomonitoring (HBM) data.

The conclusions in the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability are based on an intensive overview described in Staff Working Document (SWD) (250) (European Commission, 2020). Major conclusions were a lack of aggregated data to cover all routes of exposure, insufficient guidance on the mixture risk assessment (MRA) methods, and the need for mixture risk management is insufficiently addressed in regulatory sectors. The Plant Protection Products Regulation was seen as the most advanced regulatory sector to adapt MRA methods. With two methodological guidance documents (EFSA et al., 2021b, 2019b) and their application reports on pesticides (EFSA et al., 2022, 2020a, 2020b), it is stated that EFSA is responsible for developing MRA methods. It is therefore relevant to align the Partnership for the Risk Assessment of Chemicals (PARC) projects with regulatory needs and to find synergies between work performed in PARC projects and EFSA work (Regulation (EC) No 396, 2005).

1.2. Synergies with EFSA and Regulatory requirements

Currently only the pesticide legislation (Regulation (EC) No 396, 2005; Regulation (EC) No 1107, 2009) specifically include requirements for mixture risk assessment (MRA). EFSA has published four assessments on cumulative dietary risk characterisation of pesticides (EFSA et al., 2022, 2021a, 2020a, 2020b). DG SANTE and the regulators of the EU Member States agreed on an action plan on how to implement MRA methods in the coming years (EFSA, 2021). Training using MCRA as part of the long-lasting partnership between EFSA and RIVM is being organised by EFSA and/or competent authorities for regulators, risk assessors and experts³. User-friendly tools, models and relevant data for MRA will

² https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/chemicals-strategy_en

³ <https://www.rivm.nl/en/food-safety/efsa-rivm-partnership>

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be made accessible to all relevant stakeholders. The trainings may include the MCRA software (sections 3.2 and 7.2). In areas other than pesticides, assessments were conducted by EFSA on groups of substances with similar chemical structures that are likely to pose similar health effects. This grouping approach enables ECHA and EFSA to identify substances that may be of potential concern. The findings from these assessments are presented in various EFSA opinions, which are published for public awareness (EFSA CONTAM Panel et al., 2017; EFSA CEP Panel et al., 2019; EFSA CONTAM Panel et al., 2020; Battilani et al., 2020).

For other legislation, the methods and tools for MRA are less advanced as they are for pesticides. However, the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability has emphasised the need to address risk assessment of both intentional and unintentional mixtures in European Regulations. In this context, EFSA aims that by 2030 the Agency and its partners will be ready for the routine implementation of human health risk assessment to multiple chemicals across its domain of activity. This will require the development of harmonised tools and consolidated data on both dietary and non-dietary exposure to multiple chemicals. Currently, such tools and methods have not been fully developed and additional work is needed before a routine implementation can be achieved.

Therefore, EFSA called for a Roadmap for the Risk Assessment of Combined Exposure to Multiple Chemicals (RACEMiC). This Roadmap was published in October 2022 (de Jong et al., 2022).

To develop the roadmap an overview of currently available methods, data and tools both within and across the chemical domain was created based on a literature search and external stakeholder input. Based on this overview, the scientific gaps were identified and prioritised for their impact on implementation of MRA within EFSA's domain of work. The RACEMiC Roadmap identified scientific gaps including among others the availability of sufficient New Approach Methodologies to fill hazard data gap, the availability of methods and tools for MRA of large (cross-silo) assessment groups and the lack of acceptance of HBM data in the regulatory process. Interconnectivity of these project proposals with other ongoing projects such as the EU funded PARC and the EU funded Athlete project was also identified.

Regarding human risk assessment of chemical mixtures, many activities have been finalised since the European Commission has published SWD 250 and the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability, and new initiatives to proceed on the recommendation of the strategy were initiated. Before starting the PARC project Real-life Mixtures, these achievements and initiatives were overviewed.

Although the conclusions from the workshops aiming to discuss the MAF under REACH have not been published yet, many European projects have recently published work on MRA.

Recently, EFSA and OECD published guidance on scientific methods for the risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals and OECD published guidance on the use of HBM in regulatory decision making (EFSA et al., 2021b; OECD, 2018a). EFSA called for the RACEMiC roadmap that was recently published. The internationally agreed methods for risk assessment as described in EFSA and OECD guidance are followed in the PARC project Real-life mixtures.

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1.3. Synergies with EU funded projects using HBM data and OECD considerations

On 7th October 2020, in the period the PARC partnership was set-up, DG RTD and ANSES organised a workshop to overview the synergies between PARC and EU funded projects. That workshop included presentations on work performed for human risk assessment of mixtures before initiating PARC such as the EU funded project EuroMix⁴ and work in the EU funded EHEN cluster⁵ addressing risk assessment based on HBM data. The synergies were taken into consideration in drafting the PARC project Real-life mixtures. As stated in the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability, a minor limitation in current risk assessment of mixtures is the lack of aggregated exposure data. Therefore, the interpretation of HBM data might be complementary to EFSA's mixture risk assessment (MRA) methods.

The EU funded exposome projects, e.g., the EU funded project Athlete⁶ and other exposome projects in the EHEN cluster, are reporting HBM data and case study results. These EU funded projects started in 2020 and MRA results were reported recently. The EU funded project EuroMix delivered an integrated test and human risk assessment strategy for chemical mixtures. Furthermore, a HBM study was performed and observed HBM studies were compared with sources of exposure. The HBM4EU delivered recommendations on MRA based on the HBM data collected in the HBM4EU project (Luijten et al., 2023). The methodology for human risk assessment was discussed in detail by EFSA in international workshops and several EFSA opinions have been published which include examples of MRAs.

Limitations to the use of HBM data are analytical approaches, uncertainty, and variability associated with the data. HBM data provide exposure levels across a study population and provide a means of comparing exposures across population groups by age, sex, nationality, or other demographic descriptors. The HBM4EU dashboard and overviews of HBM results might overcome these limitations since an enormous data collection has been achieved in the EU funded project. All over Europe, HBM data have been harmonised and are visible both in the HBM4EU dashboard⁷ and the IPCHEM database⁸.

According to the OECD guidance and consideration, biomarkers can be measured in humans, uncertainties due to interspecies differences do not apply. If substances are detected together in a significant number of samples from one population, it could be concluded that the probability of co-exposure is high (OECD, 2011, 2018a). The same applies for effect-biomonitoring. If a HBM study is large enough and representative of a population, statistics can be applied to the study results to

⁴ <https://www.euromixproject.eu/>

⁵ <https://www.humanexposome.eu/>

⁶ <https://athleteproject.eu/>

⁷ <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/what-we-do/european-hbm-platform/eu-hbm-dashboard/>

⁸ <https://ipchem.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>

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generate probabilities of co-exposure or mixture effects for different combinations of substances, and these probabilities could inform the estimate of combined exposure. This activity intends to provide an active knowledge exchange within PARC, for example there are 14 effect-biomarkers with 14 case studies for 4 relevant modes of action proposed to be investigated to address real-life mixtures.

Evaluation of HBM data, in comparison with other monitoring data, such as surveys on product use, environmental concentrations, emissions, etc., can be valuable in examining testing hypotheses about exposure pathways and magnitude of exposure.

A comparison of actual versus modelled exposure is only meaningful if the modelled exposure considers all relevant sources and exposure routes, and the database is very good with respect to product information, consumer behaviour patterns and indirect exposure information (e.g., via house dust). The estimation of actual exposure from HBM data requires an understanding of the compound's toxicokinetic information.

1.4. Objectives of the PARC project Real-life mixtures

The overview of synergies with EU funded projects and in particular, the lessons learned from the HBM4EU project, the discussions with DG ENVIRONMENT and DG SANTE, and the EFSA and OECD guidance were the starting point for the project of Task 6.2.3. “Real-life mixtures” (P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM) (Socianu et al., 2022). This project is considered to be complementary to EFSA's methods. It addressed the gap of missing aggregated exposure data as outlined in 2019 in the SWD (250) document supporting the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability and it is recommended in the EFSA and OECD guidance.

The PARC project Real-Life mixtures is focused on mixture risk assessment (MRA) based on HBM data. It continues on the lessons learned from the HBM4EU project and the priorities set by DG SANTE, EFSA and other stakeholders. The MRA strategy, the HBM data that will be used, the toxicological hazard data following the EFSA and OECD guidance on grouping and the kinetic conversion models will be reported in AD6.5 Deliverable.

Additional to this project, there is a close interaction with PARC Task 4.1.4 which aims to collect HBM data. Furthermore, the integrated model and data platform in PARC Task 8.3 and WP7 are cooperating on making tools and data accessible for future risk assessors and risk managers.

The Real-life mixtures project will fill-in basic science gaps to explore how measurement of the concentration of chemicals in biological samples (HBM data) can be used in practice for MRA. HBM data present several advantages for chemical risk assessment as they directly considered aggregate exposure from multiple sources and routes and make it possible to estimate real co-exposures when several chemicals are sampled in same individuals. The main objectives of the PARC project Real-life mixtures are detailed below.

- Build a common strategy to perform human risk assessment to chemical mixtures from HBM data in integrating chemical exposome and risk assessment approaches.

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The project will bring together knowledge developed for mixtures in regulatory risk assessment and in the field of exposome and epidemiology to apply it to HBM data. Exposure assessors, epidemiologists, and toxicologists will jointly interpret the risk of co-exposure events data following the recent EFSA and OECD guidance on harmonised methodologies for the risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals and the EFSA guidance on the scientific criteria for grouping chemicals into assessment groups for human risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals. Based on this guidance and their own expertise, they will develop a common strategy to perform risk assessment of mixtures using HBM data.

- Prioritise real-life mixtures from HBM data.

MRA is commonly based on external exposure estimated in combining chemical concentrations by source with the corresponding exposure factors (food consumption or use of cosmetics for example). Moreover, mixtures are mostly composed of chemicals from the same chemical family. Thus, one challenge of this project is to use real-life co-exposure observations from HBM data for general and occupational populations across Europe to identify real-life mixtures across regulatory silos in covering the mixtures of concern currently identified in EFSA/ECHA opinions as priorities (PFAS, pesticides, heavy metal, mycotoxins, and independently of the chemical group, chemicals that may trigger developmental neurotoxicity). These results will help to verify the relevance of external MRA and to improve prioritisation of chemicals to follow for risk assessment.

- Develop hazard and kinetic information on prioritised mixtures.

MRA requires the grouping of chemicals based on a common health effect and the collection of hazard data on toxicity of the different components. Efforts have been made in recent years to organise health-based guidance values in the OpenFoodTox database (Kovarich et al., 2022) to perform single risk assessment from external exposure. However, a lot still have to be done for MRA as the common effect can be different from the critical effect on which Human Biomonitoring Guidance Value (HBM-GV) are based. Moreover, as using HBM data to perform risk assessment was recently developed within HBM4EU project, the establishment and collection of internal toxicological values such as HBM-GV is still at its early stage. Nevertheless, kinetic data for chemicals assessed by EFSA will be published in the latest release of OpenFoodTox (expected in 2023). Moreover, as part of the new project on OpenFoodTox (OpenFoodTox 3.0), the intention is to collect information on non-critical target organs. Hazard data gaps regarding prioritised mixtures will be filled. Also, kinetic information to perform reverse and forward dosimetry will help to bridge internal, as observed in HBM, and external exposure estimates as typically addressed in regulations, to make risk assessments possible in the absence of HBM-GV for example.

- Study the link between mixture biomarkers of exposures and effects.

HBM surveys also collect information on biomarkers of effects and/or health effects that can be used to study the association with exposure to multiple chemicals. Thus, epidemiological models will be applied in combination with toxicological information, when possible, to develop knowledge on the level of evidence of main mixtures to which population are exposed.

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- Perform MRA for prioritised mixtures.

The project will provide concrete results on risk assessment of prioritised mixtures (general life and occupational context) in combining toxicity and exposure data following a component-based approaches based on dose additivity. A tiered approach will be applied to refine the assessment depending on the availability and quality of input data.

- Develop knowledge and tools for risk assessors and managers.

The project will provide relevant knowledge regarding the sources of exposure and chemicals of concern (major contributors to mixtures) by performing dedicated regulatory risk assessment of combined exposure as under development in different regulations. It will also propose a coherent implementation of the data and models for evaluating the risk of mixtures for end-users being EFSA panels/ECHA working groups, national experts responsible for risk assessment of mixtures and stakeholders.

2. Description of the general strategy

2.1. Prioritised mixtures strategy

Mixtures for which risk assessment will be performed in this project were prioritised following two complementary ways. A first set of chemical families and their associated relevant health effects that specifically addressed the mixtures of concern currently identified by EFSA and the European Commission were defined (Section 2.1.1). Another criteria for prioritisation owing the risk-based and exposure-driven prioritisation methods proposed by EFSA (2021b). With the second, mixtures are based on their probability of co-exposures using HBM data, and when possible, on their contribution to combined risk when HBM data are used in combination with hazard data. Mixtures are close to those observed in real-life and thus can contain substances from several chemical families across regulatory silos.

2.1.1. Prioritised mixtures and their effects from regulatory needs

The prioritised mixtures to be studied were identified in the PARC strategy with consideration of pre-existing knowledge on exposure, hazardous properties including epidemiological data for some of the compounds and concerns on cumulative risks. The identification of the first set of priorities for PARC started before the launch of the Partnership with the legacy from HBM4EU and with a survey sent to the interim governing board members. In order to have a clearer view on the prioritisation strategy within the different WPs, a survey dedicated to the prioritisation of substances and meetings with WPLs and task leaders to discuss the prioritisation of methods took place after the beginning of PARC. The approach and results are overviewed in PARC deliverable D2.1 Prioritisation criteria report WP2. This process led to a prioritised list of 10 chemical families by PARC stakeholders (academia, HBM4EU

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workshop, European Commission, Ministries of several Member States). The PARC T6.2 task leaders on integrative risk assessment refined these prioritised chemicals groups with the EFSA and the European Commission to ensure synergies with results reported in EFSA opinions or ongoing discussions within working groups of DG SANTE. From these discussions, PFAS, heavy metals, pesticides, and some mycotoxins were prioritised in T6.2. Further to this, associated health effects highlighted in the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability were prioritised for the Real-life mixtures project.

Thus, four different chemical groups were prioritised and associated with specific effects of concern. More specifically, several pesticides were associated with acute effects in the nervous system/AChE inhibition, and a different group of pesticides with effects on the motor division of the nervous system. The pesticides identified being risk drivers with the highest exposure in the EFSA opinions were selected as well as pesticides of concern from DG SANTE perspective (van Klaveren et al., 2019; EFSA et al., 2020a). The challenging question for the present project is to estimate the risk for the exposure of European populations when the systemic exposure levels are measured with HBM surveys and to compare these results to the estimated risk obtained by EFSA from external dietary exposure.

The group of PFAS were associated with effects on the immune system, heavy metals for effects on the kidneys, and mycotoxins for effects on the haematological system. As an overarching effect of concern and its possible association with any chemical, developmental neurotoxicity (DNT), was also prioritised. This was also aligned with EFSA following the EFSA opinions ((EFSA CONTAM Panel et al., 2020)). EFSA is currently implementing a prioritisation exercise for pesticides (to be published second half of 2023), thus these results could also be compared to the list of prioritised pesticides from EFSA (te Biesebeek et al., 2021).

Thus, six case studies were identified at first instance for the Real-Life mixtures project, with consideration of the different chemical groups and the associated effects of concern. Following this approach, the case studies proposed are:

- Case Study 1: Pesticides - Effects on nervous system, motor division (CAG-NAM)
- Case Study 2: Pesticides - Effects on nervous system, brain and/or AChE inhibition (CAG-NAN)
- Case Study 3: PFAS - Effects on Immune system (CAG-INM)
- Case Study 4: Metals - Effects on kidney (CAG-RNL)
- Case Study 5: Mycotoxins - Effects on hematopoietic system (CAG-HAE)
- Case Study 6: Overarching for all chemical groups - Developmental neurotoxicity (CAG-DNT).

Other study cases may be included at a later stage, to take account of the results of the identification of mixtures or to integrate other families of substances such as endocrine disruptors. EFSA is currently implementing a prioritisation exercise for pesticides (to be published second half of 2023) that can also be considered for next case studies.

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2.1.2. Prioritised mixtures from co-exposures and risk metrics

EFSA et al. (2021b) proposed three approaches to prioritise substances for mixture risk assessment (Figure 1). Two are risk-based combining exposure and hazard data: “Combined risk metrics” and “Risk metrics for single chemical”, and one is based only on exposure data: “Exposure-driven approach”.

Figure 1 Workflow for risk-based and exposure-driven prioritisation methods applied to the grouping of chemicals into assessment groups (EFSA 2021)

The exposure-driven approach method allows to identify chemicals that have a likelihood of co-exposure, expressed as probability. Chemicals that have a probability of co-exposure can be defined as a potential mixture and would remain under consideration for grouping regarding their common effect. In contrast, chemicals with a low probability of co-exposure would be considered as of low priority for combined risk assessment and can be excluded. This approach is particularly useful in cases where the risk assessment deals with a large number of chemicals for which the collection or generation of hazard data may not be readily feasible.

The “Combined risk metrics” approach uses hazard data for the common effect or common target organ/system of each chemical. Thus, the relative contribution of each chemical to the combined risk in the assessment group are compared and their probability to contribute to the combined risk assessed. Chemicals showing a high contribution to the combined risk above will remain in the

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assessment group. In contrast, chemicals with low contribution to the combined risk can be excluded from the assessment group.

When hazard data are not available for the common effect or common target organ/system, the “Risk metrics for single chemical based on the critical effect of each chemical” can be applied. In that case, chemicals with high-risk metric for the single chemical can be prioritised as part of the assessment group. In contrast, when the risk metric for the single chemical is demonstrated to be low, the chemical is considered as a low priority chemical and may be excluded from the assessment group.

As the application of the two risk-based approaches requires the collection and organisation of hazard data for each substance under consideration, this approach cannot be applied to HBM survey containing a multitude of chemicals and thus the exposure-driven approach was applied as a first tier in this project (Section 4). Further in the project, when more hazard data will be available from WG2, the combined risk approach could be applied to prioritise mixtures from HBM data and compared the obtained results with the one obtained with the exposure driven approach. In the case study of pesticides, CAG-NAN and CAG-NAM, parent-compounds to be included in the risk assessment performed with HBM data were selected using the “Risk metrics from single chemicals” approach.

2.1.3. General strategy proposed in the project

To develop mixture risk assessment (MRA) methods, the Task 6.2.3 Real-life mixtures project is divided into three steps: 1) Prioritisation of mixtures, 2) Collection of hazard data, 3) MRA (Figure 2).

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Figure 2. General strategy developed in Task 6.2.3 Real-life mixtures project and implication of working groups

The Task 6.2.3 Real-life mixtures project involves partners from Task 6.2 and Task 4.1.4 with different backgrounds related to risk assessment: HBM surveys, exposure, epidemiology, statistics, toxicology, toxicokinetic, etc. To be able to work on different steps of the mixture strategy, partners were allocated into three working groups with main objectives described below. Transversality between working groups was ensured by the project coordination and WG leaders. A close collaboration between the three WGs and the Task 8.3 to implement the strategy with the relevant data in the PARC model network was also conducted.

WG 1: HBM data analysis, exposure and risk assessment: ANSES, RIVM with UU-IRAS, MU, NIPH, AU, VITO, NIJZ, IISPV, WR, LNS, SECO, IVL, INRAE, JSI, UNIVIE, STAMI, TTL, BPI, UBA, UGR, DTU

- Real-life mixture prioritisation from HBM data;
- Link mixture exposures with effect biomarkers/health effects;
- Develop and implement statistical analysis in PARC model network;
- Develop risk assessment metrics in collaboration with WG2 and their implementation in PARC model network.

WG 2: Grouping, relative potency, QSARs and AOPs: BPI with IISPV, UNIPD, ICPS, WR, LNS, UU-IRAS, MU, NIPH, AU, ANSES, VITO, SECO, EHESP, Sciensano, TiHo, NMBU, NVI, DTU, NIJZ, UBA, TTL, UG-PL, IVL, IRFMN

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- Group prioritised substances by common effects;
- Collect and organise hazard data;
- Select HBM-GV;
- Develop toxicological values from reference points when no internal or external health-based guidance values (HBM-GV and HBGV) exist;
- Apply *in silico* methods (will be developed in a later stage of the project).

WG 3: Kinetics and models: Ineris, AUTH with ANSES, UU-IRAS, RIVM, URV, ONIRIS, WR, UNN, SLU, FOPH, UNIPD, MU, UGR, NIPH, AU, VITO, IISPV, UBA, ICPS, BPI, JSI, IVL

- Inventory PBK models for prioritised mixtures;
- Adapt, develop PBK models for mixtures and associated parameters;
- Test the use of generic/specific PBK models;
- Develop proxy such as excretion factors, steady-state, etc.

As explained in part 2.1 and described in Figure 2, mixtures for which risk assessment will be performed in this project are prioritised using 3 approaches:

- 1/ from regulatory needs integrated in PARC strategy regarding chemical families and their effects,
- 2/ from exposure-driven prioritisation method using HBM data,
- 3/ to complete prioritised chemical families in 1/ by chemicals from other chemical families with similar common effect.

With approach 2/ (based on co-exposure) and approach 3/ (common effect), mixtures will cross regulatory silos and thus become more realistic.

Approach 1/ (grouped by effect according to regulatory needs) and approach 2/ were started during the first year of PARC. First developments of these approach are described in this deliverable.

With approach 1/, the hazard and the respective risk is estimated based on HBM data for co-exposures of individuals to different chemicals in each prioritised chemical groups for the specific adverse outcome e.g., for effects on kidney from HBM co-exposure to metals (Section 2.1.1). The detailed list of substances composing the prioritised chemical families was distributed to the three WGs (Appendix 1). In WG1, a first inventory of HBM survey was made building on HBM4EU HBM collection and on HBM survey from new partners of Task 6.2.3 (Section 3). The inventory was used to verify if prioritised chemicals were analysed and detected in the HBM survey as the basis to perform risk assessment. The partners with HBM survey have started to harmonise and organise their HBM data to be uploaded in MCRA tool (platform containing various models to assess health risks) (Sections 3.2 and 7.2). On the basis of the list of substances, composing the prioritised chemical families and their respective effect, the WG2 has started the collection of hazard data needed to perform risk assessments (Section 5.1). The WG3 has started to organise PBK models related to prioritised chemical families and collect related

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parameters. They also tested the use of the generic PBK model implemented in MCRA in comparison of specific PBK models.

In parallel, the WG1 started to develop the approach 2. The first step of this approach is to define real-life mixtures applying the exposure-driven prioritisation methods as proposed by EFSA et al. (2021b) (Section 2.1.2). Within this approach, mixtures are formed based on their probability of co-exposure (Figure 2). Statistical methods specifically developed to identify co-exposure mixtures (Crépet et al., 2019; Ottenbros et al., 2021) were adapted to HBM data and (re)implemented in MCRA Toolbox (Sections 4 and 7.3).

These methods will be applied by each partner when their HBM data will be uploaded in MCRA Toolbox. An example is already available on ESTEBAN survey as proof of concept (Section 4.3). The real-life mixtures obtained from co-exposures will be then analysed by WG2 for their common effect and for the collection of new hazard data if needed. WG3 will also reflect on these real-life mixtures regarding toxicokinetic aspects. In addition, occupational scenarios with potential mixed exposure to high levels of similarly acting priority chemicals and relevant studies will be identified to provide data for the MRA in occupational scenarios.

Finally, the three working groups will join their force to perform risk assessment for prioritised chemical family mixtures (approach 1 and 3) and for real-life mixtures obtained from HBM data (approach 2), Figure 3.

When possible, results for general population will be compared with risk assessments performed from external (diet) exposure. Some partners of WG1 will also apply and compare adapted statistical methods to study the association of exposure to mixtures with biomarkers of effect or health effects available in the HBM surveys. For similar studied health effects, those results will be analysed with regards to risk results obtained with toxicological data.

Figure 3..Distribution of knowledge between the three working groups. Collaboration between WG1 and WG2 led to the establishment of risk metrics. Risk assessments are the result of collaboration between the 3 WGs

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3. Description of available HBM studies

3.1. Description of HBM studies

3.1.1. Data inventory method

The objective was to identify HBM studies conducted in Europe and specifically the ones that address unintentional mixtures of concern identified by the EFSA and ECHA. These priority mixtures include Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), pesticides, heavy metals, mycotoxins, developmental neurotoxicity (DNT) and Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals (EDCs) (Section 2.1.1). A data inventory has been created to gather information about these HBM studies and identify available study for this project. This inventory will allow us to have a good overview of HBM studies in Europe and chemicals measured in each study.

To achieve this, an excel file was created which included questions regarding the meta-data of each study. This information included details such as: general information such as name of the study, population type (general population, control, workers, etc.) and age, analysis already performed on it (mixture identification, mixture risk assessment), exposure biomarkers, health outcomes, effect biomarkers, and others. The excel file was shared with all partners involved in the PARC Task 6.2.3 project and they were asked to include details of their studies in the inventory and indicate the availability status of their data (“data available immediately”; “data will be available in 20XX”; “measurements still in progress”). Several rounds of email correspondence were initiated to ensure the seamless progress of this process.

To conduct mixture risk assessments (MRA) effectively, it is imperative to possess measurement data for each individual within a given cohort or subset. In light of this, we have requested that the owners of HBM data create multiple rows for the same study, but for each subset. In this context, each row represents a distinct study that focuses on a specific age group, and possibly for subsets of substances where all individuals have undergone measurement. Such an approach is necessary to ensure that the requisite data is available for conducting MRAs.

After the completion of the inventory, data owners of the listed study were asked to indicate their willingness to participate further in this project. They would have to harmonise (Section 3.2) and upload their data into the MCRA tool for the purpose of conducting MRAs in various settings:

- Participation in joint real-life mixture identification (Section 4)
- Participation in real-life mixture identification per country (Section 4)
- Participation in studying link between mixture exposure and effect biomarkers and health effects (Section 5.2)
- Participation of risk assessment for prioritised case studies (Section 9).

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The uploading of HBM data in MCRA requires signing of a data controller – data processor agreement as the individual data are hosted on the RIVM servers, this agreement is prepared by the legal department at the RIVM.

3.1.2. Data inventory overview

The inventory is available on the Microsoft Teams SharePoint of the project and on request for external people. It should be considered as a living document, with the potential for alteration of the recorded data. It is imperative to note that the inventory is not exhaustive and not all of the datasets listed are accessible for this project. Table 1 presents a comprehensive list of countries that have conducted HBM studies. Table 2 present the list of chemicals group measured in different studies.

Table 1 List (non-exhaustive) of countries with Human biomonitoring (HBM) datasets in Europe

Country	Institute(s)	Type	Name of the study
France	Santé Publique France/ Anses ; INSERM	General population	ESTEBAN, EDEN and SEPAGES
Belgium	VITO	General population & hotspots	FLEHS1- 4 and 3xG
Spain	IISPV, ISCIII, FINBA-IDAEA-CSIC -UGR	General population (Pregnant women)	EXHES-Spain, DEMOCOPHES, SPECIMEn-Control group, BEA, HBM4EU-mom and BIOAMBIENT.ES, INMA-Asturias and INMA-Granada
The Netherlands	RIVM, UU-IRAS	General population	Specimen, Doetinchem
Greece	AUTH	General population	EXHES-Greece and CROME
Czech Republic	RECETOX/MU	General population	CELSPAC
Slovenia	JSI, NIJZ	General population	SLO-CROME, DEMOCOPHES, SLO-HBM-I and SLO-CRP
Norway	NIPH	General population	NEB II (The Norwegian Environmental Biobank), EuroMix
Denmark-Greenland	Public Health, Aarhus University (AU-PH)	General population	ABC / FETOTOX and BOC-DNBC, BOC-GRL, ACCEPT, ACCEPT-BioSund
Germany	UBA	General population	GerES V, GerES V-sub (HBM4EU Aligned Studies), GerES IV, ESB, DEMOCOPHES
Finland	TTL	General population	FIOH LIMS bio welder data
Finland and 7-8 other countries ⁹	all HBM4EU e-waste and chromate study	Occupational exposure	HBM4EU e-waste/chromate study

⁹ HBM4EU e-waste/chromate study involves multiple countries for e-waste study including Finland: TTL; Portugal: ESTsSL, INSA; United Kingdom: HSL; Belgium: KU Leuven, UA; Luxembourg: LNS; Poland: NIOM; Latvia: RSU; The Netherlands: RUMC; Denmark: IPASUM

Chromate study: Finland: TTL; Italy: DPH, ISS; Portugal: ESTeSL, INSA; PL: HSL, IOM; France: INRS; Denmark: IPASUM; Belgium: KU Leuven, Luxembourg: LNS; Poland: NIOM; The Netherlands: RUMC

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		partners are co-controllers of the data	
Italy	UNIPD	General population, occupational exposure	ETU levels in urine in subjects living near vineyards; Anaesthetic gases level in urine in health care workers
Luxembourg	LNS		HBM4EU Lux aligned study / Oriscav-Lux2
Croatia, Republic, Denmark, Italy, Netherlands, Spain, Switzerland, Portugal and Argentina	Czech Republic, France, Slovenia, and	WUR + RUMC (coordinators)	SPRINT (still ongoing)

Table 2 List (non-exhaustive) of chemicals measured in the HBM studies

Substance family	Biomarkers
Pesticides	Pyrethroid, Organochloride, carbamate, neonicotinoid, other pesticides /pesticide families
Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS)	PFOA, PFNA, PFOS, PFBA, PFHxA, other PFAS
Mycotoxins	Aflatoxins, Deoxynivalenol / Nivalenol, Alternaria toxins, Enniatins, Fumonisin, Ochratoxin A, T2/HT2 toxin, Zearalenone
Heavy metals	As, Cr, Pb, Hg, Methyl mercury, Mn, Ni, Fluoride
Bisphenols	BPA, BPS, BPF
Phthalates	MEHP, MEHHP, MEOHP, MECPP, MBzP, MnBP, MiBP, MEP, MiNP, MCOP, MiDP, MCNP, MnOP, MOP, MMP, MnPeP, MCHP, MPHP, ...
DINCH	MINCH, MCOCH, MHNCH, MONCH, ...
PCBs	
Other dioxins furans	PCDDs, PCDFs, ...
Flame retardants	PBDEs, HBCDs, TBBPA, BDCIPP, DPHP, B CEP, BCIPP, DnBP, BBOEP, TBBPA, HBB, PBEP, BTBPE, PBT, DP, DBDPE, HCDBCO, EHTBB, BEHTEBP, OBIND, TBX, TBECH, ...
PAHs,	FLUO, NAPH, PYR, CRY, PHE, FLA, BaA, BaP, BcPh, BcFA, BcFL, BghiP, BjfA, BkFA, ACE, ACY, AN, CPP, DBahA, DBaeP, Dbai, DBaIP, ...
Acrylamide	AAMA, GAMA, AAVaI, GAVaI, ...
Parabens	Methylparaben, Ethylparaben, isopropylP, Propylparaben, etc.
Organic solvents	toluene, ethanol, Tetrachloroethylene
UV-Filters	BP3, BP1, BP6, 4HBP, 4MP

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The population that has been addressed in various studies encompasses a wide range of demographics including general population (children, teenagers, adults, pregnant women), workers, hotspots, etc. These groups represent a diverse cross-section of society and provide valuable insights into the exposure of different populations.

3.1.3. HBM studies

Among the studies identified in the data inventory, some are clearly involved in the project and may be included in the first analysis sets. These studies are briefly presented in Appendix 2.

3.2. Data format process

Harmonisation of individual HBM and accompanying data is essential in order to make them FAIR. Furthermore, data harmonization will improve the comparability between HBM studies, and enhance the interoperability for use with tools such as MCRA (Monte Carlo Risk Assessment software) or the tool for the calculation of summary statistics of the HBM data, which can be made available via IPCHEM and/or integrated into the European HBM dashboard.

All the necessary documents and instructions' manuals are available in this website: <https://hbm.vito.be/tools/data-harmonization>.

The data harmonisation process includes the following steps:

Step 1: Fill the biomarker list

VITO has developed a biomarker list in which data providers should indicate the biomarkers available for their study and in which matrix they were measured. Additional metadata information must be supplied by the data owner in the Information sheet, such as the Institute and data collection ID, name, description and acronyms. The filled biomarker list should then be sent back to VITO. Upon receipt of this information, the VITO Data management team provides a personalised data template adapted for each data collection (Excel format) with a column for the actual measurement value of each indicated biomarker, and two additional columns (for LOD and LOQ respectively). In the case there is exposure data available for biomarkers not included in the biomarker list, the data provider should contact the VITO team at PARC.DATAMANAGEMENT@vito.be.

Step 2: Fill the empty data template using instructions of the basic codebook

As indicated in step 1, VITO will provide the data owner/provider a personalised empty data template that should be filled according to the instructions of the basic codebook. In the basic codebook, all information regarding how each variable should be encoded is provided. For the HBM4EU occupational studies, the basic codebook was extended with a few specific variables for these occupational studies.

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The data must be entered in different sheets of the excel template, this structure was chosen to avoid the need for replication of data. The structure is based on considering the sample as the main unique identifier in the dataset. The different sheets in the data template are the following:

- 1) Information of the study: In the sheet “STUDYINFO”, the fields on study ID, study name and study description will automatically be filled based on the information provided in the biomarker list.
- 2) Information on the sample is provided in the sheet “SAMPLE”. Each sample must be mapped to a time point and to a subject. TIMEPOINT has been included to indicate if a collection of samples must be considered together, e.g., relevant in repeated sampling design. In the sheet “TIMEPOINT”, a short description of the different times in which samples were collected has to be provided, even in the case where only one time point is available.
More than one sample may be mapped to the same subject, e.g., when blood and urine samples for a given subject are available. In the codebook, a description of the variables, and the format in which they need to be provided can be found under the corresponding sheet.
- 3) Information on the subject is provided in two sheets “SUBJECTUNIQUE” and “SUBJECTREPEATED”. This has been split to enable the capturing of values that may change through time, e.g., BMI of the individual at first versus second sampling time point. All information that is considered unique to the person from the first sampling onwards, has been included in the table “SUBJECTUNIQUE”, e.g., sex of the subject. All information that may change, has been included in table “SUBJECTREPEATED”. The link with timepoints shall be indicated in *id_timepoint* referring to the TIMEPOINT sheet. Please note that in the sheet “SUBJECTUNIQUE”, linkage between the subjects is also created. This enables to identify e.g., mother-child pairs.
- 4) The data obtained from chemical measurements of the samples is to be provided in the sheets with prefix DATA_. For each matrix, a separate sheet is provided. Please note that the *id_sample* shall be extracted for the specified matrix from the sheet “SAMPLE”.

VITO also provides an example data template with simulated data, however, not all biomarkers and matrices are included in the example data template since the list of possible biomarkers is quite long.

Step 3: Data validation

VITO developed a data validation tool that allows to perform a check of the individual level data, prepared in the harmonised data templates, regarding the formats and rules specified in the basic codebook.

To do so, the user must access the data validation tool in this website: <https://hbm.vito.be/tools/tool-data-validation>. The filled data template should be selected prior to running the tool. The tool checks if the data are correctly formatted following the rules in the basic codebook.

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The tool will generate a report with critical, error and warning messages, and display these on the screen. If any critical errors are displayed, a file format mistake has happened. All errors should be corrected, and warnings should be checked.

While correcting, the table heads can be clicked to sort the messages according to their variable name, severity level or sheet name. A pdf file of the messages can be created by right clicking the page, pressing print and selecting 'save as pdf' as printer.

After correcting, the corrected file must be re-selected, and validation should be rerun. These steps should be repeated until no errors are displayed and all warnings have been properly checked. Once this is achieved, the filled data template is ready for further use in MCRA.

4. Real-life mixtures identification from co-exposures using HBM data

4.1. Grouping and choice of studies

Identifying real-life mixtures from co-exposure requires the measurement of several substances (if possible, from different chemical families) in the same individuals. Using HBM data can be a limitation as they are not designed for mixture risk assessment and thus do not generally provide all chemicals in the same individuals. Indeed, the whole population dataset is generally divided in sub-dataset providing measurements for a part of studied chemicals. Thus, one challenge is to define the optimal sub-dataset to be used to identify mixtures from the largest initial number of substances.

For the general population, the individuals were grouped by age groups (children 3-11 years, teenagers 12-17 years, adults 18-39 years, mother-newborn pairs, pregnant women, etc.). For the workers, only occupational studies on the same category of workers and biomarkers of exposure could be grouped. According to the current data inventory there are no such studies.

Two approaches have been chosen to carry out mixture identification: 1) An independent mixture identification by HBM database where each data owner will define mixtures according to the substances analysed in their study; 2) HBM databases with identical substances and populations will be considered for mixture identification and results obtained from each database compared.

The first approach is the easiest to implement because it does not require alignment of the studies. Indeed, the same statistical methods (Section 4.2) will be applied in each database, which will allow mixtures to be determined in a homogeneous manner. On the other hand, it does not enable an easy comparison of the identified mixtures because the initially measured substances can differ between studies.

Then, the second approach can be implemented to define main European mixtures. To compare the identified mixtures among different European countries, studies or subsets of studies where the same substances were analysed in the same individuals within an age group will be grouped. In practice each

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data controller will perform a mixture identification, then the identified mixtures will be compared. From the analysis of the data inventory, it is not possible to determine cohort groups because the inventory does not provide all the subsets that are possible from a database. As a first step, aligned studies from HBM4EU which by definition have studied the same substances in the same populations and any national studies that have the same protocol could constitute a group. If within a study, a selection of substances must be made in order to have only substances measured in the same individuals, the priority substances of this task (Appendix 1) have to be selected first and then on a case-by-case basis of each study.

4.2. Statistical analysis of HBM data

Each data set will be compiled with the harmonisation process presented above (Section 3.2) Descriptive statistics will be calculated and exploration of co-exposure will be performed in a harmonised way. These steps will be performed using the MCRA software (van der Voet et al., 2020). The Maximum Cumulative Ratio (MCR) will be applied to determine the number of substances composing the cumulative risk (Price and Han, 2011; OECD, 2018a). Then as a follow-up of the EuroMix and HBM4EU projects, the two methods developed to identify mixtures from co-exposures, naming Sparse Non-negative Matrix Underapproximation (SNMU) in combination with clustering (Crépet et al., 2019, 2022) and Network Analysis based on partial correlations (Ottenbros et al., 2021) will be applied to HBM dataset. All these methods have been implemented in MCRA.

4.2.1. Data preparation for statistical analysis

The data will be processed in MCRA under the same harmonised data preparation protocol. This plan is meant to evolve over the course of the project and to be adapted to each dataset's specificities. The preparation protocol steps are presented below:

- Standardisation: Urine concentrations are standardised by creatinine or normalised by specific gravity depending on each study's method. Creatinine standardisation is dividing the biomarker concentration by creatinine (Šulc et al., 2022). Blood concentrations are standardised by dividing them by total lipids for lipid-soluble biomarkers (e.g., PCBs, BDEs, etc.).
- Censored value imputation (biomarker concentrations): MCRA allows different methods to handle left-censored values. Such values might be substituted by
 - Zero;
 - $LOR \times f$ such LOR is either the LOD (Limit of Detection) or LOQ (Limit of Quantification) and f a factor;
 - $LOD \times f$ if censored value below LOD or $LOD + f \times (LOQ - LOD)$ if missing value is between LOD and LOQ .

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- Imputation by censored lognormal model (in brief, for each substance a censored log-normal concentration model is fitted to the data, which is subsequently used for imputation of censored data by a random value from the fitted distribution truncated by LOQ).

This last option is applied to the data, with a fallback to one of the other methods if the censored lognormal distribution cannot be fitted to the data.

- Missing value imputation (biomarker concentrations): Such values might be:
 - Set to zero
 - Impute from data
 - Not imputed (missing values are not imputed, and subsequent analyses are based on complete cases only)

The option “Not imputed” is applied at first to work on complete cases.

- Missing value imputation (covariates): An option for imputation of missing characteristics (covariates) of study participants will be implemented later on in MCRA, assuming a missing (completely) at random.
- Later on, the selection of biomarkers could be discussed to ensure data quality, biomarker concentrations with high proportion of missing values could be excluded from the analysis.

4.2.2. Descriptive statistics

After data preparation, each HBM study could generate descriptive statistics using MCRA.

The expected information is summarised in Appendix 3. In short, the following are expected for the exposure biomarkers: the number of individuals with detected values (i.e, positive values), the number of missing measurements and the means, P25, P50 and P95 of the individuals with detected concentrations, distributions of concentration; for the covariates describing the individuals: the means, P25, P50, P90, minimum, maximum and number of missing values.

4.2.3. Maximum Cumulative Ratio

The maximum cumulative ratio (MCR) is a tool where the ratio of the cumulative exposure for a person exposed to multiple chemicals to the person’s largest single-chemical exposure is determined (De Brouwere et al., 2014). The single chemical that contributes most to the cumulative exposure is termed the primary chemical. Chemical-by-chemical approaches can identify the value of single-chemical exposure but not the cumulative exposure, thus, MCR can evaluate the magnitude of the toxicity missed if a cumulative risk assessment is not performed and only a single chemical approach is used. For example, an MCR value of 2 indicates that 50% of an individual’s hazard index would be missed if a chemical-by-chemical method is used to assess the individual instead of a cumulative risk assessment

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(Price and Han, 2011). This tool can also be used to determine which chemicals are the drivers for cumulative exposure.

MCR is a quantitative measure of the difference between the individual's health effects estimated using a chemical-by-chemical approach and that using an additive model of toxicity (Mao et al., 2022). As described in Price and Han (2011), the MCR can be calculated using the hazard quotient (HQ) for each substance present in a mixture and the hazard index (HI) of the mixture. In a population composed of exposed individuals where dietary exposure of n substances was performed and HQs are available (HQ_j), the MCR of person i (MCR_i) is given by:

$$MCR_i = \frac{HI_i}{\max(HQ_{ij})} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n HQ_{ij}}{\max(HQ_{ij})} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n \frac{EDI_{ij}}{HBGV_j}}{\max\left(\frac{EDI_{ij}}{HBGV_j}\right)}$$

where EDI_{ij} is the intake of chemical j by person i , $HBGV_j$ is the health-based reference value of metal j . HQ_{ij} is the hazard quotient of the exposure to the metal j of person i .

Initially, the MCR has shown how the determination of MCR values in an initial tier of an assessment can focus the higher tiers of the assessment on specific combinations of chemicals of concern which could not be recognised prior to performing the initial tier (Price et al., 2012). In the EuroMix project, the MCR was further refined and implemented in MCRA for higher tier assessment. This method is being applied in the EFSA opinions on the pilot studies cumulative risk assessment to cumulative assessment group NAN (Nervous system Acute Neurochemical) and NAM (Nervous system Acute Motor) (van Klaveren et al., 2019; EFSA et al., 2020a).

This enables the risk managers to compare exposure observations above the threshold of regulatory concern. Exposure with a higher value than 1 on the X-axis is of regulatory consideration (Figure 4). Apparently, the exposure above the threshold of regulatory considerations were explained for 75% by exposure to single pesticides rather than mixtures. It shows the frequency of exposure to mixtures and/or individual to mixtures and single chemicals in the population of interest. The MCR plot is generated in the MCRA software.

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Figure 4. Maximum cumulative ratio calculated for each individual for pesticides with effects on nervous system.

4.2.4. SNMU with cluster analysis on individuals

The Sparse Non-negative Matrix Underapproximation (SNMU) approach is applied to the pre-processed HBM data to identify single substances or mixtures that contribute most to the total exposure using a dimension reduction method (Gillis and Plemmons, 2013). SNMU was previously applied to chemical dietary exposure data in the EuroMix project (Crépet et al., 2019). In addition, a hierarchical classification to cluster individuals regarding their exposure to mixtures is applied. This method has been used before on external exposures (Traoré et al., 2016, 2018; Crépet et al., 2022).

Figure 5. SNMU scheme

The SNMU solution approximates the non-negative matrix E (exposure levels) by two non-negative matrices U and V with lower dimensions, such that the product of the two is as close as possible to the original matrix. The SNMU models is $E = U \times V + \epsilon$ where ϵ is a non-negative residual matrix. The matrices U and V were obtained by minimising the criterion:

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$$\min_{W \in \mathbb{R}^{P \times K}, H \in \mathbb{R}^{K \times N}} \|E - WH\|_F^2 + \mu \|W\|_0 \text{ such that } W \geq 0, H \geq 0 \text{ and } WH \leq E.$$

The U matrix defines the mixtures based on co-exposures where columns represent the identified mixtures and rows represents the substances. This matrix represents the mixture's composition and the statistical weight of substances in mixtures, i.e., the relative contribution of a substance to the mixture. The number of mixtures is determined by the user relying on the analysis of residual sum of squares (or RMSE for Root Mean Square Error) between the observed exposure matrix and its approximation (the product of the matrices U and V) for each number of mixtures and balancing it with biological interpretation.

The statistical weight of matrix V informs on the exposure to mixtures of each individual. Ward's hierarchical cluster analysis (HCA) is performed on this matrix in order to cluster individuals with similar exposure profiles.

SNMU on HBM data can be run in practice by performing an Exposure mixtures action in MCRA (Biometris, WUR, 2023). After setting the target level as internal, and internal concentrations as human monitoring concentrations, MCRA will ask for human monitoring analysis data. These are the processed version of the unprocessed but harmonised human monitoring (i.e., HBM) data prepared according to the code book (Section 3.2). The Exposure mixtures action allows the specification of the desired number of SNMU components as well as several technical parameters to guide the estimation process. In the current version of MCRA, the SNMU results can be generated with or without the additional cluster analysis of individuals. The basic steps to perform Mixture analysis are presented in Appendix 4. A detailed practical guidance is provided to users to perform such analysis.

4.2.5. Network Analysis

Network analysis is a general term to denote a class of statistical methods that can be applied to multivariate data to learn about the correlation structure. In the first phase of the Real-life mixtures project, it was decided to start with the specific method developed in the HBM4EU project (Ottenbros et al., 2021). This method works on standardised log-transformed data and aims to show the most important partial correlations between columns (substances). The outcome of such an analysis is graphically displayed as a network (graph). This is a collection of nodes that may have pairwise relationships. Each node represents a substance, and an edge represents pairwise dependence between substances, i.e., partial correlation in this case. The approach of Ottenbros et al. 2021 was implemented in MCRA. An important aspect of this implementation was the detection of so-called "communities" within the derived networks. These communities reflect sub-parts of the network in which correlations are denser than in other parts of the network, potentially reflecting groups of compounds that should be considered jointly in a risk assessment approach.

In this implementation, the network is estimated using the graphical lasso (which is based on partial correlation and a sparseness penalty to control the number of non-zero edges) (Friedman, Hastie and Tibshirani, 2008). The communities are detected using the Walktrap algorithm.

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Network analysis on HBM data can be run in practice by performing an Exposure mixtures action in MCRA (Biometris, WUR, 2023). After setting the target level as internal, and internal concentrations as human monitoring concentrations, MCRA will ask for human monitoring analysis data. These are the processed version of the unprocessed but harmonised human monitoring (i.e., HBM) data prepared according to the code book (Section 3.2). The Exposure mixtures action currently includes the network analysis as an additional option to performing SNMU.

4.3. Preliminary results from ESTEBAN HBM survey

As a proof of concept, the SNMU approach (Section 4.2.2) has been applied to a subset of the ESTEBAN study (Section 3.1.3). As not all substances were measured in all participants of the ESTEBAN study, a subset of 4 chemical families was defined. The metals, flame retardants, pesticides and PFAS listed in the Table 3 below were selected because, with the exception of flame retardants, these substances were identified as priority substances in PARC and were measured in the same individuals. Thus, this dataset consists of 272 adults from 19 to 74 years old (61% of women) for which 107 biomarkers of exposure were measured. For censored data, a lower bound scenario was applied: data below the LOD were replaced by 0, data between the LOD and the LOQ were replaced by the LOD, missing data were replaced by the mean. Urinary biomarkers were corrected by creatinine and flame retardants were corrected by lipid total.

Table 3 Selected substances for the first ESTEBAN subset

Family	Biomarkers	Biological matrix
Metals	Al, As, Au, B, Ba, Be, Cd, Co, Cr, Cs, Cu, Hg, Ir, Li, Mn, Mo, Ni, Pd, Pt, Sb, Se, Sn, Tl, U, V, W, Zn	Urine
Brominated flame retardants	Polybrominated diphenylether: BDE-15, BDE-17, BDE-25, BDE-28, BDE-33, BDE-47, BDE-66, BDE-85, BDE-99, BDE-100, BDE-153, BDE-154, BDE-183, BDE-209, Hexabromobiphenyl (PBB-153), Hexabromocyclododecane HBCD α , HBCD β , HBCD γ	Blood serum
Pesticides (carbamates)	IPP (2-Isopropoxyphenol), Propoxur (2-[(Propan-2-yl)oxy]phenyl methylcarbamate), carbofuran-phenol	Urine
Pesticides (pyrethroids)	cis-DCCA (cis-3-(2,2-dichlorovinyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropane-1-carboxylic acid), trans-DCCA (trans-3-(2,2-dichlorovinyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropane-1-carboxylic acid), cis-DBCA (cis-3-(2,2-dibromovinyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropane-1-carboxylic acid), F-3-PBA (4-fluoro-3-phenoxybenzoic acid), 3-PBA (3-phenoxybenzoic acid)	Urine
Pesticides (organochlorides)	4-MCP4 (4-chlorophenol); 2,4-DCP (2,4-dichlorophenol); 2,5-DCP (2,5-dichlorophenol); 2,6-DCP (2,6-dichlorophenol); 2,3,4-TCP (2,3,4-Trichlorophenol); 2,4,5-TCP (2,4,5-trichlorophenol), 2,4,6-TCP (2,4,6-Trichlorophenol); 2,3,4,6-TeCP (2,3,4,6-Tetrachlorophenol); PCP (Pentachlorophenol)	Urine

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Pesticides (organophosphates)	DEDTP (Diethyldithiophosphate), DEP (Diethyl phosphate), DETP (Diethyl thiophosphate), DMDTP (Dimethyl dithiophosphate), DMP (Dimethyl phosphate), DMTP (Dimethyl thiophosphate)	Urine
PFAS	PFBS, PFHxS, PFHpS, PFOS, PFDS, PFOSA, NMeFOSAA, NEtFOSAA, PFBA, PFPA, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnA, PFDaA	Blood serum
other	cotinine	

The steps in the application of the SNMU are described in Section 4.2.4 and in Appendix 4. The initial parameters were “number of mixtures = 20”, “sparsity = 0.1”, “number of iterations = 1000”. The number of mixtures explaining the dataset can be adjusted. The initial number is deliberately high in order to be able to study the evolution of the difference in the ratio of RMSE (root-mean-square error) in the RMSE plot (Figure 6). The higher the difference in RMSE, the more optimal the number of mixtures selected is. The final number of selected mixtures was 10 (green line). After studying the first results as explained in Section 4.2.4, the sparsity was also modified: increased (between 0.6 and 0.3) to excluded substances with very low contribution to the combined exposure.

Figure 6 Difference in RMSE ratios as a function of the number of mixtures

The 10 obtained mixtures presented in Figure 7 explain 50% of the variance of the co-exposure matrix. The detailed composition of mixture 1, which alone accounts for 30% of the variance, is presented as a pie chart (Figure 8). Mixture 1 is composed of a large number of substances: metals, PFAS and brominated flame retardants. Mixture 2 consists of 7 brominated flame retardants, some metals, a pesticide and PFAS. Mixture 3 consists of 11 metals and 3 pesticides. Mixture 4 consists of 4 pesticides, 1 PFAS and 1 metal. Mixture 5 consists of DEDTP (pesticide) and Ni (metal). Mixture 6 is composed of mostly pesticides. Mixture 7 is composed of PFAS. Mixture 8 contains metals, pesticides and

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brominated flame retardants. Mixture 9 is mainly Au and some other metals. Mixture 10 is mainly composed of PFAS. The detailed composition of mixtures 2 to 9 are presented in 0.

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Figure 7 Matrix U obtained after applying SNMU approach on an ESTEBAN subset. Each column of the mixture matrix represents the composition of a mixture. The substances part of mixture can be identified by colour coding: dark red cells indicate substance that contribute the most to the mixture whereas dark blue cells corresponds to ones that have a slight

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contribution, any other level of contribution can be found using the colour scale (i.e. orange, yellow, green, etc.); a grey cell indicates a non-included substance in the mixture.

Figure 8 Composition of the main mixture (mixture 1) after SNMU analysis on an ESTEBAN subset

A hierarchical clustering was applied on the matrix V representing the individual exposures to the 10 mixtures to cluster individuals regarding their exposure profile to the selected mixtures. There were 3 main clusters containing the main part of the population (and 4 more minor "clusters" with one or two individuals). The results are presented in Figure 9. In this figure we can see the distribution of the 272 individuals in a dendrogram, this dendrogram is then divided into clusters represented by coloured rectangles (cluster numbering is random). Pie charts in Figure 10 show which mixtures the individuals in a cluster are mainly exposed to and in which proportion. For cluster 1 (n = 110 individuals), mixture 1 predominates with mixtures 9, 10, 3, 8, 2, and 4 that also allow to characterise the exposure of individuals in this cluster. Individuals in cluster 2 (n = 37 individuals) seem to be exposed to mixtures 1

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and 10, and to a lesser extent to mixtures 3, 7, 2, 8, 9 and 4. Finally, the exposure of cluster 3 (n = 120 individuals) is characterised by mixtures 1, 3, 8, 2, 9, 4 and 10.

As mixture 1 represents a significant proportion of the exposure for these 3 clusters, it can be prioritised to be studied for its toxic common effects and if relevant to perform risk analysis. These results are very preliminary but give a glimpse of the possibilities of this statistical method which will be applied to a large set of HBM data. Data preparation, choice of subset, choice of SNMU parameters are all parameters that could be refined.

Figure 9 Hierarchical classification with clustering on an ESTEBAN subset.

Figure 10 Cluster exposure to the mixtures identified by SNMU on an ESTEBAN subset.

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5. Effects of prioritized mixtures

5.1. Hazard data for prioritised mixtures and their effects

5.1.1. Grouping chemical in assessment groups

In EFSA Scientific Committee Guidance Document on Scientific criteria for grouping chemicals into assessment groups for human risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals (EFSA et al., 2021b), a framework is proposed to apply hazard-driven criteria for grouping chemicals into assessment groups using mechanistic information on toxicity as the gold standard while also considering toxic potency and toxicokinetic features (e.g., body burden) Figure 11.

Figure 11 Hierarchical process for the application of the hazard-driven criteria for grouping of chemicals (EFSA 2021)

In practice, the lowest uncertainty in grouping can be achieved when knowledge on the adverse outcome pathway (AOP) and/or on the mode of action (MoA) is available for the chemicals under evaluation (Figure 12).

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Figure 12 Conceptual presentation of the mode of action and adverse outcome pathway (EFSA 2021)

AOPs are a conceptual framework for organising, synthesising, and presenting specialised scientific knowledge regarding the linkage between perturbation of a specific biological target, pathway, or process by a stressor, and a consequent adverse outcome(s) (AO) considered relevant to risk assessment, regulatory decision-making, and/or environmental management. They are intended to aggregate knowledge currently dispersed in different sources into a systematic and accessible format that facilitates use of that knowledge to support a broad diversity of applications and interests (<https://aopwiki.org/>). With respect to chemical stressors, the ultimate goal is to collect and understand their mechanism of action to manage chemicals as efficiently and robustly as possible, while protecting human health and the environment.

AOPs are not stressor specific since they describe motifs of biological response to a specific type of biological perturbation. They are linear representations of biological pathways that could apply to a variety of stressors initiating the response(s). They are modular, structured based on key events (KE) and their relationship. An AOP defines a single sequence of biological events leading from a single molecular initiating event (MIE) to a single AO.

Grouping using phenomenological effects or target organ/system toxicity is linked to higher uncertainty. Data-poor chemicals can be included in an assessment group along with data-rich members using ‘*in vitro* or *in silico* bridging data’ as part of the battery of new approach methodologies (NAMs). However, the resulting uncertainty might be relatively high. Structural similarity may also be used as criteria for grouping of chemicals into assessment groups but consideration of more than one feature (i.e., chemical class, common functional groups, common precursor or breakdown products) should be used to increase the confidence in the assessment of similarity of the components. There are also several software tools, such as the OECD QSAR Toolbox, available to support the identification of related substances. Many *in silico* methodologies can be used for this purpose, such as molecular docking and different machine learning tools.

In the present project, the chemicals have been grouped based on relevant common effects highlighted in the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability. PFAS were grouped based on common effects such as immunotoxic and hepatotoxic effects. Even if an AOP network underpinning immunomodulation by PFAS is still lacking, there is substantial evidence from both *in vitro* and *in vivo* experimental studies as well as epidemiology, supporting that various PFAS, not only PFOA and PFOS, affect multiple aspects of the immune system (Ehrlich et al., 2023). In the context of the European (Horizon 2020) project on human biomonitoring in Europe (HBM4EU), an AOP for 4 toxic metals inducing nephrotoxicity in humans was developed (HBM4EU, 2022). The focus was on the following metals: arsenic (As), cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb) and mercury (Hg). The common adverse outcome was identified as renal dysfunction due to proximal tubular damage. In short, in the AOP, thiol binding was identified as the molecular initiating event (MIE), followed by the key events (KEs) oxidative stress and mitochondrial dysfunction (KE1), cytochrome c release (KE2) and apoptosis (KE3) leading to the aforementioned adverse outcome. In the case of developmental neurotoxicity (DNT), this is an

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overarching adverse outcome that may be induced by pre- and/or postnatal exposure to diverse chemicals families, e.g., certain pesticides, heavy metals or metalloids, food-contact materials, etc. Given the complexity of DNT and the wide variety of DNT endpoints, it was considered to start by grouping metal(oid)s prioritized based on regulatory needs. These include lead, methylmercury and inorganic arsenic. Pesticides, such as organophosphates, carbamates and pyrethroids, affecting the nervous system were considered in two groups: pesticides associated with brain and/or erythrocyte AChE inhibition (CAG-NAN) and pesticides associated with functional alterations of the motor division of the nervous system (CAG-NAM).

5.1.2. Overall strategy to set hazard value for the common selected effect

One main challenge after grouping substances into mixture assessment groups is to collect the toxicological value (TV) (including or not including uncertainty factors (UFs)) associated to the selected common effect to perform the risk assessment. Where the whole mixture approach is applied, the toxicological value of the whole mixture must be collected (Section 6.1). Where a component-based approach is applied, the toxicological value of each chemical composing the mixture must be collected to apply the dose-addition hypothesis (Section 6.1). Until today, risk assessment was mainly performed comparing exposure from one source (e.g., diet) with an external health-based guidance value (HBGV). HBGVs are established substance by substance and mainly derived from animal studies with consideration of the appropriate uncertainty factor (UF) on a reference point (RPe.g., NOAEL or BMDL) for the critical effect which corresponds to the most sensitive endpoint. HBGV were recently organised in the OpenFoodTox database of EFSA (Kovarich et al., 2022). As the use of HBM data to perform risk assessments is rather recent (HBM4EU), the establishment and collection of an internal toxicological value such as a Human Biomonitoring Guidance Value, HBM-GV (internal reference point for the critical effect with UF) is still at its early stages and some methods must be applied to compensate the absence of HBM-GV. Another point is that the HBGV or the HBM-GV are established from the critical effect which can differ from the selected common effect of the mixture. In that case, the RP for that common effect will be used in combination with a corresponding UF.

Different risk metrics presented in Section 6.2 can be used to assess the risk from external or internal doses depending on the availability of the hazard data. When an HBM-GV is available from one mixture component for the common effect and internal (or external) RPFs are available for the others, risk assessment can be performed using the RPF approach. This is the case of the PFAS case studies. When no RPFs are available, the ratio between the HBM exposure and the HBM-TV must be calculated for each mixture component. Four cases are considered in Figure 14 to set HBM-TV for the common effect from internal (best case) to external (worst case) hazard metric:

- when an HBM-GV is available (orange): if the critical effect of the HBM-GV coincides with the common effect, this value can be used as HBM-TV,

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- when an internal RP (HBM-RP) is available (purple): if a HBM-RP exists for the common effect, an HBM-TV can be built by applying UFs,
- when an HBGV is available (blue): if a HBGV exists for the common effect, an HBM-TV can be built by applying FUE/PBPK models to convert it in an internal dose,
- when an external RP is available (blue): if a RP exists for the common effect, an HBM-TV can be built by applying FUE/PBPK models and UFs to convert it in internal dose.

When only external hazard data are available (HBGV or RP), forward and reverse dosimetry approaches can be used to make a comparison with HBM exposure possible (Section 9.1.2). The first approach is 1) to apply reverse dosimetry to HBM data on chemical or metabolite concentrations in the biological matrices, such as blood or urine, to estimate the external exposure and compare with the corresponding external HBGV (or RP when the HBGV is not specific for the selected common effect). The second approach, 2) to apply forward dosimetry to transform the external HBGV (or RP) into an internal HBM-GV (or internal reference point: an HBM-RP) and compare it directly with the internal concentration(s) of the chemical or metabolite(s). In both approaches, toxicokinetic information of the chemicals and their (main) metabolites is needed. In some circumstances, a fraction of urinary excretion (FUE) can be applied to estimate the external exposure to the parent chemical from the concentration of the biomarkers excreted in urine and vice versa. More details are given in Section 7 on kinetic and FUE. Both reverse and forward dosimetry approach were tested in the case studies on pesticides (Section 9.1, Figure 13).

Figure 14. Overall strategy to set HBM-TV for the common effect. The colours indicate how to follow the information in the different boxes.

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5.1.3. HBM-GV database

To facilitate risk assessment of real-life mixtures, an overview was created containing all relevant information concerning the internal health-based guidance values (HBM-GV) of chemicals that were prioritised within the PARC-partnership. This overview includes the following information per type of chemical substance:

- Trivial name of substance, CAS-identification number, and chemical group (pesticide, metal, metalloid, organic pollutant).
- The biomarker measured (some chemicals might be measured through multiple metabolites, e.g., biomarker for chlorpyrifos can both be chlorpyrifos or 3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol), as well as the matrix in which this biomarker was measured (e.g., blood, urine, or other matrix)
- The population group for which the guidance values were developed (children, adults, entire population, specific age groups, workers).
- The type of internal guidance values that were derived (e.g., BE-values, HBM-values, HBM-I and -II values, RfDs, DNELs, etc.)
- The critical endpoint (e.g., neurotoxicity, nephrotoxicity) for which the internal guidance values were derived, as well as additional detail on critical endpoint (e.g., type of neurotoxicity).
- All information related to the derivation of the internal guidance value: the type of study (human or animal), the point of departure (NOAEL, LOAEL, BMDL) and concentration (e.g., NOAEL of 1 mg/kg/day) used to derive the internal guidance value. But also, the uncertainty or assessment factors that were used and their justification (e.g., UF of 100 for intraspecies and interspecies variation). If external guidance values were used for the derivation of internal guidance values, then these are also listed, and more specifically, the type (e.g., RfD, TDI, MRL), the actual value, and the effect type (threshold vs non-threshold type of effect).
- All guidance values that were reported were furthermore supplemented with the source and time of publication (e.g., EFSA, WHO). This facilitates data selection for mixtures risk assessment, since guidance values from outdated reports are more easily filtered out.
- Finally, alternative endpoints different from the critical endpoint are also as given if available, as well as any other additional information mentioned in the publications that might be useful.

Through this overview, potential mixture groups can for example be identified based on a common critical endpoint for which the internal guidance values of those substances were derived. Moreover, by also reporting the source and time of publication, priority can be given to more recent guidance values published by reputable authorities such as EFSA, ECHA, WHO or the US-EPA compared to more outdated and/or single scientific studies. Finally, synergies regarding the work on HBM-GVs will be sought with members from PARC Task 4.1.

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5.2. Use of biomarkers of effect/health effects to study association with prioritised mixture exposures

This part aims to study the association between mixture exposure and biomarkers of effect or health effects in the HBM studies. For that, a working group of 6 partners (VITO, ANSES, AU, NIPH, UU-IRAS, WR-BIOM) was created. Partners in this group will work on common methods applied to their datasets, the studies involved in this analysis are described in Appendix 2.

5.2.1. Description of selected case studies

Regarding the biomarkers of effect and health effects available in the surveys of the partners involved in this part, 4 case studies described below have been selected. Other case studies might be defined later, for example cancer or genotoxic risk could be analysed in occupational studies with data on genotoxicity and inflammatory effect markers.

5.2.1.1. Thyroid and sex hormones

ACCEPT, AU-PH

The Greenlandic ACCEPT birth cohort has been described in Section 3.1.3.

Data on estrogenic and androgenic activities of real-life lipophilic POP mixtures extracted from the serum are available.

For 132 participants included in 2010-2011, thyroid hormone levels are available including thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH), Total Thyroxine (TT4), and Total Triiodothyronine (TT3).

FETOTOX-ABC, AU-PH

The Aarhus Birth Cohort Biobank (ABC) involving 1533 pregnant women study has been described in Section 3.1.3.

Data on estrogenic and androgenic activities (free of endogenous hormones) of the real-life lipophilic POP mixtures extracted from the serum are available, as well as the combined estrogenic activities of the real-life PFAS mixtures extracted from serum.

Hormone levels in early pregnancy (before week 14) are available including thyroid hormones (thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH), free thyroxine (FT4) and thyroid peroxidase antibodies (TPO-Ab)) and sex hormones (dihydrotestosterone (DHT), estradiol, estrone and estrone sulphate).

Effect of extracted real-life mixtures on estrogenic & androgenic activities and thyroid hormone function (experimental work), AU-PH

AU-PH developed SPE-HPLC-(WAX) methods for extraction of the actual real-life mixture of lipophilic POP and real-life mixture of PFAS present in human serum and tissues (e.g., placenta) with simultaneously removal of endogenous hormones. The current established methods include

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estrogenic and androgenic activities of extracted real-life lipophilic POP mixtures and estrogenic activities of extracted real-life PFAS mixtures.

Currently, further development of the extraction SPE-HPLC method for measurement of the androgenic activities of real-life PFAS mixtures with simultaneous removal of endogenous hormones has been worked on. A plan to develop the extraction method for measurement of effects on the thyroid hormone function of real-life lipophilic POP mixtures and real-life PFAS mixtures was established.

NEB II, NIPH

In NEB II (7-14 years, n=650, Norway), thyroid hormones (TSH, FT3, FT4), cardiometabolic hormones (leptin, insulin, adiponectin), lipoproteins (apolipoprotein A1, lipoprotein A, apolipoprotein B), lipids (HDL/LDL cholesterol, triglycerides, phospholipids) liver status (ALAT, ASAT), and sex hormones (FSH, LH, estradiol, testosterone) were measured in serum and plasma of around 650 children and adolescents. The following common exposure biomarkers (above 60% LOD) were measured in blood samples: brominated flame retardants, PCBs, organochlorines pesticides, and PFAS. In urine, acrylamide, phthalates, phenols, organophosphate pesticides and flame retardants were also measured. Information on potential confounders such as sex, age, maternal age at delivery, household education, passive smoking, and diet, were obtained from questionnaires.

FLEHS, VITO

In two newborn campaigns of the Flemish Environment and Health Study (FLEHS II and III; Section 3.1.3 for a general description), thyroid hormones (TSH, FT3, FT4), cardiometabolic hormones (leptin, insulin), and sexual hormones (FSH, LH, estradiol, testosterone) were measured in cord blood of around 500 newborns. The following common exposure biomarkers were measured in the cord samples of both FLEHS campaigns: metals, flame retardants, PCBs, organochlorines, and PFAS. Information on potential confounders such as sex, gestational age, maternal age at delivery, maternal pre-pregnancy body mass index, parity, and maternal smoking during pregnancy, were obtained from questionnaires.

5.2.1.2. Blood pressure

FLEHS, VITO

Blood pressure was measured in 14-15-year-old adolescents in two campaigns of the Flemish Environment and Health Study (FLEHS III and IV; Section 3.1.3 for a general description). Five consecutive blood pressure measurements are available for around 1000 participants. The following exposure biomarkers were measured in blood or urine samples of adolescents in both FLEHS campaigns: metals, flame retardants, PCBs, organochlorines, PAHs, and phthalates. Questionnaire data will be used to adjust for potential confounders such as age, sex, body mass index, socio-economic status, physical activity, smoking, and alcohol consumption.

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ESTEBAN, Anses

The ESTEBAN study has been described in Section 3.1.3. Blood pressure was measured in 2116 adults (45% of men and 55% women). The mean age was 50.9 years (from 18 to 73 years). Mean systolic blood pressure and mean diastolic blood pressure have been measured. A wide variety of exposure biomarkers have been measured for these adults however the biomarkers were analysed in subsets of individuals, i.e., these biomarkers were not measured in every individual. The following exposure biomarkers were measured in blood, urine, or hair: metals, bisphenols, pesticides, cotinine, herbicides, mycotoxins, PAH, parabens, phthalates, pyrethroids, dioxins, PFAS, flame retardants.

5.2.1.3. Immune effects

MoBa, NIPH

In two sub-cohorts of the Norwegian Mother, Father and Child (MoBa) – NEB II and HELIX (7-14 years, n = 950, Norway) –PFAS have been measured in maternal blood from week 17 to represent prenatal exposure and current PFAS exposure for children/teenagers (aged 7-14 years). Vaccine antibodies for MMR (Measles, Mumps, and Rubella) and DTP (diphtheria, tetanus and polio) have been assessed in children/teenagers. Data on other persistent pollutants (PCBs, organochlorine pesticides, brominated flame retardants) also have been explored, as well as information on potential confounders such as sex, gestational age, maternal age at delivery, maternal pre-pregnancy body mass index, parity, and maternal smoking during pregnancy from questionnaires. These data are to be analysed under Norwegian Research Council Funding in summer 2023, and the results are relevant to the risk assessment of PFAS for immune effect (Bil et al., 2023a).

FLEHS, VITO

Total count of leucocytes and of leucocyte subtypes in peripheral blood are established biomarkers of an inflammatory immune response. Exploring the associations of environmental exposures with differential leucocyte counts is critical to understand their impacts on the human immune system (Gao et al., 2019). Leucocyte data are available for around 1000 14 to 15-year adolescents recruited in two campaigns of the Flemish Environment and Health Study (FLEHS III and IV; Section 3.1.3 for a general description). Total leucocyte count and leucocyte subtype distribution (percentage of neutrophils, monocytes, lymphocytes) were assessed using a (Sysmex XE-2100) instrument for haematology analysis, which combines flow cytometry with fluorescence detection. Counts of leucocyte subtypes were subsequently calculated by multiplying the subtype percentage with the total leucocyte count. The following exposure biomarkers were measured in blood or urine samples of adolescents in both FLEHS campaigns: metals, flame retardants, PCBs, organochlorines, PAHs, and phthalates. Information on potential confounders such as age, sex, body mass index, socio-economic status, and recent health

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complaints, is obtained from questionnaires. PFAS measurements for adolescents are available in FLEHS IV.

5.2.1.4. ALS and Parkinson

Two nested case-control studies defined within the prospective EPIC (European Prospective Investigation into Cancer and Nutrition) cohort will be analysed. This cohort is a large prospective study initiated in 1992 that was designed to investigate the relationship between diet, lifestyle, and environmental factors and the incidence of cancer and other chronic diseases. Recruitment took place between 1993 and 1999. In total, more than half a million (520,000) people, with the vast majority aged between 35 and 70 years, were recruited in 10 European countries: Denmark, France, Germany, Greece, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, Spain, Sweden, and the United Kingdom. Data on diet and lifestyle were obtained through structured questionnaires at baseline. At the same time, anthropometric measurements and blood samples were taken. Outcomes included are Parkinson's disease and Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis. Cases were identified through death certificates. Metal levels in erythrocyte samples obtained at recruitment, were analysed as a biomarker for metal exposure (arsenic, cadmium, copper, lead, manganese, mercury, selenium, and zinc) from any source. The study populations comprise of ~100 cases and 300 controls matched for age, sex, and study centre.

5.2.2. Comparison of statistical methods

Using single-substance models to evaluate the health effects of chemical agents that occur in mixtures is problematic because it ignores potential confounding by other substances in the mixture and does not allow for identification of interactions between substances or evaluation of an overall mixture effect. With a small set of exposures or a large dataset, the classical multiple linear regression (MLR) model can be used to estimate both main effects and interactions in many cases, although estimates may be too imprecise to be useful when there are strong correlations between exposures.

We distinguish between the following inferential goals when studying the effects of exposure mixtures:

1. What is the overall mixture effect?
2. What are the contributions from each individual substance (what is the shape of the exposure-response relation)?
3. Are there any interactions with other substances (what do they look like)?

To answer these questions, we suggest using a combination of different approaches that are listed in order of increasing usefulness (making fewer assumptions), but also of increasing computational complexity to implement the algorithms correctly.

5.2.2.1. Regularised regression (LASSO)

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When effect estimates from a MLR model are imprecise, a possible solution is to use a penalised regression model, which adds a penalty to the size of the parameter estimates, shrinking them towards zero. Several different types of penalties can be used, but the most well-known and widely used is the Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator (LASSO), which results in many coefficients to be estimated to be exactly zero, effectively removing the corresponding variables from the model. The size of the penalty is chosen using cross-validation. The main advantages of this model are that it can be used with large datasets and many substances and runs relatively quickly. Disadvantages are that the model does not allow for non-linear effects or interactions (at least not without further modifications) and that the output provides no information regarding the precision of effect estimates or the stability of the model. The latter can be investigated using the so-called stability selection algorithm. LASSO penalised regression and cross-validation are implemented in the R package *glmnet*, while stability selection of LASSO models is implemented in the R package *stabs*.

5.2.2.2. Weighted Quantile Sums (WQS)

WQS regression aims to estimate an overall mixture effect by creating a summary score of the (quantile scores of) mixture components in a supervised fashion, using weights that are constrained to sum to 1 and where the weights for individual chemicals are bounded to be between 0 and 1. The weights are estimated using bootstrapping and the significance of the mixture effect estimated using hold-out validation. The estimated weights are often used directly to assess the importance of individual mixture components, but for more complete inference repeated hold-out validation should be used to assess the stability of the weights. There have been several extensions of the original algorithm, including a Bayesian formulation. WQS regression is implemented in the R package *gWQS*.

5.2.2.3. Random-Forest (RF)

The RF model is an example of an ensemble learning algorithm, i.e., an algorithm that combines the output from several different models to obtain a better overall model. The base models that make up the random forest are simple decision trees. By averaging predictions from (deep) decision trees that each individually tend to have low bias, but high variance, we obtain a predictor that has low bias and low variance, which explains the popularity of the approach. Compared to WQS and LASSO models, RF models allow for much easier estimation of models that allow for non-linear substance effects and interactions. There are several hyperparameters that can (and should) be tuned, but RF tuning is generally regarded to be relatively easy when compared to other Machine Learning algorithms with only a few important parameters. The flexibility of RF can also be (and often is) a disadvantage, in that summarising the estimated effects and interactions can be challenging. Importance of individual substances can be assessed using Variable Importance Scores (VIMPs), but as with the weights in WQS, the precision of these is hard to evaluate. The RF is implemented in the package *Ranger*, with tuning algorithms provided in the R package *tuneRanger*. Visualisation of estimated exposure-response relations can be implemented using Shapley values as implemented in the package *fastshap*.

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5.2.2.4. Bayesian Kernel Machine regression (BKMR)

The main idea of BKMR is to model exposure effects and interactions using kernel basis expansions. A detailed explanation of kernels and basis expansion methods is beyond the scope of the current note, but a heuristic interpretation is that model predictions are created by weighting observed outcomes, with high(er) weights for outcomes from individuals that have exposure profiles that are similar (in a sense defined by both the type of kernel used and its estimated parameters) to those for which a prediction is required. As with the RF, exposure-response relations and interactions are estimated indirectly and can be hard to evaluate or visualise. BKMR provides both an estimate of the mixture effect and estimates of variable importance (Posterior Inclusion Probabilities; PIPs). The model is implemented in the R package *bkmr*, while additional functionality that allows more critical evaluation of model convergence is provided in the R package *bkmrhat*.

5.2.2.5. Causal effect estimation

Under the assumption that estimated effects for individual substances and/or mixtures reflect causal relation and with suitable data, most of the methods listed above can be modified to estimate marginal causal effects rather than the usual conditional effects. These methods have been implemented in R packages *qgcomp* (WQS), *grf* (RF), but are available also as scripts for LASSO-based approaches and BKMR.

5.2.2.6. SNMU

The SNMU approach described in Section 4.2.4 can be used to study the association between multiple exposure and biomarker of effect. The output mixtures identified in applying the SNMU on co-exposure to substances can be used as input of epidemiological models to study the link with health effects. The models will be adjusted on potential confounding variables such as socio-economic variables, food consumption of specific food items (salt, fish, vegetables, alcohol, etc.) and physical activity.

6. Mixture risk assessment

6.1. Whole mixture and component-based approach

Two approaches are currently proposed (EFSA et al., 2019b): the whole mixture approach and the component-based approach. In the whole mixture approach, the mixture is treated as a single entity, similar to a single chemical, and so requires dose-response information for the mixture of concern or a sufficiently similar substance using read across methods. The whole mixture approach is particularly

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required with mixtures whose composition is unknown or difficult to characterise. It is also useful to apply this approach when the mixture is well known and stable over time, such as commercial formulations. The main limitation is that the results are specific to the mixture or a sufficiently similar one and cannot be used for other mixtures.

The component-based approach can be applied when the mixture components are detailed. This is defined as an approach in which the risk of a mixture is assessed based on the exposure and effect data of its individual components (EFSA, 2013c). Application of the component-based approach therefore requires exposure and effect data on the individual mixture components.

Three types of mixture effect are distinguished:

- Dose or concentration addition for the substances with similar modes of action: the mixture effect can be predicted by the sum of each single substance exposure present in the mixture, weighted by their toxic potency (Van den Berg, Birnbaum and Bosveld, 1998).
- Response addition for substances with independent dissimilar modes of action. In this case, the statistical concept developed by Bliss (1939) can be used to predict the effect :

$$R_{\text{mix}} = 1 - \prod_{i=1}^n (1 - R_i)$$
where R is the toxicological response for the mixture or the chemical i expressed in probability or fraction taking value between 0 and 1.
- Interaction, which is observed when the mixture effect is higher (synergism or potentiation) or lower (antagonism) than the sum of each single substance effect (Lederer, Dijkstra and Heskes, 2019).

However, data on the mode and mechanism of action of chemical substances are sparse. Based on scientific literature, comparing the combined effects induced by exposure to multiple substances with similar and independent (dis-similar) actions (Faust et al., 2001, 2003; Jonker et al., 2004; Junghans et al., 2006; Kortenkamp, Backhaus and Faust, 2009; Backhaus and Faust, 2012; EFSA, 2013c, 2013a; Altenburger et al., 2013; EFSA et al., 2019b; Martin et al., 2021; Van Der Ven et al., 2022; Kortenkamp et al., 2022), dose addition was established as the default hypothesis recommended by several institutions for mixture risk assessment (WHO/IPCS, 2009a; Meek et al., 2011; SCHER, SCCS and SCENIHR, 2012; EFSA, 2013c; Altenburger et al., 2013). Importantly, the dose-addition approach estimates the combined effects of substances with similar actions and ensures adequate conservatism in the case of independent actions, as it tends to overestimate the combined effects (Faust et al., 2003). Moreover, at relatively low exposure levels, i.e., around the NOAELxUF or at maximum residue limits (MRLs) when it relates to dietary exposure to pesticide residues, it was observed that toxicologically relevant interactions were uncommon (EFSA et al., 2019b). The dose addition approach also applies at low levels of exposure, when no information is available on the mode of action or dose-response relationship. As potential interaction between co-occurring pesticide residues in food cannot be fully excluded, it should be considered on a case-by-case basis. According a review of 90 studies that reported evidence of synergy in mammalian test systems performed at low doses (i.e., close to the POD) for individual chemicals (Boobis et al., 2011), only 6 studies provided useful quantitative

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information on the magnitude of synergy and indicated that the difference between observed synergisms and predictions by dose-addition did not deviate by more than a factor of 4.

Therefore, in practice, dose addition is the default hypothesis recommended by EFSA to assess the risk of mixtures, in accordance with WHO/IPCS (2009a). In the case studies of this project, the risk assessment will be based on the component-based approach using the hazard of each chemical and considering the dose addition (DA) model.

6.2. Risk metrics

Several component-based risk metrics related to dose-addition have been published (EFSA, 2013c; EFSA et al., 2019b; Kortenkamp, Backhaus and Faust, 2009; Meek et al., 2011; Sarigiannis and Hansen, 2012; Vejdovszky et al., 2019; WHO/IPCS, 2009b; WHO, 2017). They involve summing over all S substances in the mixture, the ratios of exposure level (EL) to a toxicological value (TV) to calculate a risk index $\sum_{s=1}^S \frac{EL_s}{TV_s}$ or the sum of the inverse ratios $\sum_{s=1}^S \frac{TV_s}{EL_s}$ to calculate a total margin of exposure (MOE). The TV may or may not include the uncertainty factor (UF). For example, the hazard index (HI, Hazard index) is defined as the sum of the hazard quotients (HQ, Hazard quotient) of the individual components of a mixture, where each of the hazard quotients is calculated as the ratio of exposure level of the substance to the health-based guidance value (HBGV associated with the critical effect (e.g., ADI, Acceptable Daily Intake, ARfD, Acute Reference Dose). As the HI is based on the critical effect (corresponding to the most sensitive effect) and this may differ from substance to substance, it should only be used as a first step to decide whether it is necessary to assess the mixture more precisely by focusing on a common effect. The Reference Point Index (RPI), also known as the Point of Departure Index (PODI), focuses on the same common effect and is calculated as the sum of the exposure level (EL_s) for each substance 's' divided by the reference point of substance 's' (RP_s), which can be a LOAEL/NOAEL or a BMDL for example. This is equivalent to the inverse of the sum of the MOEs of each individual substance, called the combined margin of exposure (MOET):

$$RPI = PODI = \sum_{s=1}^S \frac{EL_s}{RP_s} = \dots = \sum_{s=1}^S \frac{1}{MOE_s} = \frac{1}{MOET}$$

Where, $MOE_s = \frac{RP_s}{EL_s}$.

The mixture margin of exposure (MOE) can also be calculated as the ratio of the starting point of an index compound to the cumulative exposure, weighted by relative toxicity factors (RPFs, Relative

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Potency Factors) or toxic equivalency factors (TEFs, Toxic Equivalent Factors, WHO/IPCS 1998, US-EPA 1989):

$$MOE_{Index} = \frac{RP_{Index}}{CumE} \quad \text{where } CumE = \sum_{s=1}^S EL_s \times RPF_s \quad \text{and } RPF_s = \frac{RP_{Index}}{RP_s}$$

The RPI and MOE(T) of the mixture are then compared to the uncertainty factor (UF) established for the data. Thus, risk can be ruled out if $RPI < UF$ or $MOE(T) > UF$. In the case of measurements from different studies and with different protocols, it is not always possible to apply a single UF. However, if in the case of pesticides, the data are sufficiently homogeneous to be able to use a single UF. Therefore, Vejdovsky et al. 2019 proposed to modify the reference point index by an mRPI also called adjusted point of departure index (PODIadj) (WHO, 2020), by introducing a UF for each substance directly into the equation:

$$mRPI = PODI_{adj} = \sum_{s=1}^S \frac{EL_s \times UFs}{RP_s} = \sum_{s=1}^S \frac{EL_s}{TV_s} \quad \text{where TV includes here the UF.}$$

An mRPI value greater than 1 indicates that the risk cannot be ruled out.

When using HBM data, risk calculation must be performed from HBM-GV, and risk metrics must be adapted. The approach to set HBM-GV was developed in Section 5.1.2.

To select one of the risk metrics, we propose to consider the heterogeneity of the collected data (human, animal, *in vitro*), heterogeneity of UF values, and the type of available endpoints (most sensitive effect, specific effect, mode of action, etc.). Table 4 summarises the different component-based risk metrics with the input data, the associated requirement and uses and their use in the prioritised case studies.

Table 4 Summary the different component-based risk metrics with the input data, the associated requirement and uses and their use in the prioritised case studies

Risk metric	Effect	Toxicological value External Internal	Uncertainty factor (UF)	Equation	No risk	Requirement	Case studies
HI	Critical	HBGV - HBM-GV	Included	$HI = \sum_{s=1}^S HQ_s = \sum_{s=1}^S \frac{EL_s}{HBGV_s}$	<1	Very low tier	
RPI (PODI)	Common	RP(POD) - HBM-RP(POD)	Excluded	$\sum_{s=1}^S \frac{EL_s}{RP_s}$	< 1/UF	Need a unique UF	

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MOET	Common	RP(POD) - HBM-RP(POD)	Excluded	$MOET = \frac{1}{\sum_{s=1}^S \frac{1}{MOE_s}}$ $MOE_s = \frac{RP_s}{EL_s}$	> UF	Need a unique UF	Pesticides
MOE _{Index} (using RPF)	Common	RP(POD) - HBM-RP(POD)	Excluded	$MOE_{Index} = \frac{RP_{Index}}{CumEL}$ $CumEL = \sum_{s=1}^S EL_s \times RPF_s$ $RPF_s = \frac{RP_{Index}}{RP_s}$	> UF _{Index}	RPF must be based on comparable dose-responses Need a unique UF	
mRPI (POD _{adj})	Common	RP(POD) - HBM-RP(POD)	Included	$mRPI = \sum_{s=1}^S \frac{EL_s}{RP_s / UF_s}$ $= \sum_{s=1}^S \frac{EL_s}{TV_s}$	<1	TV includes the specific UF	Metals

6.3. Derivation of RPFs

Nowadays, RPFs are based on Benchmark Doses (BMDs) of chemicals (belonging to a mixture) if dose-response data are suitable. The Relative Potency Factor (RPF) is the ratio of the BMD of an index (or reference) compound compared with a given substance (s).

$$RPF = \frac{BMD_{Index}}{BMD_s}$$

To derive RPFs, several conditions must be met: 1) the same endpoint should be considered; 2) the dose response curves should be parallel (on a log-dose scale); 3) the compounds should not interact, i.e., dose addition applies; and 4) RPFs should be derived from experiments with (very) similar experimental setups to avoid different setups and conditions that influence the derived potency differences (Fournier et al., 2016, 2017). The second condition is of particular importance because only when curves are parallel, the RPF is not dose-dependent (i.e., does not change at the different exposure levels), therefore the same RPF can be applied to all doses of a compound to derive its equivalent reference compound dose (Van den Brand et al, 2022).

Note that each compound can serve as an index compound because RPFs will be proportional with either choice. Notably, the RPF does not depend on the value of BMR, given that the dose-response curves are parallel on a log-dose scale (Van der Ven et al, 2022).

Thus, to use RPF for risk assessment the four conditions cited above need to apply.

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7. Physiologically Based Kinetic models for prioritised mixtures

7.1. Generic and/or specific models

In recent years, Physiologically Based Kinetic (PBK, also PBPK or PBTk) models have been used in the context of risk assessment (Doerge et al., 2008; Hinderliter et al., 2011; Tan et al., 2007; Teeguarden et al., 2005; WHO, 2010) to determine biomonitoring equivalents (BE) relevant as regulatory threshold values linked with HBM data. These models use mathematical descriptions of physiological traits (tissue volumes, blood flow, etc.) and biochemical reactions (Michaelis Menten kinetics with V_{max} , K_m , etc.) to describe the chemical mass fluxes between interconnected body compartments (organs and blood). These mathematical equations describe the absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion (ADME) of substances in the body over time. PBK models can predict the concentration (or dose, amount, area under the curve) of a substance and its metabolite(s) in a target tissue based on a given exposure scenario, also called forward dosimetry using available input parameter values (Section 9.1.2). They can also be used in reverse dosimetry, where PBK models predict the external exposure (or external dose) from the internal concentration, often obtained from biological samples collected in HBM surveys (blood or urine samples for example). In both cases, modelling results can be used to refine the safety levels, either as exposure concentration or tissue concentration under which no adverse effect is expected according to the state-of-the-art knowledge. PBK models can also compare subgroups of population, characterise inter-individual variability, quantifying uncertainties, perform extrapolations, and support read-across between similar substances by comparing their concentration kinetic profiles.

PBK models can be generic or specific (Pletz et al., 2020). Generic PBK models use the same compartmental structure for all substances (or family) and are often available on risk assessment platforms. This type of models allows fits or simulations of multiple substances at once and simplifies mixture risk assessment (MRA). On the other hand, substance-specific PBK models consider detailed substance properties and modes of action to predict substance distribution to target organs and formation of metabolite(s). Specific models are generally more complex to use (often not available on platforms) and take much longer time to simulate time-concentration profiles compared to a generic model.

Figure 15 presents the workflow that will be followed in this project to provide easy tools to perform PBK modelling for risk assessment. Depending on the risk assessment needs, a generic or specific model may be used. For instance, if the purpose of the analysis is to link concentrations of substances in mixtures in blood or urine collected in biomonitoring data to recalculate the external exposure of the population, then a generic or specific model could be used. To determine which model will be used in this case, it is necessary to check if, for all the substances in the mixture, the outputs between the generic and specific models are similar (e.g., comparison of the simulated toxicokinetic profiles from the generic model against the TK profiles from the specific model after the same external chronic exposure in input).

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Conversely, if the purpose is to obtain detailed information on target organs (e.g., area-under-curve (AUC) or concentrations over time) to better establish the link with the effects, then a specific model will be preferably used to account for all the processes linked to the substances in the mixture.

All PBK models that will be used in this project (generic and specific) will be implemented in the PARC toolbox developed in T8.3. Once this step is completed, instructions will be distributed by T8.3 partners and Kinetics WG partners (e.g., which models to select depending on the substances in the mixture, how to run the model with HBM data, parameters to be selected or used to run the model, etc.).

In the final step, HBM data owners will be able to use the PBK model depending on the policy question to be answered with a user-friendly tool developed in T8.3.

Figure 15 Workflow to determine the use of generic or specific model in regards of regulatory needs.

In MRA, a generic model should be used in priority over specific models for the reasons mentioned above (Pletz et al., 2020). Several generic models are available today to perform PBK modelling on HBM data: Stochastic Human Exposure and Dose Simulation (SHEDS) model, ConsEXPO, EUSES, MCRA, Integra, IndusChemFate, HBM Simulator, MerlinExpo, and R/Httk. The aim was to compare model outputs by the generic model with the ones generated by specific models for the prioritised chemical groups using equal or similar parameter values as inputs for both models. For the generic model, the MCRA platform has been used with the implemented generic PBK model (Tebby et al., 2020; van der Voet et al., 2020) to analyse HBM data. When needed, specific models will be developed by the activity 6.2.2 (WP6). At the end, generic and specific models will be available on the PARC model network.

Depending on the substance considered, the choice to use a generic or specific model can be determined by the comparison of the outputs of these two types of models. If similar outputs are obtained for the same exposure scenario, the generic model is preferred. Conversely, if the outputs are different, then underlying reasons are discussed and the model representing best the substances

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ADME processes is selected. In the first step, similar parameter values between generic and specific model are applied. In the second step, several goodness-of-fit criteria are used, such as fits to data and numeric indicators (e.g., root-mean-square error (RMSE)). The exposure scenario considered for the comparison is an acute and/or chronic oral ingestion. Different outputs are generated depending on the substance (i.e., concentrations in blood and urine) and criteria such as the maximal concentration or the concentration at the steady state are used to compare model outputs.

7.2. Parametrisation of PBK models

7.2.1. PBK generic model description

The generic model is the one published by Tebby et al. (2020) and implemented in the MCRA platform (Figure 16). Three routes of exposure can be considered: dermal, ingestion and inhalation. Substances can be excreted via urine, exhaled through the lung, or metabolised in the liver. Urine and gut lumen are not modelled as interconnected compartments within the PBK model as they are assumed to be external compartments.

The model includes 14 physiological parameters for adult human and incorporates up to 14 substance specific parameters such as absorption rates, partition coefficients, and hepatic clearances. If metabolism is modelled as first-order rate rather than Michaelis-Menten kinetics, then the number of substance-specific parameters decreases to 13. More details are provided on the supplementary information, as well as the associated code (Tebby et al., 2020).

Figure 16 Summary of the PBK generic model.

7.2.2. Workflow

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To facilitate the comparison between generic and specific models and their use in risk assessment, the physiological and biochemical parameters for the generic model in MCRA were collected for the selected prioritised substances (PFAS, metals, pesticides and mycotoxins).

Physiological parameters that are provided in MCRA at the moment are specifically for adults. Focusing on this age group as a first step, only substance-specific parameters will change according to the substance. The HBM4EU project has analysed the parameterisation of human PBPK models for some of priority substances (DON, arsenic, lead, methylmercury, several pyrethroids, chlorpyrifos). From this output, combined with additional literature search, a table was created to collect substance-specific parameters for each prioritised substances or chemical group, in an harmonize way and aimed at facilitating their addition in the PARC toolbox (Table 5). For each selected and attributed parameter, the associated scientific publication was added. In addition, MCRA users have the possibility to provide the coefficient of variation and uncertainty, which are of importance to inform on the variability in and uncertainty of the model output. Physiological and biochemical parameters will be updated in the future according to the age group or sub-population of interest in this project (e.g., children, pregnant women, etc.).

Table 5. Example for pyrethroids parameters collection to be used for the generic PBK model implemented in MCRA.

	parameter	Substance		Pyrethroids			
		meaning	units	value (mean)	reference	Cv Variability	Cv Uncertainty
Physiological parameters	scVFat	Fat as fraction of total body volume	unitless	0.209	Birnbaum 1994, Brown 1997	0.2	0.2
	scVRich	Richly perfused organs as fraction of total body volume	unitless	0.105		0.2	0.2
	scVLiver	Liver as fraction of total body volume	unitless	0.024		0.2	0.2
	scVBlood	Blood as fraction of total body volume	unitless	0.068	Davies 1993	0.2	0.2 combine with additional
	scFFat	Fat fraction of total blood flow going to compartments	unitless	0.0850	Birnbaum 1994, Brown 1997	0.2	0.2
	scFPoor	Poorly perfused tissues fraction of total blood flow going to compartments	unitless	0.120		0.2	0.2

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		scFLiver	Liver fraction of total blood flow going to compartments	unitless	0.270		0.2	0.2
		scFSkin	Skin fraction of total blood flow going to compartments	unitless	0.0500		0.2	0.2
		scFBlood	total blood flow (cardiac output)	L/h/kg	4.8	Davies 1993	1.2	1.2
		Height_sc	stratum corneum	dm	0.0001	Russell 2008		
		Height_vs	viabile skin	dm	0.0122	Birnbaum 1994, Brown 1997		
		Falv	alveolar ventilation rate	L/h	2220	Brown 1997	1.2	1.2
		mic	microsomal proteins content	mg/gr liver	52.5	Godin 2006		
Substance specific parameters	absorption	kGut	oral 1st order absorption rate constant	1/h	0.52	Quindroit 2019	2	3
		Frac (female)	Absorbed fraction in gut	unitless	0.7	Quindroit 2019	0.2	0.2
		Frac (male)	Absorbed fraction in gut	unitless	0.7	Quindroit 2019	0.2	0.2
		Kp_sc_vs	diffusion rate from stratum corneum to viable skin	decim / h	1	Quindroit 2019		
	unbo	fub	unbound fraction in blood	unitless	1	Quindroit 2019; USEPA2019 = 0.2	0.2	0.2
	Partition coefficients	PCAir	blood-air	unitless	1.00E+99	default	1.3	3
		PCFat	blood - fat	unitless	225	Quindroit 2019	1.3	3
		PLiver	blood - liver	unitless	0.89	Quindroit 2019	1.3	3
		PCRich	blood - rich perfused tissues	unitless	1.1	Quindroit 2019	1.3	3
		PCPoor	blood - poorly perfused tissues	unitless	1.2	Quindroit 2019	1.3	3
		PCSkin_sc	blood - skin stratum corneum	unitless	19	Quindroit 2019	1.3	3
	excretio	Ke	Renal excretion rate	L/h	0		2	3

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metabolic clearance	Michaelis	Flag for Michaelis-Menten vs linear metabolism (0 = linear, 1 = MM)	unitless	0			
	CLH	linear clearance	L/h	120.12	Quindroit 2019	2	3
	Vmax	Michaelis-Menten metabolic pathway	mmoles/h/L liver	0			
	Km	Michaelis-Menten metabolic pathway	mM	0			
	Frac_Met	Fraction of total metabolism represented by the metabolite	unitless	0.37	Quindroit 2019		
	Kuri_Met	Urinary elimination rate of metabolite	1/h	0.094	Quindroit 2019		
	FUrine	Urinary flow	L/h	0.066	Quindroit 2019		
Individual and exposure parameters	BM	body mass	kg	77			
	BSA	body skin surface area	dm ²	190			
	OralDose	initial oral dose in gut lumen	mmol	7.87			
	DermalDose	initial dermal dose	mmol	0			
	Ing_rate	hourly intakes	mmol/h	0			
	Skin_exposure_rate	rate of exposure to skin	mmol/h	0			
	fSA_exposed	fraction of skin surface area actually exposed	unitless	1			
	Cinh	inhaled concentration	mmol/L	0			

Substance-specific parameters were attributed from existing PBK models, thanks to the model code collection from the partners after reviewing PBK model mixtures in the scientific literature. In the case of missing values or if no PBK model was developed for the substance, other approaches were or have to be considered (e.g., QSAR, QSPR, grouping or read-across methods and extrapolation from *in vitro*

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results). Discussions are in progress to establish a decision tree on the framework to follow in that case (e.g., should we go to QSAR values, animal data, other type of models such as biokinetic ones, etc.).

7.2.3. PFAS

For the PFAS family, the PBK model availability for 4 compounds were researched: PFOS, PFOA, PFNA and PFHxS. For PFOS and PFOA, we attributed specific parameters from the model presented in publications (Deepika et al., 2021; Fàbrega et al., 2014, 2016; Husøy, unpublished), where the PBK model was used to predict the concentration of compound in different organs. The model also includes uncertainty and variability for physiological and biochemical parameters.

A PBK model is available for PFNA (Kim et al., 2019) which consist of 6 compartments and menstrual blood loss for females. This PFNA model by Kim et al. (2019) was validated in rats and extrapolated to humans for risk assessment. The biochemical parameters can be extracted from this model. For PFHxS, two PBK models are available (Sweeney, 2022; Kim et al., 2018). The model by Kim et al. (2018) contains some biochemical parameters, which can be used for risk assessment. The model by Sweeney et al. (2022) was refined from Fàbrega et al. (2015) and Ruark et al. (2017) for physiological and biochemical parameters. This model is calibrated and evaluated for serum and urine data for human and include gender-specific renal resorption parameters. Both models are perfusion limited and include sex-specific changes in the concentration.

7.2.4. Pesticides

- Pyrethroids

For pyrethroids, we attributed substance-specific parameters from the PBK model presented in the publication of Quindroit et al. (2019), where the PBK model aimed to predict the urinary levels in humans of 4 pyrethroid metabolites (*cis*- and *trans*-DCCA, 3-PBA, F-PBA and DBCA) from widely-used parent compounds (deltamethrin, *cis* and *trans* isomers of permethrin, cypermethrin, and cyfluthrin). Organophosphates need often to be bioactivated via CYP450 metabolism pathways into the neurotoxic metabolite, which potently inhibit cholinesterases such as acetylcholinesterase and butyrylcholinesterase. In addition, chronic low dose exposure to organophosphates has been associated with noticeable changed neurobehavioral development and reduced intellectual development in children. Various PBK models have been developed for Chlorpyrifos but are missing for other organophosphates. That also means that substance-specific biochemical parameter values for organophosphates are largely lacking. As this research is based on human PBK models, more information might be available from *in vivo* and *in vitro* experimental studies.

- Chlorpyrifos

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For chlorpyrifos, several substance-specific parameters (unbound fraction in blood as well as partition coefficients between blood and fat, liver, rich and poor perfused tissues) are from the work of Zhao, S. et al. (unpublished). The other substance-specific parameters were reported according to the studies of Bouchard et al. (2005), Nolan et al (1984), Timchalk et al. (2002) and Zhao et al. (2019). Dermal exposure was considered to be neglectable and oral ingestion of Chlorpyrifos has been modelled as dominant route of exposure. We simulated model outputs based on the MCRA generic model and the specific model with a daily exposure of 1 mg/kg body weight, as this exposure concentration was used in HBM studies. Chlorpyrifos has not been detected in human urine and elimination is assumed to only take place through biotransformation. In the liver, biotransformation of chlorpyrifos to the metabolites chlorpyrifos-oxon and 3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol (TCPy) via CYP450 pathways was simulated as a Michaelis-Menten kinetic in the specific model, while a general biotransformation pathway independent of metabolite was simulated in the generic model. Michaelis-Menten kinetic parameter values for several metabolites and human CYP isomers are available in Zhao et al. (2019).

7.2.5. Metals

- Lead

For lead, specific parameters were attributed from the PBK model presented in the study of Tebby et al. (2022), where the PBK model aimed to map predicted blood lead levels in children. Several parameters came from a previous published model developed by O’Flaherty (2000).

Considering cadmium, specific models (Kjellström and Nordberg, 1978; Choudhury et al., 2001; Ruiz et al., 2010; Béchaux et al., 2014; Pouillot et al., 2022) are driven by the rates of transfer between the compartments and time-dependant parameters, whereas the generic model is based on a blood-flow limited structure. Moreover, the urinary excretion is driven by the accumulation of cadmium in kidneys in the specific models, whereas the urinary excretion of the generic model is based on the blood concentration. Considering these differences, the specific model presented in the publication of Pouillot et al. (2022) was selected to predict the urine cadmium levels. As this model is the latest published, it integrated the improvement of the previous models with an inter-individual variability with Pert distribution.

- Chromium

For chromium, three PBK models are available in the literature (Kirman et al., 2013, 2017; O’Flaherty, 2001). Despite the model codes are available, substance-specific parameters are not clear, and a deeper search is necessary. Thus, it was decided to devote more time to reflection for the assignment of parameter values for chromium.

- Mercury

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Considering the work has been done on PBK level for mercury so far, there are 4 available models in the literature (Carrier et al., 2001; Clewell et al., 1999; Gearhart et al., 1995; Ou et al., 2018). The first model was developed for females and infants by Ou et al. (2018) considering oral exposure. The second model reviewed was developed for pregnant women and foetuses, considering oral exposure by Clewell et al. (1999). The architecture of the model relied on the work by Gearhart et al. (1995) for methylmercury in humans and monkeys, during pregnancy and foetal development. Metabolism from MeHg to inorganic mercury was included in the liver, brain and intestine. A diffusion-limited distribution from placenta to the foetus connected the maternal and foetal models. The fourth model was developed for animals and humans by Carrier et al., (2001), considering oral exposure, and represents 2 conceptual models for organic and inorganic mercury. Filling MCRA tables procedure relied on the work that has been done in the models described and more specifically in the work done by from Carrier et al. (2001) and Ou et al. (2018).

- Arsenic

The work that is presented in the literature concerns 4 different PBK models for Arsenic (El-Masri and Kenyon, 2008; Mann, Droz and Vahter, 1996; Yu, 1999). These 4 models are very similar and are built on comparable databases. The model of El-Masri and Kenyon (2008) is the most recent one, and it has been validated by El-Masri et al. (2018) and Dede et al. (2018). Additionally, it has been taken into account in more thorough exposure and risk assessments, such as lifetime exposure through dietary intake for the general population as a whole by Georgopoulos et al. (2008) and Dong et al. (2016), and for children specifically by Liao et al. (2008). The construction of a clear PBK/TK model genealogy is hampered by the fact that all 3 of the exposure studies used slightly modified PBK models, adopting original elements of all 3 "parent" PBK/TK models in a piecemeal manner, and incorporating elements of all 3 models to varying degrees (family tree). Parametrisation process was based on previous published models. In more detail, the parameters were originated from El-Masri and Kenyon (2008) and Yu (1999).

7.2.6. Mycotoxins

The MCRA input in the excel file was based on data found in reported specific human PBK models, which was the case for zearalenone (ZEN) and aflatoxin B1 (AFB1). Parameters such as the absorption rate, fraction unbound and clearance (linear or Michaelis-Menten) were found for ZEN, AFB1 and DON.

- ZEN and AFB1

For ZEN, multiple published models were found in the literature (Mukherjee et al., 2014; Shin et al., 2009), however, for filling out the MCRA excel file, the model published by Mendez-Catala et al. (2021) was used. For ZEN, multiple studies reported the excretion rate expressed in percentages (Gerding et al., 2015; Warth et al., 2013; Zhang et al., 2020). Regarding the Michaelis-Menten data (for ZEN and

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AFB1) the MCRA file is limited to only include one V_{max}/K_m value, even if there are various metabolites formed.

- DON

A specific human model for deoxynivalenol (DON) was available at RIVM (Notenboom, S. et al., unpublished). The excretion rate was found for DON with the appropriate unit.

- OTA

For mycotoxin ochratoxin A (OTA) a generic model was available (Punt et al., 2022). The specifics on the parameters were not included in the supplementary materials but were available in-house at WFSR. The parameters fraction absorbed, and fraction unbound were calculated *in silico*. The clearance of OTA was among other methods determined *in vitro* and resulted in no clearance. Partition coefficients in Punt et al. (2022) were calculated with different methods than the DeJongh method (Berezhkovskiy, 2004; Rodgers and Rowland, 2006; Schmitt, 2008). These methods do not only base their calculations on the LogP but also on the pKa of a substance as fraction ionised and fraction un-ionised also influence partitioning. However, for maintaining homogeneity within partition coefficients listed in the excel file, they were calculated with the DeJongh method.

- Other mycotoxins

For other mycotoxins, i.e., nivalenol, fumonisins, T-2/HT-2, alternaria toxins and enniatins, no specific PBK models were found and, therefore, these mycotoxins were not included in the excel sheet. The HBM4EU additional deliverable 12.8 did not list additional PBK models of interest.

Additionally, the partition coefficients were calculated with the quantitative property-property relationship (QPPR) method of DeJongh et al. (1997) for DON, nivalenol, HT-2, T-2, ZEN, OTA and AFB1, since the original model includes this QPPR.

7.2.7. Parametrisation gaps identified

By filling the parameter table for the generic model, unclear or missing values or no PBK model developed for the substance were identified:

- Mycotoxins: Parameters for the Cosmos MCRA model were investigated for DON, nivalenol, HT-2, T-2, ZEN, OTA and AFB1. For all substances, partition coefficients were calculated using the QSAR of DeJongh et al. (1997) and the QSPR of the ICF model (since these are used in the Cosmos model). *In vivo* data was not available to determine the partition coefficients. Fraction absorbed in the gut (Frac) was only available for one mycotoxin, whilst the 1st order absorption rate constant (k_{Gut}) was available for five out of seven mycotoxins where one was based on a Papp value calculated to a k_a value. The fraction unbound in blood is in almost all cases assumed to be the same as the fraction unbound in plasma, which was calculated based on the LogP/LogK_{ow}. The renal excretion rate was only available for DON and ZEN, however for

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ZEN the renal excretion rate is expressed in percentages (8-40%) (Gerding et al., 2015; Warth et al., 2013; Zhang et al., 2020). Metabolism parameters were only available for DON, ZEN and AFB1. Other mycotoxins are not metabolised. It was difficult to find correct values for metabolism since some mycotoxins are metabolised and multiple V_{max}/K_m 's are available for all the different metabolites.

- Chromium: For substance-specific parameters of chromium, difficulties appeared to obtain clear values from published PBK models. The model code originally developed by O'Flaherty (2001) and updated by Kirman et al. (2017) are both complicated to follow, and there is no detailed description of the parameters used and their associated values in their articles. More time is needed to do no mistake in attributing parameter values.

7.3. Results on generic/specific model comparison for prioritised mixtures

Comparison of the predictions obtained with the generic models versus substance-specific models allows to (i) determine which model will be used in this project on mixture risk assessment and (ii) provide to risk assessors a list of substance-specific parameters values for the generic model for each substance of the mixture.

7.3.1. PFAS

- PFOA

Simulations were performed for an individual exposed to an oral dose of 0.0913 ng/kg bw/day for 100 days of PFOA (Figure 17). This dose corresponds to the dietary exposure of PFOA estimated for one individual of the EuroMix study (Husøy, unpublished).

Figure 17 Comparison between generic (red dotted line and confidence intervals in grey) and specific (blue line) model for PFOA (μM) in plasma.

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The general model (red dotted line and confidence intervals in grey) predicts much lower plasma concentrations than the specific model (blue line) (Husøy, unpublished). This is probably due to the lack of kidney compartment in the general model, and thereby a lack of reabsorption of PFOA.

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Figure 18. Comparison between generic and specific model for PFOA (μM) in plasma for 30 years, in the same plot with y on a log scale with generic (red dotted line) and specific (blue line) (A), the specific model on normal y scale (B) and the generic model on normal scale (C).

However, PFOA accumulates in the human body and have a half-life in humans of several years. In Figure 18, simulations were performed for an individual exposed to a daily oral dose of 0.0913 ng/kg bw/day for 30 years of PFOA. The specific model gives a 1000-fold higher plasma concentration than the general PBPK model (Figure 18. Comparison between generic and specific model for PFOA (μM) in plasma for 30 years, in the same plot with y on a log scale with generic (red dotted line) and specific (blue line) (A), the specific model on normal y scale (B) and the generic model on normal scale (C). Figure 18A). The specific model also gives a plasma concentration of PFOA that reach a steady state (Figure 18B), which is in line with what would be expected for an accumulating substance like PFOA. In contrast, the general PBPK model gives a continuously increasing plasma concentration. It is reasonable to conclude that a specific model is needed for PFOA, which includes a kidney compartment that can model the reabsorption of PFOA in the kidney.

7.3.2. Pesticides

- Pyrethroids

The specific model selected was that developed by Quindroit et al. (2019) for several widely used pyrethroids to the urinary concentrations of metabolites. Simulations were performed (acute exposure) for an adult exposed to an oral dose of 0.1 mg/kg for 1 hour of exposure (Figure 19) to cis-permethrin (cis-PM). This dose corresponds to the orally exposure on human volunteers from the

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study of Ratelle et al. (2015)

Figure 19 Comparison between generic (blue line) and specific (orange line) model for cis-permethrin concentration (mg/L) in blood, fat and liver.

These first results indicate that the generic model predicts rapid absorption and short residence times in the organs, except in the fat. Additionally, in venous blood and liver, the time to reach the maximum concentration is predicted earlier with the generic model compared to the specific one. A factor of 2 was observed between the two models regarding C_{max} .

For metabolites, similar performance is observed for both models (Figure 20) compared to observed data. As for parent compound, metabolites concentrations in urine were predicted with a rapid absorption and shorter residence times for the generic model than the predictions obtained with the specific model.

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Figure 20 Comparison between generic (blue line) and specific (orange line) model for cis-permethrin metabolites concentrations in urine (mg/L). The red dots represent data from literature. The y-axis is in logarithmic scale.

- Chlorpyrifos

Chlorpyrifos was ingested each day (1 mg/kg) over a time-course of 10 days, while inhalation and dermal exposure was neglected. Two models with same input parameter values were used to model chlorpyrifos. Exposure was modelled for fat, liver, and venous blood in μg Chlorpyrifos per kg tissue. The generic model for chlorpyrifos was based on the implemented MCRA PBK model developed by Tebby et al. (2020) and the specific model was based on the unpublished model by Zhao (unpublished) modelled using Berkeley Madonna software. The specific model included biotransformation to chlorpyrifos-oxon and 3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol (TCPy), while the generic model assumed an aggregated parameter value for biotransformation to multiple metabolites. We used the Michaelis-Menten kinetic parameter values for the bioactive metabolite chlorpyrifos-oxon reported by Zhao et al. (2019) in the genetic model. The differences of modelled biotransformation pathways might be the reason why the simulated tissue exposures using the generic model decline much slower after a daily peak concentration has been reached compared to the simulated tissue concentrations modelled by the specific model (Figure 21). Consequently, daily body burden residues build up each day in the generic model outputs but not in the specific model output. Even though chlorpyrifos is excreted more by biotransformation in the specific model than in the generic model, higher maximum concentrations are simulated in liver and venous blood but not in fat in the specific model. An explanation could be that the specific model incorporates absorption routes with a total higher absorption (stomach-liver, stomach-intestine, and intestine-liver) instead of just one as implemented in the generic model

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(intestine-liver). A steady-state of maximum concentration appears to be reached within 10 days of simulation in the specific model but not in the generic model.

Figure 21 Comparison between generic MCRA (left, blue lines) and specific (right, orange lines) model for Chlorpyrifos concentrations in fat, liver, and venous blood ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$). One mg Chlorpyrifos /kg body weight was ingested once every day over a time-course of 10 days.

7.3.3. Metals

- Lead

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The specific model selected here was the one developed by Tebby et al., (2022) to simulate lead concentrations in blood. This model is the most recent available and up-to-date, based on the models developed by O’Flaherty et al. (1993, 1995).

Simulations were performed for a 30-year-old woman exposed to a single oral dose of 0.114 mg/kg for 1 hour of exposure (Figure 22).

Figure 22 Comparison between generic (blue line) and specific (orange line) model for lead concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$) in blood.

The generic model predicts a rapid elimination explained by the bone resorption (which is included into the specific model). About a 1.6-factor between the two models is observed for predicted C_{max} in venous blood.

Regarding the chronic exposure scenario, i.e., 1-year exposure to 0.114 mg/kg/d, the generic model predicts a similar level of Pb venous blood concentration at steady-state (811 $\mu\text{g/L}$) than the one for specific model (891 $\mu\text{g/L}$). However, a rapid elimination is still predicted for the generic model, which can also be explained by the bone resorption (included into the specific model).

- Cadmium

In the case of this work, cadmium partition coefficients were estimated for the generic model. The parameters were estimated based on the specific model of Béchaux et al. (2014). Moreover, the physiological evolution with age is integrated by the stochastic physiological model of Beaudouin et al. (2010).

Simulations were performed on a chronic lifetime dietary exposure from birth to 80-year-old for a population of 10,000 individuals. The dietary exposure was estimated based on the methodology developed by Pruvost-Couvreur et al. (2020) considering the socio-demographical parameters of the French population in order to have a coherent dietary lifetime exposure. Briefly, this methodology is

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based on the simulation of lifetime trajectories considering several socio-demographical parameters. Then, the weekly dietary exposures were estimated based on logistical regressions with the socio-demographical parameters retained, performed on the dietary exposures of a population of reference. As displayed in the Figure 23, MCRA generic model (Tebby et al., 2020) has less variability than the specific model and underestimates the concentration of cadmium in urine.

This study is a first draft to develop a new model for cadmium considering a blood-flow limited structure and displays that a generic model can give a first approximation of cadmium in urine. Nonetheless, the model needs validation to be used in risk assessment.

Figure 23 Comparison of the outcomes between MCRA generic model (in red) adapted for cadmium and the outcomes of Béchaux et al. (2014) specific model (in blue). The graph displays the interindividual variability with the 5th percentile, the median and the 95th percentile.

- Mercury

The model that relied on the calculations for the generic approach originated from MCRA (Tebby et al. (2020)). The specific model was based on the work from Ou et al. (2018) and implemented in the

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INTEGRA platform. The scenario depiction was an oral ingestion of 1 µg of inorganic mercury in the 8th hour of the day and concerned an adult of 25 years old.

The results differ between the MCRA model and INTEGRA specific model (Figure 24). This is due to the fact that the rapid biotransformation that takes place in the human gut was not considered in the general model description. In addition, there are differences in the excretion rate as INTEGRA specific model as it predicts a more rapid excretion from blood compartment than the MCRA.

Figure 24. Comparison between MCRA generic model and specific model for inorganic Mercury

The graph describes the excretion of Mercury per kilogram of body weight after a unique exposure incident exposure on the 8th hour of the simulation among two PBK simulation tools MCRA (blue) and INTEGRA (red). The simulation describes the excretion in blood compartment.

- Arsenic

The PBK model for iAs used for the calculations in the generic case was originated from MCRA (Tebby et al., 2020). The specific model calculations were relied on the work from El-Masri and Kenyon (2008). The scenario depiction was an oral ingestion of 1 µg of inorganic mercury in the 8th hour of the day. The results among the two PBK simulation tools are quite similar (Figure 25). Arsenic specific model predicts a higher distribution in blood compartment instead of MCRA model. The excretion ratio until the steady state condition is reached seems to be similar.

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Figure 25. Comparison between MCRA generic model and specific model for inorganic Arsenic

The graph describes the excretion of inorganic Arsenic after a unique exposure incident exposure on the 8th hour of the simulation among two PBK simulation tools MCRA (blue) and INTEGRA (red). The simulation describes the excretion in blood compartment.

7.3.4. Mycotoxins

- DON

As can be seen in Figure 26, the generic Cosmos model implemented in MCRA and the specific model for DON from Notenboom et al. (unpublished) provide comparable results for the parent compound for both acute and chronic (multiple exposure per day due to short half-life) exposure. To make this comparison, the same input parameters are used for both models and the outcomes were extracted from figures obtained from MCRA using the WebPlotDigitizer. The simulations are highly similar in venous blood, adipose tissue and liver tissue. As stated before, the Cosmos model implemented in MCRA does not allow the simulation of metabolites and urinary excretion (yet). This is possible in the specific model. Based on this comparison it is expected that mycotoxins without specific ADME processed can be modelled using generic models.

Figure 26 Comparison of the outcomes of the MCRA Cosmos generic model used for DON to the outcomes of the DON-specific model of Notenboom et al., unpublished. The figures show the concentration-time profiles of DON and its metabolites (only for the specific model).

- ZEN

The model code of a specific model for ZEN is available from literature (Mendez-Catala, Wang and Rietjens, 2021). However, the code does not run following implementation in the suggested software. As a result, no comparison could be made between the generic model and a specific model for ZEN. If needed within this project, the authors can be contacted for the running code, or the code could be altered within this project.

7.3.5. Summary

To summarise, Table 6 below indicates for which substances and exposure scenario the generic model could be used in mixture risk assessment considering the first outputs. Both scenarios of acute (i.e., short-term exposure) and chronic exposures (long-term constant or intermittent exposure to a substance) were investigated. In the case of HBM data, chronic exposure is generally considered. It allows to identify for which prioritised compounds specific PBK models need to be developed and/or implemented in the PARC model network (link with Tasks 8.3 and 6.2.2).

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Table 6. Summary of the comparison of generic and specific models for prioritised substances in the mixture project, for both acute and chronic exposure.

Substance	Biological matrix	Acute exposure		Chronic exposure	
		Generic model	Specific model	Generic model	Specific model
Pyrethroids	Blood		x	Not tested yet	
Pyrethroids	Urine	x		x (not illustrated here, in a current work with EFSA not yet published)	
Chlorpyrifos	Blood			Not tested yet	
Pb	Blood		x	x	
Cd	Urine				x
As					
Hg	Not tested yet				
PFOA	Blood	Not applicable	Not applicable		x
PFOS	Blood				x
DON	Blood	x		x	
ZEN	Not tested yet				

For pyrethroids, Pb and DON, the generic model implemented in MCRA can be considered with some minor modifications for mixture risk assessment. For Cd and PFAS, a specific PBK model needs to be used to account of all specific processes related to the substance. Some substances were not yet investigated for this comparison, but it will be done soon. The activity 6.2.2 of PARC will be needed to support the mixture risk assessment on the kinetic side when specific PBK model will be necessary (i.e., according to substances selected in case studies). It is important to note that these are the first outputs and further results (e.g., goodness-of-fit criteria) are needed to conclude on which model to use for mixture risk assessment. This will be investigated in the next years of this project.

7.4. Use of proxy for excretion factors and steady-state

Kinetic models (TK or PBK) can be used to determine or refine parameters used in the first tier of risk assessment, such as the fraction of urinary excretion, or to estimate when the steady-state is reached. This is particularly needed for to set hazard value for the common selected effect (see section 5.1.2 and Figure 13)

Application of a FUE to convert external to internal dose and vis-versa

For the conversion of an HBM-GV of a substance in urine from an external TV, some simple equations can be used under certain conditions (Apel et al., 2023). With respect to these conditions, it is practical to distinguish between an acute (single dose) exposure and a chronic (multiple dose) exposure. In both cases the elimination half-life ($t_{1/2}$) of a substance plays a crucial role.

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Acute (single dose) exposure

In case of a single dose exposure, the prerequisite is the collection of a composite urine sample over a sufficient time period. When $t_{1/2}$ is reached, and when the absorption rate of a substance is higher than the elimination rate, the fraction of the absorbed dose that is eliminated in urine in unchanged form is approximately 0.5, i.e., approximately 50% of the absorbed dose is excreted via the urine. For example, in case $t_{1/2} = 6$ h, then 6h after exposure 50% is excreted, and 12h and 24h after exposure, respectively 75% and 94% of the absorbed dose is excreted.

The exposure to a single dose may occur during working hours (in case of occupational exposure) or during the consumption of a meal (in case of dietary exposure) and for this practical reason usually a urinary collection period is taken of 24 hours. In practice, a so-called fraction of urinary excretion (FUE) is determined which is the fraction of the dose eliminated in urine in unchanged form. Then, the average urinary concentration of a substance excreted during 24h can be calculated, and an HBM-GV can be obtained (see also Sections 5.1.2 and 9.1.2).

In case most of the dose is eliminated in the form of a metabolite, then it is wise to determine the concentration of the metabolite in the urine. In that case, the molecular weight of the parent compound and the metabolite should be known.

Chronic (multiple dose) exposure

In case of a multiple dose exposure, the prerequisite is that the substance has reached steady-state in humans. Steady-state is reached when a substance has accumulated in blood and tissue upon multiple dosing and input (exposure) and output (elimination) are at equilibrium. The substance concentrations at steady-state fluctuate between maximum and minimum concentrations within each exposure interval. The level of accumulation is determined by the interplay between the exposure interval (τ) and the elimination half-life of the substance ($t_{1/2}$). The longer the elimination half-life and the shorter the exposure interval, the higher the accumulation will be. For example, if the exposure interval is 24 hours (once a day) and the $t_{1/2}$ is 6h for the considered substance, then (almost) all of the dose is eliminated before the next exposure occurs and no accumulation is observed, hence no steady state is achieved. If the dosing interval equals the elimination half-life (i.e., $\tau = 6$ h) then some accumulation occurs. The extent of fluctuation at steady state between the maximum concentration ($C_{ss,max}$) and the minimum concentration ($C_{ss,min}$) is also determined by τ and $t_{1/2}$. The longer the elimination half-life and the shorter the dosing interval, the less will be the fluctuation between $C_{ss,max}$ and $C_{ss,min}$. The outcome of the interplay between τ and $t_{1/2}$ on the extent of accumulation and fluctuation has been nicely demonstrated by Aylward et al. (2012).

In case steady-state is reached the same equation can be used for the determination of the HBM-GV as mentioned above.

In case steady state is reached and a high accumulation level is obtained ($t_{1/2} \gg \tau$), then the fluctuation between $C_{ss,max}$ and $C_{ss,min}$ is relatively small, and it is not necessary anymore to collect a 24h urine

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sample. In that case, a spot urine sample can also be used to determine if the urinary concentration of the substance (or the metabolite) is below or above the HBM-GV of the substance (or the metabolite) in urine.

However, in case steady-state is not reached after chronic (multiple dose) exposure the equation(s) mentioned above cannot be used.

Obtaining the FUE

In those cases where the parent compound is extensively metabolised (e.g., pesticides), studies reported the molar percentage of administered parent compound recovered as metabolite in urine. Usually, FUE is based on human studies for which a one-compartment model (which represents the entire body) is fitted, as illustrated by Ratelle et al., (2015) for pyrethroids. When no experimental data are available or a TK or PBK model is not parametrised, a hypothetical scenario of FUE=0.05 and FUE = 0.95 can be applied as default worst case and best-case scenario as proposed in Šulc et al. (2022) (Figure 27).

Figure 27 Illustration of the possibilities to obtain the fraction of urinary excretion for metabolites (source: CELSPAC-SPECIMEn study: Risk assessment, WP6 symposium, June 2022).

For the pesticides case-study (acute exposure) few FUEs are available from the bibliography and then default values were used (Section 9.1). To refine this parameter value, a reflexion is leading on using TK or PBK models to simulate FUE values. The Figure 28 presents where the kinetic WG3 can be involved, as well as the possible link with WP5 of the PARC project to provide TK data.

Proxy are commonly used in the lower tier of risk assessment. The use of PBK models in higher tier of risk assessment will make it possible to decrease the associated uncertainty.

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Figure 28 First draft of the workflow to follow to obtain FUE (example for pesticides case studies).

8. Implementation of mixture risk assessment in an integrative model toolbox

8.1. PARC model network integrating relevant models, with the MCRA platform as an example

The PARC model network, developed in PARC task 8.3, will be a web-based computational environment that will bring together the different tools available from the PARC consortium addressing the full chain for aggregated exposure, hazard and risk assessment for health effects in the general population and in specific and occupational populations. The PARC model network should serve regulatory risk assessors concerning modelling of chemical risks. Next to regulatory assessors there will be other interested stakeholders, e.g., researchers, industry, NGOs, etc.

One component in the PARC model network is the Monte Carlo Risk Assessment (MCRA) toolbox¹⁰ (van der Voet et al., 2020). Currently, it is the only available toolbox that spans many aspects of modelling risk assessment, from agricultural use of chemicals to dietary exposure, then aggregating dietary and non-dietary exposures using absorption factors or PBK models to internal predicted exposures that can be compared with HBM data, and from identifying assessment groups for common effects via dose

¹⁰ <https://mcra.rivm.nl>

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response modelling for *in vivo* or *in vitro* data to hazard characterisation models including the use or modelling of assessment factors. In the Real-life mixture project, MCRA was selected for use to obtain results at an early stage of PARC. In task 8.3, MCRA will be used as part of and linked to other parts of the evolving PARC model network.

For further discussion of the PARC model network, we refer to PARC Deliverable 8.3 (under development).

8.2. Modular design, data formats & ontologies for sharing data

Mixture risk assessment involves the use of many models in order to come to final results such as mixture risk metrics (Section 6.2) or identified risk drivers for aggregated exposure. For many components, models are being created or improved by a large number of research groups, many of them in or connected to PARC. The PARC model aims to link relevant models in a digital ecosystem. This means that we do not design a super-tool that includes all best models, but rather an infrastructure where models can be lined up in pipelines. Consequently, the PARC model network will have a modular design, with modules defined for each recognisable functionality that can be used on its own or in combination with other modules. For this, existing toolboxes containing many models may be made more transparent and interoperable by allowing access to their separate parts (modules). In such a modular design, it is essential to define the links between models. Output from one model will be input for the model next in the pipeline. It is then essential to harmonise the data formats used for the data that need to be transferred from one system to another. This can be based on ad-hoc agreements, but the experience is that this often takes a lot of time. In PARC, there is an inter-WP working group to base data formats on semantic modelling and agreed ontologies. First examples related to HBM data, and therefore relevant to the Real-life mixtures project, are being worked on in a project of activity 7.2.2.

As an example of the foreseen development in the PARC model network, MCRA is already a toolbox containing a large number of models. The current state of modularisation is shown in Figure 29. In the first year of the Real-life mixtures project, the attention has been focused on the modules in the top middle of the figure, such as Human monitoring data (harmonised HBM data as agreed in PARC), Human monitoring analysis (pre-processing of HBM data) and Exposure mixtures (SNMU, clustering and network analysis). Note that links can be made (and are planned to be made in the sequel) to other modules, such as Exposures (better named Internal exposures), Kinetic models (linking to externally developed PBK models), Hazard characterisation, Relative potency factors and Risk, to name just a few.

Figure 29. Modular design of the MCRA tool. Not all links are shown in this graph.

8.3. Implementation of modules for specific aspects

In the first year of the Real-life mixtures project, functionality was improved or newly developed in specific modules of MCRA, as part of the PARC model network.

8.3.1. Human monitoring data

In PARC, human monitoring data are being harmonised to a standard format (Section 3.2). This format was designed in collaboration between the partner responsible for the data and the developers of MCRA. In MCRA, an additional data converter was written to adapt the data to the MCRA formats. Data summaries were optimised, in agreement with the European HBM dashboard.

8.3.2. Human monitoring analysis

For transparency, it is requested that individual raw data (i.e., without prior transformations or corrections) is uploaded in the HBM monitoring data module since subsequent data pre-processing steps are part of the modelling process. Therefore, functionality has been implemented in the human

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monitoring analysis module for e.g., normalisation and standardisation of biomarker concentrations, and imputation of censored or missing HBM data. Currently, normalisation of urine measurements by specific gravity is supported, as well as urine standardisation using creatinine. Support for standardisation of blood biomarkers to total lipid consent has also been made available. Censored values can be imputed based on a random sample following from a censored log-normal model, or by a constant value (e.g., half LOD or LOQ). Missing values can be imputed univariately by drawing (at random) from the observed values. Alternatively, analyses can focus on complete cases only, i.e., samples with missing values are discarded. Further pre-processing steps are planned and already partly implemented, such as simultaneous assessment of substances found in multiple biological matrices.

8.3.3. Co-exposure mixtures

The Exposure mixtures module has been completely re-designed. It was previously only possible to apply SNMU to modelled (predicted) dietary or aggregated exposures, now the option has been added to apply SNMU or network analysis to human monitoring analysis results, i.e., to pre-processed HBM data. The Exposure mixtures module now has a setting ‘Internal concentration type’ that can be set either to ‘Internal modelled concentrations’ or ‘Human monitoring concentrations’⁶. In the former case, data from the module (dietary) Exposures are used, in the latter data from the module Human monitoring analysis. Two multivariate methods for mixture selection are now implemented in the exposure mixtures module, namely SNMU and network analysis. Sparse nonnegative matrix underapproximation (SNMU) was already available, but an optional hierarchical clustering of individuals has now been added. Moreover, the structure and form of the output (tables and graphs) was improved. Secondly, network analysis in combination with community detection was added. These procedures were proposed in previous projects (Euromix and HBM4EU). The first procedure (SNMU + clustering) has been implemented according to Crépet et al. (2019, 2022). The second procedure (network analysis) follows Ottenbros et al. (2021).

8.3.4. Kinetic models

An inventory is being made of useful specific PBK models and these are compared to the generic Euromix model implemented in MCRA (Section 7.1). Preparing for a next stage of the Real-life mixtures project, it may be useful to link more PBK models to the Kinetic models entry point in MCRA. The structure of the Kinetic models module has been improved, e.g., by separating physiological from chemical-dependent parameters. It was recognised that MCRA could handle PBK models only substance by substance, whereas metabolism to other substances may be very important in many cases. Consequently, the structure of MCRA was adapted to allow metabolites in kinetic models, which was experimented in a first case study with a PBK model for chlorpyrifos and its metabolites chlorpyrifos-oxon and TCPy.

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8.4. User interfaces and demonstrators for specific user groups

MCRA is a web-based system. Actions with MCRA can be accessed from a user interface page related to the desired output, e.g., exposure mixtures or risk. The user then has to go through a series of pages representing each underlying module that is needed for the calculation. Although straightforward, this may be a tedious procedure when many modules are needed (which is common). Therefore, it is the intention to develop simplified user interfaces for specific user groups, e.g., regulators. In MCRA, standard actions can be set up to implement this.

For training project participants in the use of MCRA with HBM data, guidance notes were prepared on reading in and pre-processing HBM data (Van der Voet, 2022) and use them for multivariate analyses (Engel, 2022).

9. Application to mixture risk assessment for prioritised chemical families and their effects

9.1. Pesticides and neurotoxicity

9.1.1. Context and objectives

9.1.1.1. CELSPAC-SPECIMEn study

The SPECIMEn study (Vlaanderen et al., 2019) was aimed at an investigation of exposure to pesticide mixtures in the residential population. The study was part of the HBM4EU programme and was conducted as a joint effort by five institutions in five European countries. The focus of the SPECIMEn study was the evaluation of pesticide mixtures in the European population and the characterisation of differences among adults and children, non-agricultural and agricultural areas, and seasons. The involved institutions and countries were IRAS – Institute for Risk Assessment Sciences (the Netherlands, study leader), ISCIII – Instituto de Salud Carlos III (Spain), RECETOX, Masaryk University (the Czech Republic), RSU – Rīga Stradiņš University (Latvia), and NPHC – National Public Health Center (Hungary). The research questions of the SPECIMEn study were:

- Which combinations of pesticides are commonly detected in human biological samples?
- Do patterns in pesticides detected in human biological samples differ between age groups and study populations in different countries?
- Do patterns in pesticides detected in human biological samples differ between people living in non-agricultural and agricultural areas?
- Do patterns in pesticides detected in human biological samples differ between seasons (winter and summer)?

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The participants were recruited to the study as adult–child pairs. These pairs were generally in a direct family relationship (mother/father, son/daughter) and always shared the household at the time of sample collection. The inclusion criteria for participants were:

- Minimum age of adult participants (20 years),
- Age range for child participants (5-12 years),
- Living in the current home address for at least 6 months (adjusting period),
- No intention to move in the following 6 months (sampling period),
- No occupational exposure to pesticides in participants,
- No occupational exposure to pesticides in other household members.

Since the SPECIMEn study also aimed to study potential differences in pesticide exposure in agricultural and non-agricultural areas, participants were also selected based on the characteristics of the vicinity of their home address. A participant’s home address at a distance of 250 m or less from fields, orchards, vineyards, or any other area where pesticide spraying may take place was designated as being located in an agricultural area. A participant’s home address at a distance 500 m or more from fields, orchards, vineyards, or any other area where pesticide spraying may take place was designated as being located in non-agricultural area. The target number of participants was equal to at least 50 adults and 50 children in agricultural areas and the same number in non-agricultural areas. This number was selected as a minimum for further statistical testing and analysis.

Human biological samples were collected in two seasons: winter (very little field spraying was assumed) and summer (field spraying was assumed). This was done to account for presumable environmental pesticide concentration differences between seasons, but also due to differences in human behaviour between seasons. The biological matrix of choice was first-morning urine. Lifestyle and dietary questionnaires were collected with urine samples to assess other potential pesticide exposure pathways and variables. The collected urine samples from both winter and summer sampling seasons were analysed using suspect screening approach (Huber et al., 2022). Ottenbros et al. (2023) published the results of the SPECIMEn study in 2023.

In the case of the Czech Republic, the SPECIMEn study was carried out as part of CELSPAC (Central European Longitudinal Studies of Parents and Children) CELSPAC – SPECIMEn study (<https://www.recetox.muni.cz/hear/projects/specimen>) and received ethical approval under ref. no. ELSPEC/EK/3/2019. Potential participants were pre-selected on the basis of spatial criteria affiliated with agricultural and non-agricultural areas and later via internet advertisements (e.g., posts on social media web pages, short announcements on local news pages, announcements on the internet pages of selected towns after communication with the town mayor), radio announcements, and announcements on local television stations. Overall, 110 adult-child pairs were recruited to the study. Target analysis for 12 pesticide biomarkers of exposure was conducted with health risk assessment (Šulc et al., 2022). Associations between pesticide exposure, DNA damage, and oxidative stress were also investigated (Janoš et al., 2023).

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9.1.1.2. EFSA CAG for nervous systems

EFSA has developed a methodology to carry out cumulative risk assessment (CRA) of pesticide residues in food (EFSA, 2013b). As part of a pilot programme for the implementation of this methodology, acute cumulative dietary exposure assessments have been performed for two cumulative assessment groups (CAGs) of pesticides that affect the nervous system: pesticides associated with brain and/or erythrocyte AChE inhibition (CAG-NAN, 47 pesticides) and pesticides associated with functional alterations of the motor division of the nervous system (CAG-NAM, 100 pesticides) (EFSA et al., 2020a). The exposure assessments used external exposure data such as pesticide residue monitoring data collected by Member States under their official monitoring programmes in 2014, 2015 and 2016 and individual food consumption data from 10 populations of consumers from different countries and from different age groups. Exposure estimates were obtained for each group of pesticides by means of a 2-dimensional Monte Carlo simulation, which was implemented in the Monte Carlo Risk Assessment (MCRA) software. A very conservative tier I modelling approach and a refined, but still conservative tier II modelling approach were used. In these assessments, common risk assessment practice was followed, and the cumulative exposure was calculated as total margin of exposure (MOET) at the 50th, 90th, 95th, 99th and 99.9th percentiles of the exposure distribution.

The aim of proposing the two case studies on pesticides CAG-NAN and CAG-NAM (Sections 9.1.4 and 9.1.5) is to explore how HBM data can be used in practice to perform mixture risk assessment and compare obtained results with mixture risk assessment performed with external (dietary) exposure data as identified from residue monitoring studies in different commodities and food consumption as performed by EFSA. This work contributes to the broader research question on how inclusion of HBM data could improve human health risk assessment and help for prioritisation of pesticides monitoring and potential needs for risk management to follow. Thus, the main goal is to compare the results from the retrospective cumulative risk assessment performed using external dietary exposures to pesticide residues (EFSA approach) to the cumulative risk assessment results obtained using internal human biomonitoring data, in which all sources and routes of exposure are reflected. The following questions should be discussed:

- How similar are the conclusions of the different approaches (HBM data vs the combination of residues and consumption data, all sources and routes vs dietary) with regard to human health concerns?
- Do both approaches result in the identification of the same risk drivers?
- Could the results on human health risk assessment trigger different policy or risk management measures?

The two approaches (reverse and forward dosimetry) mentioned in Section 5.1.2 and described in detail under Section 9.1.2 were applied to perform risk assessment from HBM data on pesticide based on metabolites in urinary concentrations (Figure 30). One of the main challenges is to attribute the different pesticide metabolites measured in HBM data to the parent compounds used in risk

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assessment performed by EFSA, in order to make results of mixture risk assessment from external and internal exposures comparable.

9.1.2. Reverse and forward dosimetry to perform risk assessment from HBM data

As mentioned in Section 5.1.2, two approaches (reverse and forward dosimetry) can be applied to perform risk assessment using HBM data on pesticide urinary concentrations (Figure 30).

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Figure 30 Reverse and forward dosimetry to perform risk assessment from HBM data on pesticide metabolites urinary concentrations. EDI is Estimated Daily Intake ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}/\text{day}$), HBM-ELm: exposure level expressed in urinary concentration of the metabolite ($\mu\text{g}/\text{g crea.}$), CE: anthropometry- and gender-based reference value for creatinine excretion in urine derived for selected members of the population (e.g. children, adults) ($\text{g crea.}/\text{day}$) (Šulc et al., 2022): substance, m: metabolite, FUE: fraction of urinary excretion on molar basis, RP: reference point, MW: molecular weight, BW: body weight, MOET: Total margin of exposure

The first approach 1) applied reverse dosimetry to HBM data on metabolite urinary concentration (HBM-ELm) to estimate the external daily intake (EDIs) (Equation a) for each pesticide as described in the literature (Katsikantami et al., 2019; F. Fernández et al., 2020; Šulc et al., 2022). In cases where urinary concentrations of two or more metabolites are considered in the estimation of a pesticide EDI, then equation a) is modified accordingly:

$$EDIs = \frac{HBM - ELm1 \times CE \times \left[\frac{MWs}{MW(m1)} \right]}{BW \times FUEm1} + \frac{HBM - ELm2 \times CE \times \left[\frac{MWs}{MW(m2)} \right]}{BW \times FUEm2} + \dots$$

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Then, to allow comparison to the EFSA approach the margin of exposure (MOE) is estimated using the NOAEL value for each compound (Equation b) as reported in the EFSA (2019a) for the selected pesticides and summed to calculate the total margin of exposure MOET (Equation c).

The second approach 2) is also based on the use of HBM data and has been implemented in line with the broader strategy described in Section 5.1 for different types of chemicals and effects. It applies a forward dosimetry to NOAEL set by EFSA for each pesticide in regards of the common effect to estimate an internal reference point HBM-RP (Tarazona et al., 2022) for its urinary metabolite(s). The internal reference points (HBM-RP) can then be used to calculate the MOET (equation f), by summing the MOE which corresponds to the HBM-RP divided the HBM exposure levels (equation e).

The HBM-RP for the urinary metabolite(s) is estimated in compliance with the appropriate toxicological value, here the NOAEL and the consideration of the fraction of urinary excretion (FUE) and the molecular weight (MW) of the parent compound and its metabolite(s) (equation d). The FUE is defined as the amount (g) of the metabolite excreted in urine as the fraction of the exposure to parent pesticide (equation g). The FUE can be estimated from: human data, from animal data or PBK modelling (Section 7.4). Furthermore, in the absence of any specific data, scenarios for FUE values can be considered as proposed by Šulc et al. (2022).

9.1.3. Application to CELSPAC-SPECIMEn pesticide mixtures

Using reverse dosimetry approach, daily intakes of tebuconazole, chlorpyrifos and cypermethrin were reconstructed based on three possible scenarios. The cumulative risk assessment of pesticide mixtures having an effect on the nervous system, based on the total margin of exposure (MOET) calculations were deployed as described in detail in Section 9.1.2, Figure 30 and in Šulc et al. (2022). This approach is based on the presumption that pesticides included in the same cumulative assessment group (CAG) might produce joint, cumulative toxicity, following the dose addition model, even if they do not have similar modes of action. This assumption is applicable since the exposure levels are at the residue scale. Therefore, primarily health risks in two CAGs were assessed: CAG on chronic functional effects on the motor division (CAG-NAM) and CAG on the brain and/or erythrocyte acetylcholinesterase inhibition (CAG-NAN) as the highest risks are expected to be observed for these effects.

9.1.3.1. Data availability

To assess the possible risk of combined exposure to a mixture of pesticides, urinary concentrations of 12 current-use pesticides (CUP) metabolites were measured by means of high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) in tandem with a mass spectrometer-mass spectrometer system (MS-MS). Metabolites 3-PBA, t/c-DCCA, TCPY and TEB-OH were detected in more than 40% of samples and thus used in further analysis (for all measured metabolites and their parent compounds Table 10). Regarding FUE values, the following was retrieved from literature: FUE for chlorpyrifos metabolite

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TCPY and tebuconazole metabolite TEB-OH are 0.7 and 0.38 (Nolan et al., 1984; Oerlemans et al., 2019). The excretion of pyrethroid metabolites is in the range 0.13–0.27 for 3-PBA and 0.28–0.64 for t/c-DCCA (Eadsforth and Baldwin, 1983; Eadsforth, Bragt and Van Sittert, 1988; Ratelle, Coté and Bouchard, 2015; Woollen et al., 1992) thus, mean FUE of 0.20 and 0.47 were used. Animal NOAELs were available from EFSA reports (EFSA et al., 2019a). Table 8 contains an overview of NOAEL values used ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}\text{-bw}/\text{day}$) for each respective parental compound in cumulative assessment groups.

Table 7. Parental pesticides and biomarkers of exposure measured in urine in the CELSPAC-SPECIMEn study.

Chemical group	Pesticide name	Biomarker name	Biomarker abbr.	Biomarker CAS	Biological half-life (h)
Pyrethroid	Cypermethrin	3-phenoxybenzoic acid	3-PBA	3739-38-6	6.4 a
	Cyfluthrin	4-fluoro-3-phenoxybenzoic acid	4F3-PBA	77279-89-1	
	Permethrin	trans/cis-3-(2,2-dichlorovinyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropane carboxylic acid	t/c-DCCA	55667-40-8	6.3 (trans) a, 6.4 (cis) a
Organophosphate	Chlorpyrifos	diethyl dithiophosphate	DEDTP	298-06-6	-
		3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol	TCPY	6515-38-4	27 b
	Malathion	2-isopropyl-4-methyl-6-hydroxypyrimidine	IMPY	2814-20-2	-
	Coumaphos	dicarboxylic acid	MDA	1190-28-9	-
Chloroacetamide	Pethoxamid	coumaphos	-	56-72-4	-
		pethoxamid	PM	106700-29-2	-
		pethoxamid metabolite-42	PM MET	-	-
Phenylpyrazole	Fipronil	fipronil sulfone	FPS	120068-36-2	-
Triazole	Tebuconazole	hydroxy-1-tebuconazole	TEB-OH	212267-64-6	7.8 c

a related to cypermethrin, (Ratelle et al., 2015)

b related to chlorpyrifos, (Nolan et al., 1984)

c related to tebuconazole, (Oerlemans et al., 2019)

Table 8. Cumulative assessment groups of multiple pesticides with effects on the nervous system and pesticides and effect specific no observed adverse effect levels ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}\text{-bw}/\text{day}$).

type	CAG	NOAEL ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}\text{-bw}/\text{day}$)		
		Cypermethrin	Chlorpyrifos	Tebuconazole
acute	CAG on functional effects on the sensory division	60000	100000	10000
acute	CAG on functional effects on the autonomic division	20000	100000	250000
acute	CAG on functional effects on the motor division	20000	10000	
chronic	CAG on functional effects on the sensory division	5000	15000	
chronic	CAG on functional effects on the autonomic division	6000	15000	
chronic	CAG on functional effects on the motor division	5000	5000	
chronic	CAG on the brain and/or erythrocyte acetylcholinesterase inhibition		100	
chronic	CAG on functional effects on neuropathological endpoints	25000		

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CAGs in **bold** are the most relevant for cumulative health risk assessment for the nervous system in the study population, as the highest risks are expected to be observed for these effects, source: (EFSA et al., 2019a)

9.1.3.2. Risk assessment using reverse dosimetry

To estimate daily intake (EDI) of parent pesticides, reverse dosimetry approach, with aim to perform risk assessment from HBM data, as described in Section 9.1.2. and in Šulc et al. (2022) was used. In the case of pyrethroid metabolites, cypermethrin was selected as a parent compound. Using aforementioned fractions of urinary excretion, realistic scenario EDIs were calculated. Obtained FUE presented in 9.1.3.2 were derived on the basis of healthy volunteers and are only applicable to adults. Thus, the daily intakes with 0.05 and 0.95 FUE were additionally used to estimate the worst-case and the best-case scenario. The best-case scenario assumed that 95% of the respective parental compound was excreted as a measured biomarker. On the other hand, the worst-case scenario assumed that only 5% of the respective parental compound was excreted as a measured biomarker.

9.1.3.3. Risk results from CELSPAC-SPECIMEN study

Assessment of the cumulative risk of the combined exposure of pesticide mixture with an effect on the nervous system was performed in adults and children from the CELSPAC-SPECIMEN cohort. The emphasis was primarily on two CAGs: CAG-NAM and CAG-NAN, as the highest risks are expected to be observed for these effects. Using the realistic scenario, MOET below 100 was not observed in any participant with higher median value in children (median CAG-NAM MOET = 14,316; median CAG-NAN MOET = 758) than in adults (median CAG-NAM MOET = 36,227; median CAG-NAN MOET = 1,301). Considering the worst-case scenario, when only 5% of the parent pesticide is excreted in the urine, the MOETs for both CAG-NAM and CAG-NAN below 100 were observed in the case of 1% and 72% of children samples respectively (median CAG-NAM MOET = 1,252; median CAG-NAN MOET = 54). In adults, values of MOET below 100 were observed only in the case of CAG-NAN (53% of all adult samples) and thus exposure could be considered a risk for humans (median CAG-NAM MOET = 2,845; median CAG-NAN MOET = 93). Similar results for Czech adult population were also obtained using external exposure data by EFSA (Section 9.1.1.2) for the CAG-NAN (brain and/or erythrocyte AChE inhibition for acute exposure). In the case of CAG-NAM (functional alterations of the motor division), MOET at the 50th percentile of the exposure at Tier II estimated by EFSA was ten times lower, but still within the safe level (EFSA et al., 2020). The results of cumulative risk assessment across all CAGs and scenarios are presented in Šulc et al. (2022).

9.1.4. Application to the prioritised pesticides from the CAG-NAN

Regarding risk results obtained by EFSA (Section 9.1.1.2) for the CAG-NAN, the MOET calculated under tier II was below 100 at the 99.9th percentile for toddlers and other children's populations (EFSA et al.,

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2020a). Five pesticides belonging to the CAG-NAN group were identified as risk drivers: Chlorpyrifos, Triazophos, Omethoate, Dichlorvos, and Formetanate. In the upper tail of the exposure distribution Carbofuran, Azinphos-ethyl, Dimethoate Pirimiphos-methyl, and Methomyl were also contributors to the exposure. In this T6.2.3 Real-life mixture project these 10 pesticides were selected as a prioritised mixture (Section 2.1). The purpose of this case study is to perform cumulative risk assessment for these 10 pesticides based on biomonitoring data (internal exposure) in order to compare the results to those obtained by EFSA based on food monitoring data c and individual food consumption data (external exposure).

9.1.4.1. Data availability

In order to conduct the mixture risk assessment, hazard data on the ten selected pesticides, information on their biomarkers and concentrations from HBM surveys available in the database inventory (Section 3) were collected.

Hazard data: Animal NOAELs based on brain and/or erythrocyte AChE inhibition for acute exposure set by EFSA (2019a) were selected in order to use the same points of departure as EFSA did in order to avoid distortion between internal vs external exposure approaches for cumulative risk assessment. These NOAELs are presented in Table 10. Only one HBM-GV was available in the literature for chlorpyrifos (Arnold et al., 2015).

Regarding available biomarkers in HBM data potentially associated to the 10 selected pesticides, non-specific metabolites of organophosphates (OP) i.e., dialkylphosphates (DAP) were generally measured as well as two metabolites considered specific: 3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol (TCPy) for chlorpyrifos and carbofuranphenol for carbofuran. No exposure biomarkers of formetanate and methomyl were measured in available HBM data.

WG3 conducted an inventory of available PBK models for the 10 selected pesticides. For chlorpyrifos, a specific human ingestion PBPK model is available, however no specific ingestion models were available for triazophos, omethoate, formetanate pirimiphos-methyl and methomyl. Two rodents' models are available for carbofuran. Regarding FUE values, only one value of 0.7 for TCPy was retrieved from literature (Nolan et al., 1984).

Table 9 Hazard characterisation of pesticides in CAG-NAN to be considered in acute cumulative risk assessment (EFSA et al. 2019)

Pesticide	Chemical family	Indicator of specific effect	Study type	NOAEL (mg/kg bw)
Chlorpyrifos	Organophosphate	AChE inhibition (erythrocytes)	Comparative cholinesterase assay rat (gavage)	0.5
Triazophos	Organophosphate	AChE inhibition (erythrocytes)	1 year dog (diet)	0.012

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Omethoate	Organophosphate	AChE inhibition (brain)	Acute neurotoxicity rat (gavage)	0.25
Dichlorvos	Organophosphate	AChE inhibition (erythrocytes)	13-week rat (gavage)	0.1
Carbofuran	Carbamate	AChE inhibition (brain)	Acute neurotoxicity rat (gavage)	0.015
Pirimiphos-methyl	Organophosphate	AChE inhibition (brain, erythrocytes)	Acute neurotoxicity rat (gavage)	15
Dimethoate	Organophosphate	AChE inhibition (erythrocytes)	Acute neurotoxicity rat (diet)	1
Formetanate	Carbamate	AChE inhibition (brain, erythrocytes)	Acute oral cholinesterase activity study in female rats (gavage)	0.5
Methomyl	Carbamate	AChE inhibition (brain, erythrocytes)	Acute neurotoxicity rat (gavage)	0.25
Azinphos-ethyl	Organophosphate	AChE inhibition (erythrocytes)	90-day neurotoxicity dog (diet)	0.0125

HBM data: The population of interest was children, as they were the individuals at risk according to the threshold of regulatory concern in the EFSA risk assessment (van Klaveren et al., 2019; EFSA et al., 2020a). Urinary concentrations from the ESTEBAN study (France) were used to perform a pilot risk assessment. In this study, 6 urinary DAP metabolites of organophosphate insecticides were measured i.e., dimethylphosphate (DMP); dimethylthiophosphate (DMTP); dimethyldithiophosphate (DMDTP); diethylphosphate (DEP); diethylthiophosphate (DETP) and diethyldithiophosphate (DEDTP) were measured as well as carbofuranphenol and TCPy which were considered as specific metabolites of carbofuran and chlorpyrifos, respectively.

In ESTEBAN, data was available for 244 children from 6 to 18 year of age (Table 10).

9.1.4.2. Low tiered risk assessment using reverse dosimetry

In van Klaveren et al. (2019) annexes, for the other children population in France, these 4 pesticides were the ones contributing the most to French children' exposure. Based on the available data previously described, a lower tier mixture risk assessment on 4 out of 10 active substances (chlorpyrifos, triazophos, omethoate and carbofuran) was started as presented in Figure 31.

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Figure 31 General approach applied to CAG-NAN pesticide case studies.

As presented in Table 7, all the DEPs exposure were attributed to triazophos and all the DMPs exposure to omethoate. As a higher tier, in a later stage, we will refine the metabolites allocation to consider the other prioritised organophosphates. To make use of left-censored data, when the concentration was below the LOD, a value of 0 was attributed and when it was below the LOQ, half of the LOQ was assigned. The reverse dosimetry approach was used to obtain estimated daily intake (EDI) (equation a) in Section 9.1.2). As specific fractions of urinary excretion (FUE) are not available for all the selected active substances, two scenarios were considered using FUE values of 0.95 and 0.05 (Šulc et al., 2022) as best-case and worst-case scenario for carbamates and a worst-case scenario of 0.5 for organophosphates. The value of 0.5 was chosen assuming a good metabolisation into the common metabolites for organophosphates. Indeed, studies in several species have shown rapid breakdown of the majority of organophosphate pesticides tested with the appearance of metabolites in the urine. Typically, 90 to 95% of radioactivity from a labelled pesticide can be recovered in 24 hours after oral or parenteral administration (WHO, 1996). The major metabolic route of organophosphates in humans is hydrolysis producing DAP metabolites in one hand and a specific moiety (e.g., TCPy for chlorpyrifos) that are excreted in urine (Cocker et al., 2002). For carbofuran, Jongeneelen et al. explored different approaches using either a PBPK generic model or general pharmacokinetic parameters with a FUE value of 0.05, to derive a biomonitoring guidance value for carbofuran (Jongeneelen, Berge and Boogaard, 2013). They considered a threshold limit value-threshold weighted average for occupational exposure to obtain a biological exposure equivalent in urine.

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Creatinine excretion (CE) values were converted in mmol/kg/day from Remer et al. (2002) in grams of creatinine per day. A value of CE was assigned by gender and age class to each individual. MOE were then calculated for each pesticide by the ratio between the NOAEL and the EDI. Finally, the MOET was calculated by summing the individual pesticide's 1/MOE. These calculations were made with R software.

Table 10 Summary of the data used to perform risk assessment for the CAG-NAN (N=244 individuals). LOD: limit of detection, LOQ: limit of quantification, %>LOQ: percentage on quantified levels

Pesticide	Considered metabolite(s)	Specificity	LOD (µg/L)	LOQ (µg/L)	%>LOQ
Triazophos	DEP	Common	0.3	0.6	20,5%
	DETP	Common	0.3	0.6	34,4%
Chlorpyrifos	TCPy	Specific	0.02	0.05	2,05%
Omethoate	DMP	Common	0.8	2	40,6%
	DMTP	Common	0.3	0.6	93,4%
Carbofuran	Carbofuranphenol	Specific	1	5	2,05%

9.1.4.3. Preliminary risk results from ESTEBAN survey

Table 11 shows the results of the lower tier calculations for the mixture of the four pesticides belonging to the CAG-NAN in French children from 6 to 18 years in ESTEBAN HBM data. The results for French children from 6 to below 10 years old, representing 83 out of 244 individuals from the dataset are presented separately to compare with EFSA results. These results were obtained using the reverse dosimetry approach with two scenarios: a best-case scenario where 95% of the active substance is excreted as the metabolites and a worst-case where 50% of the active substance is excreted as the metabolites.

For the 6-year to below 10-year-old population of French children, the number of individuals for which the MOET is below 100 is 5 times higher than the results found in EFSA's Tier I assessment and far away from the ones obtained in Tier II. In their tiering approach for dietary risk assessment, for occurrence data, in Tier I extrapolations of measurement were made and for left-censored data, half of the LOQ was imputed for food-substance combinations with quantifiable findings. In Tier II, authorised pesticides were allocated to each sample randomly, and half of the LOQ was imputed based on estimate use frequencies.

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Compared to EFSA probabilistic modelling, in this assessment we derived acute exposure estimates from only one urine sample for each individual. This does not take into account the daily variability and associated uncertainty. Moreover, we do not have specific FUEs nor specific metabolites for tiazophos and omethoate, which are important limitations.

The treatment of left-censored data for DMP, DEP and DETP could also overestimate the risk. In addition, TCPy and carbofuranphenol are quantified in only 2% of the samples.

The main sources of risk overestimation in this first approach are linked to the fact that DAP metabolites represent non-specific metabolites of organophosphates pesticides, and they were allocated to the main potent parents. Furthermore, several studies documented the common presence of DAPs in residential environments and foods (Sudakin and Stone, 2011). Therefore, the presence of DAPs in urine reflects not only recent exposure to many parent organophosphates but also exposure to preformed non neurotoxic DAPs.

Table 11 Total margin of exposure (MOET) using the reverse dosimetry approach, calculated using HBM data from ESTEBAN for various percentiles of exposure (CAG-NAN, lower tier).

Data	Approach	Scenario	Population	MOET, 50 th percentile	MOET,95 th percentile	MOET,99 th percentile	MOET 99.9 th percentile	% of individual with MOET<100
EFSA 2019	Tier I		6 to <10 y	235	78.8	41	11.4	10%
EFSA 2019	Tier II		6 to <10 y	2570	782	287	59.1	0.3%
ESTEBAN	Lower tier	Best case	6 to <10y	87	10	7	6	54.2%
ESTEBAN	Lower tier	Worst case	6 to <10y	46	5	4	3	67.5%
ESTEBAN	Lower tier	Best case	6 to <18y	155	10	5	1.1	42.2%
ESTEBAN	Lower tier	Worst case	6 to <18y	81	5	2	0.6	57%

9.1.4.4. Next steps

In the following months, we will perform a cumulative risk assessment using the forward dosimetry approach with the lower tier. HBM-RPs values will be derived for the 4 pesticides and MOETs will be calculated by determining the ratio between the HBM-RPs and the urinary concentrations of each metabolite. In order to refine the cumulative risk assessment for the reverse dosimetry, in a higher tier, and to be closer to the tiered proposed by EFSA we will try to revise the allocation of the

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metabolites so that more prioritised pesticides can be included in the mixture. Regarding fractions of urinary excretion (FUE), the feasibility to obtain realistic FUE through PBPK modelling will be evaluated with WG3, as for now only a human chlorpyrifos specific PBPK model is available.

9.1.5. Application to the prioritised pesticide from the CAG-NAM

In EFSA assessment for the CAG-NAM, the research question was to characterise the acute cumulative risk of functional alteration of the motor division of the nervous system (e.g., locomotor activity, muscle strength, coordination and equilibrium) resulting from combined dietary exposure to pesticide residues under the assumption of dose addition (EFSA et al., 2020a).

The probability for the total margin of exposure (MOET) to be equal to or greater than 100 (acceptable risk) at the 99.9th percentile of exposure (threshold of regulatory concern) was greater than 95% for all population groups considered (toddlers and children from Bulgaria, France, the Netherlands, Denmark, the UK). Seven pesticides belonging to the CAG-NAM, i.e., triazophos, chlormequat, beta-cypermethrin, deltamethrin, omethoate, thiram and acrinathrin, were identified as risk drivers in these 10 populations of consumers (EFSA, 2019; EFSA et al., 2020a; van Klaveren et al., 2019).

This project is implemented on selected risk drivers from EFSA risk assessment (triazophos, chlormequat, beta-cypermethrin, deltamethrin, omethoate, thiram) and on additional prioritised pesticides (alpha-cypermethrin, lambda-cyhalothrin, azinphos-ethyl, formetanate) as described in Section 2.1.

9.1.5.1. Data availability

Hazard data: Data on hazard characterisation for each pesticide of the CAG-NAM were retrieved from the EFSA Scientific Report on the establishment of cumulative assessment groups of pesticides for their effects on the nervous system (EFSA et al., 2019a). The collected NOAEL values were based on acute effects on motor division observed in toxicity studies as indicated in the Table 12.

Table 12 Hazard characterisation of pesticides in CAG-NAM to be considered in acute cumulative risk assessment (EFSA et al., 2019a)

Pesticide	Indicator of specific effect	Study type	NOAEL (mg/kg bw)
Triazophos	AChE inhibition (erythrocytes)	1-year dog	0.012
Deltamethrin	Ataxia, landing-foot splay, tremor	1-year dog (capsule)	1

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Pesticide	Indicator of specific effect	Study type	NOAEL (mg/kg bw)
Omethoate	Increased motor activity, tremor, abnormal gait, reduced grip strength	Acute neurotoxicity rat (gavage)	0.35
Chlormequat	Ataxia	1-year dog (diet)	10
Thiram	Reduced grip strength	Acute neurotoxicity rat	5
Cypermethrin, beta-	Abnormal gait, tremor	90-day dog (capsule)	1
Cypermethrin, alpha-	Ataxia	90-day dog (diet)	2.3
Cyhalothrin, lambda-	Ataxia, tremor, convulsion	1-year dog (capsule) Acute neurotoxicity rat (gavage)	0.5
Azinphos-ethyl	AChE inhibition (erythrocytes)	90-day dog (diet)	0.0125
Formetanate	Ataxia, tremor, reduced motor activity	Acute neurotoxicity rat (gavage)	1

For CAG-NAM, the FUE values retrieved from the literature when available were included in Table 14. The feasibility to obtain realistic FUE through PBK modelling for the ones that are missing will be evaluated with WG3.

Urinary metabolites were selected on the basis of HBM data availability (HBM4EU and ESTEBAN survey as first application) and toxicokinetic relevance. Thus, for triazophos two metabolites (DEP, DETP) were identified, whereas for alpha-cypermethrin, beta-cypermethrin, lambda-cyhalothrin and azinphos-ethyl unique metabolites were identified in the context of this project. For deltamethrin, 3PBA and cis-DBCA were both analytically determined in urinary samples from the ESTEBAN cohort. However, cis-DBCA has been recognised as more relevant biomarker for deltamethrin exposure based on higher urinary excretion rate in comparison to 3PBA (Apel et al., 2023) and thus it was selected as a unique metabolite for deltamethrin in this project. Pesticides with unknown metabolites (chlormequat, thiram, formetanate) were not considered further in the cumulative risk assessment (Table 14).

The anthropometry- and gender-based reference value for the urinary 24-h creatinine excretion (CE) of healthy children and body weights was obtained from Remer et al., (2002) (Table 13).

Table 13 Calculation of an anthropometry- and gender-based reference value for creatinine excretion in urine (CE value in g of creatinine per day) for children (based on data from Remer et al. 2002)

Gender	Creatinine excretion (g creatinine/day)		
	6-8y	9-13 years	14-18 years
Boys	0.49	0.76	1.47
Girls	0.45	0.72	1.23

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HMB data: As for CAG-NAN, the population of interest was children, as they were the individuals at risk according to the threshold of regulatory concern in the EFSA risk assessment (van Klaveren et al., 2019; EFSA, 2019; EFSA et al., 2020a). Urinary concentrations from the ESTEBAN study (France) were also used to perform a pilot risk assessment for CAG-NAM. In van Klaveren et al. (2019) annexes, for the other children population in France, triazophos, deltamethrin, omethoate, chlormequat, beta-cypermethrin, lambda-cyhalothrin, thiram, oxamyl, formetanate, alpha-cypermethrin, azinphos-ethyl and chlorpropham were those contributing the most to French children' exposure. In ESTEBAN, data were available for 491 children from 6-17 years of age (Table 15).

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Table 14 Selection of urinary metabolites for CAG-NAM

Prioritised chemical	Family	MoA	Urinary metabolite analytically identified (HBM4EU)	Proposed selection of metabolite based on literature	Urinary metabolite (ESTEBAN cohort)	Final selection of metabolite considering data availability in ESTEBAN cohort	FUE % (molar)
Triazophos	Organophosphate	AChE inhibitor	DEP, DETP	DEP ⁽³⁾ , DETP	DEP, DETP	DEP, DETP	<i>tbd</i> (PBPK modelling)
Deltamethrin	Pyrethroid	Binding to VGSC	DBCA (= Br2CA), 3-PBA, DBCA+C6H8O6	DBCA ^{(1) (2)}	3PBA, (cis-DBCA is also measured)	cis-DBCA	45 ^{(1) (2)}
Omethoate	Organophosphate	AChE inhibitor	DMP, DMTP	DMP, DMTP	DMP, DMTP	DMP, DMTP	<i>tbd</i> (PBPK modelling)
Chlormequat	Quarternary ammonium compound	Partial agonist of mAChR & nAChR	Unknown biomarkers – not considered further				
Thiram	Dithiocarbamate	Neurotoxicity due to the metabolite CS2 (presumed)	Unknown biomarkers – not considered further				
Cypermethrin, beta-	Pyrethroid	Binding to VGSC	3PBA, cis DCCA (= cis Cl2CA), trans DCCA (= trans Cl2CA), DCCA, DCCA+C6H8O6	DCCA ⁽¹⁾	3PBA, (cis and trans-DCCA is also measured)	DCCA	36 ⁽¹⁾
Cypermethrin, alpha-	Pyrethroid	Binding to VGSC	3PBA, cis DCCA, trans DCCA, DCCA, DCCA+C6H8O6	DCCA ⁽¹⁾	3PBA, (cis and trans-DCCA is also measured)	DCCA	36 ⁽¹⁾
Cyhalothrin, lambda-	Pyrethroid	Binding to VGSC	3PBA, ClF3CA	ClF3CA ⁽¹⁾	3PBA	3PBA	25.1 ⁽¹⁾
Azinphos-ethyl	Organophosphate	AChE inhibitor	DMP, DMTP, DMDTP	DMP, DMTP, DMDTP ⁽⁴⁾	DMP, DMTP, DMDTP	DMDTP	<i>tbd</i> (PBPK modelling)
Formetanate	Carbamate	AChE inhibitor	Unknown biomarkers – not considered further				

(1) (Tarazona et al., 2022) (2) (Apel et al., 2023) (3)(Wongta et al., 2022) (4) (Quirós-Alcalá et al., 2012) DET: Diethyl phosphate; DETP: Diethyl thiophosphate; DMP: Dimethyl phosphate; DMTP: Dimethyl thiophosphate; DMDTP: Dimethyl dithiophosphate; DBCA: 3-(2,2-dibromovinyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropane carboxylic acid; 3-PBA: 3-Phenoxybenzoic acid; DBCA+C6H8O6: glucuronide conjugate of DBCA; DCCA: 2,2-(dichlorovinyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropane carboxylic acids; DCCA+C6H8O6 glucuronide conjugate of DCCA; ClF3CA: 3-(2-chloro-3,3-trifluoroprop-1-enyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropanecarboxylic acid.

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9.1.5.2. Low tiered risk assessment using reverse dosimetry

The reverse dosimetry presented in Section 9.1.2 was used to perform CAG-NAM mixture risk assessment. In reverse dosimetry approach, urinary concentration of the selected metabolites from individual HBM data were used to calculate the Estimated Daily Intake (EDI) of the parent pesticide (Figure 30, equation a) and combined with the NOAEL values presented in Table 12 to estimate the MOE for each mixture component (Figure 30, equation b).

As for CAG-NAN, when the urinary concentration was <LOD, a value of 0 was attributed and when it was >LOD but <LOQ, half of the LOQ was assigned. At urinary concentrations > LOQ the creatinine-adjusted concentration was used based on anthropometry and gender specific data for 24-hours urinary creatinine excretion in healthy children aged 3–18 years from Remer et al. (2002).

As specific fractions of urinary excretion (FUE) were not available for all the selected substances, two scenarios were considered. FUE value of 0.95 (Šulc et al., 2022) was used as a best-case scenario for all compounds and 0.5 or 0.05 as worst-case scenario for organophosphate and pyrethroid pesticides, respectively. The FUE of 0.05 was selected as a worst-case scenario for the pyrethroids in CAG-NAM since based on available literature “realistic” values the degree of excretion is lower than 50% of the amount of the administered dose, i.e., FUE<0.5 (Table 15) (Khemiri et al., 2017; Tarazona et al., 2022). The FUE of 0.5 was selected as a worst case for organophosphates in the CAG-NAM, assuming complete metabolism of the organophosphate to the metabolites identified in the HBM4EU studies. Limited published information supports this approach. For triazophos the main urinary metabolite has been found to represent 85% of the radioactivity excreted by this route (FAO/WHO, 2002). In human, 76-100% of radioactivity was reported to be excreted in urine, 24 hours after oral dosing with P-dimethoate (WHO/IPCS, 1989). It is expected that PBK modelling will provide more relevant information and lower the underlying uncertainty.

At this stage cumulative risk assessment calculations were performed for all substances included in Table 15 using reverse dosimetry.

Table 15 Summary of the data used to perform risk assessment for the CAG-NAM (N=491 individuals). LOD: limit of detection, LOQ: limit of quantification, %>LOQ: percentage on quantified levels

Active substance	Considered metabolite(s)	Specificity	LOD (µg/L)	LOQ (µg/L)	%>LOQ
Triazophos	DEP	Common	0.3	0.6	21,6%
	DETP	Common	0.3	0.6	36,7%
Deltamethrin	Cis-DBCA	Specific	0.005	0.015	99,6%
Omethoate	DMP	Common	0.8	2	40%

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Active substance	Considered metabolite(s)	Specificity	LOD (µg/L)	LOQ (µg/L)	%>LOQ
	DMP	Common	0.3	0.6	92,7%
Cypermethrin,-beta	Cis-DCCA Trans-DCCA	Common	0.005	0.015	99,4%
Cypermethrin-alpha		Common	0.005	0.015	98,7%
Cylothrin,-lambda	3-PBA	Common	0.005	0.015	99,6%
Azinphos-ethyl	DMDTP	Common	0.3	0.6	0,2%

9.1.5.3. Preliminary risk results from ESTEBAN survey

The total margin of exposure (MOET) was estimated for selected priority pesticides using HBM data from ESTEBAN for various percentiles of exposure and applying reverse dosimetry.

Table 16 Total margin of exposure (MOET) using the reverse dosimetry approach, calculated using HBM data from ESTEBAN for various percentiles of exposure (CAG-NAM, lower tier).

Data	Approach	Scenario	Population	MOET, 50th percentile	MOET,95th percentile	MOET,99th percentile	MOET 99.9th percentile	% of individual with MOET<100
EFSA 2019	Tier I		6 to <10 y	281	98	60.1	28.6	3.19%
EFSA 2019	Tier II		6 to <10 y	2750	792	318	84.3	0.088%
ESTEBAN	Lower Tier	Best case	6 to <10y	203.1	14.2	9.4	6.3	34.89%
ESTEBAN	Lower Tier	Worst case	6 to <10y	106.9	7.5	4.9	3.3	61.74%
ESTEBAN	Lower Tier	Best case	6 to 18y	342.6	16.4	7.8	1.3	26.48%
ESTEBAN	Lower Tier	Worst case	6 to 18y	180.3	8.6	4.1	0.7	52.74%

Best case: scenario where FUE=0.95

Worst case: scenario where FUE=0.5 for organophosphates and 0.05 for pyrethroids

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The results for the CAG-NAM differed from the respective values using the EFSA approach (EFSA, 2019) within a factor of 10 for the best-case scenario.

9.1.5.4. Next steps

At a later stage, the contribution of each active substance to the MOET will be estimated and the main contributors will be identified to refine the assessment. One alternative for refinement would be using FUE values specific for each mixture component, obtained either based the literature data or estimated using PBPK modelling. A cumulative risk assessment calculation for all substances included in Table 15 using forward dosimetry will also be performed.

9.2. Metals and kidney effects

9.2.1. Context and objectives

Chronic exposure to certain metals, even at relatively low doses, may induce nephrotoxicity in humans. In addition, it is known that a combined exposure to mixtures of (some of) these metals occur in humans, e.g., through dietary and/or occupational exposure. In the context of the HBM4EU project, an Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) for 4 toxic metals inducing nephrotoxicity in humans was developed. The focus was on the following metals: arsenic (As), cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb) and mercury (Hg). The common adverse outcome was identified as renal dysfunction due to proximal tubular damage. However, it was concluded that it was difficult to distinct between an adverse effect of these toxic metals on glomeruli and/or tubuli. Therefore, in this case study the common adverse effect of metals in humans is defined as nephrotoxicity, keeping in mind that nephrotoxicity is focussed on glomerular and/or tubular damage.

The risk assessment of the internal exposure to a single chemical is based on the comparison of the actual, internal exposure level (HBM-EL) to an acceptable internal toxicological value (HBM-TV) (section 5.1.2). In case the HBM-TV includes an uncertainty factor, and the HBM-EL is below the HBM-TV, in other words $HBM-EL / HBM-TV < 1$, the risk is acceptable. In case $HBM-EL / HBM-TV$ is equal to or above 1, the risk is not negligible and should be explored in more detail. This HBM-TV is, depending on the organisation/institute, called HBM-Guidance Value (HBM-GV), Biomonitoring Equivalent (BE), Biological Exposure Index (BEI) or Biological Limit Value (BLV). Whenever the HBM-TV of the components of a mixture is based on a common effect (i.e., nephrotoxicity) dose addition can be applied, and the $HBM-EL / HBM-TV$ ratios of the components can be summed to obtain a modified Reference Point Index (mRPI) (Section 6.2). The determination of such mRPI is considered a first (or lower) tier approach in mixture risk assessment (Section 9.2.3). As mentioned above, in some cases an uncertainty factor (UF) is incorporated in the HBM-TV and to make this clear we have defined the internal HBM-TV as follows: $HBM-TV_i = HBM-RP_i / UF_i$, where $HBM-RP_i$ stands for the HBM-Reference Point of compound i .

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The goal of this case study is to determine the mRPI of a mixture of four toxic metals based on HBM data available in Europe and HBM-GVs for these metals in blood and/or urine.

9.2.2. Data availability

The (first tier) mixture risk assessment of the combined internal exposure to four toxic metals will be based on the determination of the mRPI (see above and Section 9.2.3). Therefore, information of two important components is needed: HBM data (concentrations of relevant exposure biomarkers in biological matrices) and the guidance value (HBM-GV) for the internal exposure of each of these metals.

HBM data of these toxic metals are available for different general subpopulations in various European countries (Section 3.1). In addition, there is an occupational dataset describing exposure of E-waste workers to three of these metals (Hg, Pb, Cd). These data are being compiled in WG1 and presented in Section 3.

In WG2 (the hazard WG), available HBM-GVs for several metals are being evaluated from the HBM-GV database (Section 5.1.3). In case a guidance value is missing, HBM-TV is preliminary established in combining available information from bibliography on a HBM reference point (HBM-RP) for the nephrotoxic effect of that particular metal and, if necessary, an uncertainty factor (UF) (Section 5.1.2). In order to combine HBM data and HBM-TVs there are 4 basic requirements: 1) the HBM-TVs should refer to the same exposure biomarker that has been measured, e.g. inorganic mercury; 2) the HBM-TV should refer to the same biological matrix in which the exposure biomarker has been measured, e.g. inorganic mercury in urine; 3) if the HBM-TV has been established for a specific subpopulation (e.g. children, adults or workers) the exposure biomarker should have been measured in this subpopulation and 4) exposure biomarker concentrations and HBM-TVs should have the same unit.

With respect to the latter requirement, we should keep in mind that the toxicokinetics of the mixture components may also play a role. For example, due to exposure frequency/duration and the rate of elimination of a chemical, large fluctuations may occur in the urinary concentration of an exposure biomarker. In addition, diuresis may also have an effect on the urinary concentration of an exposure biomarker. This could mean that an HBM-TV in urine refers to e.g., morning urine, 24-hour urine or that the urinary biomarker concentration is corrected for diuresis (e.g., if correction is made on the basis of creatinine excretion, the HBM-TV could be expressed as $\mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine instead of $\mu\text{g/L}$).

This means that HBM data and HBM-TVs should be well tuned to one another.

9.2.3. Risk assessment using a tiered approach

Based on the common effect of metals on the kidney, it was decided to determine the risk of combined exposure to these metals by calculating the modified Reference Point Index (mRPI). This can be done by following a tiered approach.

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Tiered approach

The lower tier approach in hazard assessment lacks refinement and specification of uncertainties. Therefore, whenever the lower tier mRPI is higher than 1, a second (or higher) tier is deemed necessary.

In the present lower tier, the mRPI is defined as follows:

$$mRPI_{low} = \frac{HBM\ EL_{As}}{HBM\ RP_{As}/UF_{As}} + \frac{HBM\ EL_{Cd}}{HBM\ RP_{Cd}/UF_{Cd}} + \frac{HBM\ EL_{Hg}}{HBM\ RP_{Hg}/UF_{Hg}} + \frac{HBM\ EL_{Pb}}{HBM\ RP_{Pb}/UF_{Pb}} \quad (1)$$

With HBM-EL = exposure level (i.e., exposure biomarker concentration) from HBM data

For the higher tier hazard assessment, the relative potency factors (RPFs) of the mixture components are determined (potencies relative to an index compound, Section 6.2). These RPFs should be based on a specified common adverse effect determined for the various mixture components in a study (in a biological matrix) or in different studies with the same study design. For example, in case of nephrotoxicity, the glomerular filtration rate (GFR or eGFR) has been determined in a study (or similar studies) in a specified (sub)population in which also the various metals (including their metabolites) have been determined. The summed internal exposure equivalents are compared to the HBM-TV (=HBM-RP_{index}/UF_{index}) of the index compound. In equation (2), cadmium is the index compound.

$$mRPI_{high} = \frac{HBM\ EL_{index} + HBM\ EL_{As} \cdot RPF_{As} + HBM\ EL_{Hg} \cdot RPF_{Hg} + HBM\ EL_{Pb} \cdot RPF_{Pb}}{HBM\ RP_{index}/UF_{index}} \quad (2)$$

For the selected four metals (As, Cd, Hg and Pb) these RPFs are not available yet. In order to determine whether the mRPI is below or above 1, the mRPI is calculated according to equation (1), see Figure 32 on the general approach used for metal case study.

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Figure 32. General approach applied to metals case study

HBM data

The exposure level of each metal in a population can be expressed in two ways: 1) at the population level and 2) at the individual level. If HBM data are only available on a population level, then the mean (P50) or high exposure levels (P95) can be used. If mean and high exposure levels for each metal are significantly different, adding up P95 levels could lead to a serious overestimation of the mRPI. If HBM data are available at the individual level, the mRPI should be calculated for each individual within a (sub)population and subsequently the distribution of the individual mRPIs should be calculated and expressed as P50 and P95 values. In fact, expressing the mRPI at the individual level is a refinement of the aggregated population level and uncertainties will be reduced. Therefore, in terms of exposure assessment, calculating the individual exposure is considered as a higher tier approach (Table 17). In this project, as HBM data are available, we will use the higher tier of exposure to calculate mRPI. Referring to the above, we have a lower and higher tier in the exposure as well as the hazard part of the risk assessment which can be summarised as follows:

Table 17 Lower and higher tier in the exposure and hazard assessment

Tier	Exposure	Hazard
Low	at population level	no RPFs, use 4 HBM-TVs, 1 for each metal
High	at individual level	RPFs, use 1 HBM-TV of reference compound

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HBM-TV data

In the past, HBM-GVs have been published and gathered in the HBM-GV database (Section 5.1.3) for some of these metals in blood and/or urine and sometimes specifically for certain subpopulations, e.g., for workers or the general population.

In case, we have several HBM-RPs for a specific metal, we will select one on the basis of the 4 requirements mentioned in Section 9.2.2 on data availability. This comes down to combining an HBM-TV with corresponding HBM data based on 1) the same exposure biomarker; 2) the same matrix; 3) the same (sub)population and 4) the same unit.

In case we do not have an HBM-GV for a specific metal we need to derive an HBM-TV based on the common effect of nephrotoxicity. In general, HBM-TVs can be derived in different ways, based on an external (toxicological) reference points (derived from animal or human studies) or on dose-response relationships based on an (internal) effect biomarker measured after exposure of humans to a metal and, if needed, an adequate UF is applied (Section 5.1.2). The latter approach is preferred due to the fact that most HBM-TVs for metals are derived in this way and that, most likely, this will introduce less uncertainty.

9.2.4. Preliminary results for HBM data and selected HBM-TV

HBM data

The Figure 32 shows a first extraction of the data inventory (Section 3) where, there are 9 studies available with HBM data for the 4r metals in several countries (n = 8). Several (sub)populations have been identified (e.g., children, teenagers, adults, 1 for workers with 3 metals (Cd, Hg, Pb), etc.). More HBM data are coming for other countries such as NL, CZ, etc. A deeper investigation of the databases is in progress to evaluate the nature of exposure biomarkers, the biological matrices, the unit, the sampling period, etc.

HBM-TV

The available HBM-RPs from the HBM-GV dataset (Section 5.1.3) considering the two different matrices (blood or urine) have been summarised in Table 18. Question marks are explained in the legend and refer to future work that needs to be carried out. Only in the case of cadmium, UFs (so-called assessment factors) have been applied to the HBM-RP for the general population and workers to derive HBM-TVs.

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Table 18 Availability of HBM-RPs for the selected metals (As, Cd, Hg and Pb) in blood and urine

	As	Cd	Hg	Pb
Blood	? ¹	√	? ²	? ³
<i>Ref</i>	<i>Auth</i>	<i>Auth/Org</i>	<i>Org</i>	<i>Org</i>
Urine	? ⁴	√	√	NA
<i>Ref</i>	<i>Auth</i>	<i>Auth</i>	<i>Org</i>	-

√ = Available; Ref = Reference; Auth = Author; Org = Organisation; NA = not available;

¹ to be determined (from Lin et al., (2020))

² HBM-I and HBM-II values are available, but it is not clear for which adverse effect

³ BMDL from EFSA and BLV from ECHA differ a factor 10-17

⁴ BE value not based on nephrotoxicity (Hays et al., 2010)

9.2.5. Next steps

Work planned for the coming months regarding the selection of the HBM-TV values (i.e., HBM-RPs and UFs) and the start of the lower tier risk assessment can be summarised as follows:

1. Establish HBM-RPs
 - In which unit: Cd (and As and Hg)
 - In which matrix: As and Hg
 - For which forms/substance(s): As and Hg
 - For which (sub)population: Pb (and Cd)
 - Which HBM-RP to use: Cd, Hg, Pb
2. Determine uncertainties (UFs)
 - Start with: Cd and Pb (maybe also Hg)
3. Interact with WG1 (HBM data) and WG3 (kinetics)
 - Relevant for: As, Hg, Pb

A first application of the lower tier approach is planned to be performed to the ESTEBAN survey (FR) and the Doetinchem Cohort Study (NL). Once the whole approach will be well defined from this pilot study, it will be applied by each partner with HBM data involved in this case study.

9.3. PFAS and immune effects

9.3.1. Context and objectives

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EFSA's CONTAM panel performed a risk assessment for PFAS in which they determined impaired vaccination response as the critical effect. A cumulative risk assessment of four PFAS (PFOA, PFOS, PFNA and PFHxS, hereafter called 'EFSA-4') was performed assuming equal potencies and a TWI of 4.4 ng/kg bw/week was established (EFSA CONTAM Panel et al., 2020). The TWI was determined based on a PBK modelling approach linking serum concentration considered to be without deleterious effects with the corresponding intake. According to the risk assessment several segments of the European population are exposed to critical PFAS levels above the determined TWI. PFAS contaminates our environment generally and at 'hot spots' and therefore also our foods including drinking water, which is considered the dominating human exposure source. Use of HBM data reflects the aggregated exposure, including also other sources of exposure.

The extrapolation of the BMDL₁₀ to the TWI consisted of several intermediate steps, of which one was a predicted serum level of 6.9 ng 'EFSA-4' PFAS/mL in mothers (35 years old) obtained with PBK modelling (EFSA CONTAM Panel et al., 2020). This value should protect their children from reaching a body burden of 17.5 ng 'EFSA-4' PFAS/mL via breastfeeding. PBK simulated concentrations of PFOS (4.9 ng/mL) and PFOA (2 ng/mL) at age 35, together present the value of 6.9 ng EFSA-4 PFAS/mL, where EFSA assumed that the toxicokinetics of PFOA = PFNA, and that of PFOS = PFHxS. Among others in HBM4EU, this value of 6.9 ng/mL has been used as HBM-GV for the EFSA-4 PFAS.

In HBM4EU, a comparative case study of PFAS MRAs was carried out using data from 9 HBM studies across Europe where blood of teenagers was measured for 12 PFAS (Bil et al., 2023b). In this paper, 3 approaches for mixture risk assessment of PFAS were explored: (1) the EFSA \sum 4 approach, 2) the RPF approach, 3) the HI approach. The HI approach resulted in the highest risk estimates, followed by the RPF approach and the sum value approach. The assessments indicated that PFAS exposure may result in a health risk in a considerable fraction of individuals in the HBM4EU teenager study, thereby confirming the conclusion drawn in the recent EFSA scientific opinion.

The latter study implemented internal RPFs that were derived based on hepatotoxicity in rodents (Bil, Zeilmaker and Bokkers, 2022). However, in 2020, EFSA established a tolerable weekly intake for four PFAS assuming equal toxic potency for immune suppressive effects in humans. Therefore, we explored the possibility of deriving RPFs for immune suppressive effects using available data in rodents and humans (Bil et al., 2023a). Internal RPFs were successfully derived for PFAS based on rat thymus weight, spleen weight, and globulin concentration. The available dose–response information for blood cell counts did not show a significant trend. Immunotoxic potency in serum was determined in the order PFDA > PFNA > PFHxA > PFOS > PFBS > PFOA > PFHxS (Table 19). Risk assessment using these latter internal RPFs for immune suppressive effects in humans is proposed for the PFAS case study.

9.3.2. Data availability

The following data will be used to perform PFAS MRAs using the MCRA tool:

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- The available internal RPFs derived from rodent and human data for immunotoxicity in Bil et al. (2023a) (Section 9.3.1 and 9.3.3, Table 19).
- The existing immunotoxicity related HBM-GV from EFSA (Section 9.3.1).
- The PFAS data available from HBM studies in European countries (Section 9.3.5)

9.3.3. Risk assessment using internal RPFs

To perform mixture risk assessment, the concentrations of PFAS measured in one individual will be multiplied with the respective internal RPFs of the PFAS compounds to obtain PFOA equivalent (PEQ) blood levels. After that, the PEQ blood levels are summed to obtain a PEQ blood level per individual. Then, relevant subgroups are established. Because the EFSA TWI is based on a transgenerational developmental immunotoxicity effect, women of reproductive age and their future children are the most sensitive sub-population (EFSA CONTAM Panel et al., 2020). Therefore, PEQ population distributions will be established to gain insight in the sensitive sub-population in comparison to the entire study population. Subsequently, the PEQ distributions of the women of reproductive age and the entire population will be compared to the HBM-GV.

To interpret the risk from exposure to PFAS mixtures, the sum PEQ values for women of reproductive age in the entire population will be compared to the HBM-GV of 6.9 ng/mL and to an age-dependent HBM-GV curve (Figure 33 and Table 20).

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Table 19 Internal relative potency factors (RPFs) and lower and upper bounds of the 90%-confidence intervals for per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) based on thymus weight, spleen weight, globulin concentration, and liver weight in the male rat.

Substance	Abs. thymus 28d ^a		Rel. thymus 28d ^a		Abs. spleen 28d ^a		Rel. liver 28d ^a		Rel. liver 42-90d ^b	
	Internal RPF	LB and UB 90% CI	Internal RPF	LB and UB 90% CI	Internal RPF	LB and UB 90% CI	Internal RPF	LB and UB 90% CI	Internal RPF	LB and UB 90% CI
PFBA	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.0	0.69-1.4	1.8	1.1-2.7
PFHxA	6.4	5.3-7.9	6.8	5.2-11	NR	NR	5.6	3.6-8.1	12	8.7-15
PFOA	1.0		1.0		1.0		1.0		1.0	
PFNA	6.5	5.5-8.0	6.8	5.4-11	6.5	4.6-9.3	4.3	2.9-5.9	5.5	4.5-7.1
PFDA	6.1	Inf-Inf	NR	NR	12	5.7-19	7.4	5.0-11	-	-
PFDoDA	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	11	8.3-14
PFBS	1.8	1.5-2.2	2.1	1.7-3.3	0.72	0.27-1.3	1.8	1.3-2.4	0.19	0.13-0.27
PFHxS	0.54	0.0-0.72	0.65	0.0-1.0	0.26	0.11-0.44	0.58	0.40-0.78	0.61	0.46-0.78
PFOS	3.9	3.2-4.8	4.4	3.5-7.0	2.4	1.4-3.6	5.4	4.0-7.0	3.5	2.2-5.0
HFPO-DA	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	25	17-35	8.8	6.5-12

Note: -, no data; CI, confidence interval; HFPO-DA, hexafluoropropylene oxide-dimer acid; Inf, infinity; LB, lower bound; NR, no significant trend in the dose-response analysis; PFBA, perfluorobutanoic acid; PFBS, perfluorobutane sulfonic acid; PFDA, perfluorodecanoic acid; PFHxA, perfluorohexanoic acid; PFHxS, perfluorohexane sulfonic acid; PFNA, perfluorononanoic acid; PFOA, perfluorooctanoic acid; PFOS, perfluorooctane sulfonic acid; UB, upper bound.

^a As presented in Bil et al. (2023a)

^b As presented in Bil et al. (2022)

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Figure 33 Sum PFOA and PFOS serum levels in women over time, based on Figure 12 and 13 in the EFSA opinion (2020). Newborns are exposed via breast feeding only, which ceases at age 1. After age 1 a weekly exposure to the TWI of 4.4 ng PFAS/kg bw results in a serum level of 6.9 ng/mL at age 35. On x-axis: age (years). Y-axis: serum level (ng/mL) of PFOA, PFOS and sum of both PFAS.

Table 20 The simulated EFSA-4 PFAS blood levels in women (aged 15-50) per year of age.

Age (year)	Sum EFSA-4 PFAS concentration in serum (ng/mL)	Age (year)	Sum EFSA-4 PFAS concentration in serum (ng/mL)
1	17.5	26	6.1
2	9.4	27	6.2
3	6.4	28	6.3
4	5.0	29	6.4
5	4.4	30	6.5
6	4.1	31	6.6
7	3.9	32	6.7
8	3.9	33	6.7
9	4.0	34	6.8
10	4.1	35	6.9
11	4.2	36	7.0
12	4.3	37	7.0
13	4.5	38	7.1
14	4.6	39	7.1
15	4.8	40	7.2
16	4.9	41	7.2
17	5.0	42	7.3

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18	5.2	43	7.3
19	5.3	44	7.4
20	5.4	45	7.4
21	5.6	46	7.4
22	5.7	47	7.5
23	5.8	48	7.5
24	5.9	49	7.5
25	6.0	50	7.5

9.3.4. Preliminary risk assessment results from ESTEBAN survey

To illustrate the methodology, a first pilot mixture risk assessment (MRA) is planned to be performed in early 2023 with the use of the Esteban data (Fillol et al., 2021). Some preliminary results are described below.

In the Esteban study, the levels of 17 individual PFAS exposure biomarkers were determined in two sub-samples of the Esteban study population, in adults (N = 744) and children (N = 249), resulting in assessment of exposure to 993 individuals in total. Concentrations of PFAS in serum were quantified using LC-MS/MS. The Esteban study showed that multiple PFAS were detected in the French population (6 or 7 PFAS in >40% of the children and adults respectively). PFOS and PFOA were the main detected PFAS in both children and adults. Women of reproductive age were defined as having an age between 15 and 49 (Kantorová et al., 2020).

MRA was performed with Esteban data for women between 15- and 49 years old (N = 215), allowing inclusion of 9 PFAS (PFBA, PFHxA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFDoDA, PFBS, PFHxS, and PFOS) in the MRA by using RPFs (Section 9.3.1 and Table 19). Two data treatments were applied to the censored data: a lower bound scenario where values <LOD = 0, and values between LOD-LOQ = LOD; and an upper bound scenario where values <LOD = LOD, and values between LOD-LOQ = LOQ. The cumulative risk was expressed as the percentage of women with a sum PEQ serum concentration exceeding the HBM-GV. Table 21 shows the first results of this pilot study. The percentage of women above the HBM-GV of 6.9 ng/mL is 96% and 98% for the lower and upper bound scenario respectively.

Table 21 Sum PFOA Equivalent Exposure (PEQ) for 9 PFAS (PFBA, PFHxA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFDoDA, PFBS, PFHxS, PFOS) in ng/mL for women of reproductive age (n = 215) in the Esteban study population (preliminary results, will be revised).

Scenario	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Number of individuals	215	215
P5 Sum PEQ (ng/mL)	7.72	8.62
P50 Sum PEQ (ng/mL)	18.89	20.57
P95 Sum PEQ (ng/mL)	52.15	52.84
P97.5 Sum PEQ (ng/mL)	65.48	66.17
Mixture Risk (% above HBM-GV)	96	98

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9.3.5. Next steps

Later in 2023, available HBM exposure data for the relevant PFAS uploaded to MCRA will be used to perform MRAs, with a special focus on sensitive subgroups. Studies available in WG1 and the biomarkers they measured are reported in the Table 22 below.

Table 22 PFAS data available from HBM studies in European countries part of WG1.

29 biomarkers			31 studies		
PBBS	PFHxS	PFUnA	ABC / FETOTOX	ESTEBAN	study
PFBA	PFNA	PFUnDA	ACCEPT	EuroMix	HELIX_MoBA
PFBS	PFOA	FHpA	BEA	EXHES-Greece	INMA-Asturias
PFBSm	PFOS	N-EtFOSAA	BIOAMBIENT.ES	EXHES-Spain	INMA-Granada
PFDA	PFOSA	N-MeFOSAA	BOC-DNBC	FLEHS II	NEB II
PFDoA	PFFPA		BOC-GRL	FLEHS III	NEB II
PFDoDA	PFFPeA		CELSPAC: Young	FLEHS IV	PCB cohort
PFDS	PFTeA		Adults	GerES V	POPUP-cohort
PFHoS	PFTeDA		CELSPAC-FIREexpo	GerES VI	Riksmaten Ungdom
PFHpA	PFTTrA		CROME	GerES V-sub	SEPAGES
PFHpS	PFTTrDA		ESB	HBM4EU chromatates	
PFHxA	PFUDA				

To improve and extend the mixture risk assessment methodology, we will search for new and relevant hazard data for PFAS. We will explore data availability for associations between PFAS exposure and responses to Covid-19 vaccinations and other vaccinations. In parallel, we will look into derivation of RPFs based on *in vitro* information for immunotoxicity of PFAS in combination with QIVIVE modelling. Interested partners are invited to collaborate with (future) *in vitro* data on immunotoxicity of PFAS.

9.4. Developmental neurotoxicity (DNT)

9.4.1. Context, objectives and levels of evidence for DNT effects

At first it was agreed to follow a tiered approach similarly to other case study (e.g., CAG-NAN and CAG-NAM), for which EFSA developed CAGs and performed dietary cumulative risk assessment (CRA), which consisted of including prioritised pesticides (phase 1) and, in a further step, chemicals identified in the relevant scientific literature (Grandjean and Landrigan, 2006, 2014)(phase 2) (Section 2.1.3 Figure 2). In phase 3, chemicals identified in real-life mixtures (e.g., HBM studies) would also be considered. However, since a CAG for pesticides inducing developmental neurotoxicity (DNT) has not been developed yet by EFSA and taking into account risk management priorities, the strategy was shifted to start with metal(oid) compounds. Therefore, data from WG1 on HBM exposure will be used to prioritise real-life mixtures, and such exposures will be linked to DNT health effects.

Three possibilities were identified for selection of DNT endpoints/health effects:

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1. Use of neurodevelopmental disorders (NDD) as human DNT outcomes. According to the DMS-V, (American Psychiatric Association, 2022) human NDD are classified in 7 groups:
 - Intellectual disabilities (IQ)
 - Communication disorders
 - Autism spectrum disorders
 - Attention Deficit and Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD)
 - Specific learning disorders
 - Motor disorders
 - Other NDDs
2. Use of DNT *in vitro* battery (IVB) endpoints (e.g., reported by Blum et al. (2023)) which are based on key biological processes underlying the development of the nervous system:
 - Neural progenitor cell proliferation
 - Migration
 - Differentiation
 - Neurite outgrowth
 - Synaptogenesis
 - Functional endpoints related to non-neuronal cells (e. g., myelination)
 - Neural network formation
3. Use of DNT endpoints from Regulatory Toxicology studies (OECD TG 426 or US-EPA OPPTS 870.6300) based on *in vivo* studies wherein exposure covered pre- and early postnatal (lactation) periods. The endpoints derived from these pivotal studies include:
 - Ontogeny of developmental reflexes
 - Behavioural and functional tests: (loco)motor activity, auditory startle response, learning and memory (cognition)
 - Neuropathology observations
 - Brain morphometry: changes in dimensions of brain structures
 - Brain weight relative/absolute
 - Functional, behavioural, and neuroanatomical abnormalities are assessed in offspring.

Despite using a different approach, this DNT case study shows some synergies with the work recently conducted by EFSA on the development of an AOP-informed IATA (Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment) for DNT hazard identification and characterization of the insecticide deltamethrin (EFSA PPR Panel et al., 2021). Both the IATA developed by EFSA and this case study share the assessment of the applicability of the DNT *in vitro* testing battery (IVB) designed to explore fundamental neurodevelopmental processes that might be disrupted by exposure to chemical substances.

Due to the complexity of DNT endpoints and the currently available resources, the case study will build up on previous work by PARC colleagues (Corinne Sprong and Andreas Kortenkamp) who developed a case study focused on IQ decline under the EU funded project ATHLETE.

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9.4.2. Data availability

Information on levels of chemicals and metabolites (if appropriate) will be available from HBM studies inventoried in this project (Section 3). Therefore, HBM studies where lead (Pb), methyl-mercury (Me-Hg) and inorganic arsenic (iAs) have been measured will be selected. Blood levels of Pb and Me-Hg and urine iAs levels are preferred as these are the chemical species and proper biological matrices for assessing internal exposure prior to proceeding with risk assessment. If blood data are not available for child population, PBK modelling can be used to estimate blood level from urine, in considering the related uncertainties.

Hazard data and HBM-GVs for specific effects (if available, otherwise for critical effects will be collected instead) will be collected from the results generated in previous or ongoing prospective cohorts (birth cohorts) as well from DNT IVB recently published (Blum et al., 2023).

Furthermore, a literature search will be conducted for prioritised metal(oid)s and potential DNT effects. Data from HBM in birth cohorts found in this search may also be used as supplementary information. A preliminary search returned the following results:

- a. Literature review on metals and DNT:
 - ("Lead"[Mesh] OR "Mercury"[Mesh] OR ("Arsenic"[Mesh])) AND (("developmental neurotoxicity") OR neurodevelopment*) -- 500 hits
 - ("Lead"[Mesh] AND "Mercury"[Mesh] AND ("Arsenic"[Mesh])) AND (("developmental neurotoxicity") OR neurodevelopment*) -- 16 hits
- b. Literature review on Lead (Pb) and developmental neurotoxicity:
 - ("Lead"[Mesh]) AND (("developmental neurotoxicity") OR neurodevelopment*) -- 274 hits (183 abstracts potentially relevant, other abstracts related only with HBM)
- c. Literature review on Mercury (Hg) and developmental neurotoxicity:
 - ("Mercury"[Mesh]) AND (("developmental neurotoxicity") OR neurodevelopment*) -- 214 hits (81 abstracts potentially relevant, association between HBM data and neurodevelopment)
- d. Literature review on Arsenic (As) and developmental neurotoxicity:
 - ("Arsenic"[Mesh]) AND (("developmental neurotoxicity") OR neurodevelopment*) -- 84 hits (66 abstracts potentially relevant)

PODs of Pb and methyl Hg related to IQ loss have already been used by EFSA for single substance risk assessment (EFSA CONTAM Panel 2010, 2012 respectively). PODs for iAs have also been derived by EFSA, but they are not related with neurotoxic effects (EFSA CONTAM Panel, 2009).

- Pb: BMDLs derived from blood lead levels in $\mu\text{g/L}$ (corresponding dietary intake values in $\mu\text{g/kg bw per day}$): developmental neurotoxicity (DNT) BMDL_{01} , 12 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (0.50 $\mu\text{g/kg bw.day}$) (EFSA CONTAM Panel, 2010);
- Me-Hg: a tolerable weekly intake (TWI) of 1.3 $\mu\text{g/kg b.w.}$ expressed as mercury (EFSA CONTAM Panel, 2012)
- iAs: No PTWI is available. Instead, BMDL_{01} (1% extra risk) between 0.3 and 8 $\mu\text{g/kg bw per day}$ for lung, skin and bladder cancer, as well as skin lesions (EFSA CONTAM Panel, 2009).

Regulatory external reference values for metal(oid)s are listed below (Wong, Roberts and Saab, 2022):

Table 23 Regulatory external reference values for metal(oid)s (Wong, Roberts and Saab, 2022).

List of current heavy metal reference values.

Metals/ Metalloids	Reference Value	Agency and Year
Inorganic Arsenic	2.14 µg/kg/day	JECFA 1988 EPA 1991 ATSDR
	0.3 µg/kg/day	2007
Cadmium	0.3 µg/kg/day	
	1 µg/kg/day	EPA 1989 JECFA 2010 EFSA 2011
	0.83 µg/kg/day	ATSDR 2012
Lead	0.36 µg/kg/day	
	0.1 µg/kg/day	
	Young Children: 0.26 µg/kg/day*	FDA 2018
Methylmercury	Older Children and Adults: 0.16 µg/kg/day**	
	0.3 µg/kg/day	ATSDR, 1999
	0.1 µg/kg/day	EPA (2001)
	0.23 µg/kg/day	JECFA 2007
Chromium (III)	0.19 µg/kg/day	EFSA 2012
	1500 µg/kg/day	EPA (1999)
Chromium (VI)	300 µg/kg/day	EFSA (2014)
	3 µg/kg/day	EPA (1998)
	0.9 µg/kg/day	ATSDR 2012
	2.2 µg/kg/day	Health Canada (2018)

*Assuming a 11.4 kg 1 year old.

**Assuming an 80 kg adult.

9.4.3. Proposed approach to identify common adverse effects and perform risk assessment

A top-down approach should be used for identifying common adverse neurodevelopmental effects and, where available, mechanistic information from a) AOPs included in the AOP-wiki or published in the open literature, and b) from two DNT IVB recently developed by EU and US-EPA scientists.

The case study on DNT is to be articulated in five steps that take new developments into account:

Step 1. Co-exposure to chemicals based on HBM data. We have started with silos instead of overarching chemicals and have focused on relevant chemicals, i.e., those which EU population is exposed to. Data from HBM studies where co-occurrence is identified for the selected chemicals (Pb, Me-Hg, iAs) in the appropriate biological matrices will be used.

Since blood from children is rarely available in the setting of birth cohorts (blood is the optimal biological matrix for lead and methylmercury analysis), TK modelling might be necessary to estimate blood levels from concentrations in other biological matrices. Total urinary Hg is not an adequate biomarker of Me-Hg exposure; instead, total Hg in blood or hair are better biomarkers to assess long-

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term Me-Hg exposure. On the other hand, the use of total urinary arsenic (tAs) to estimate iAs values is affected by high inherent uncertainty, whereas measurement of iAs in urine provides a more accurate and realistic exposure assessment. In case HBM data are not measured in the adequate biological matrices, forward dosimetry might be performed to estimate blood concentrations from external exposures.

Following the approach 2/ of the general strategy presented in Figure 2 of section 2.1.3, more chemicals with potential DNT effects will be added in this case study in regards of their real-life co-exposures with metals.

Step 2. Chemicals showing the same DNT adverse outcome/mode of action/AOPs can be grouped into the same assessment group. iAs had a high score on cognition (and behavioural changes). Initially, the focus is on IQ decline, which represents a data-rich endpoint supported by mounting epidemiological and animal studies on Pb, Me-Hg and iAs, among other chemicals. Apart from IQ decline, other DNT endpoints can also be considered through neuropsychological scales administered to children for the assessment of neurodevelopment in clinical and research settings, such as the Bayley Scale of Infant and Toddler Development (BSID-IV) or the Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children (WISC-V) is an intelligence test that measures a child’s intellectual ability and 5 cognitive domains that impact performance (Table 24).

Table 24. DNT endpoints other than IQ decline that can be obtained from neuropsychological scales (BSID-IV and WISC-V) administered to children.

Scale	Age range	Domains
BSID-IV	1-48 months	Cognition
		Motor
		Language
		Socio-emotional
		Adaptive behaviour
WISC-V	6-16 years	Verbal comprehension
		Visual spatial
		Fluid reasoning
		Working memory
		Processing speed

Impairment in any of these domains can be used as human DNT endpoints for risk assessment, including mixture risk assessment (MRA).

Growing evidence on mechanistic data has allowed to develop AOPs for DNT adverse outcomes, particularly cognitive (learning and memory) impairment as can be found in the AOP wiki (e.g., AOP:12, AOP:13, AOP:42, AOP:134, AOP:54, AOP:8). The advantage of AOPs is that some relevant processes

(Key Events) can be measured by using NAMs (e.g., IVB) or *in silico* tools, whereas the final adverse outcome can be obtained from human or *in vivo* studies.

Development of NAMs projects in PARC is meaningful for regulators because:

- Recent evidence based on an Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) has developed and assembled an IVB that allows screening of chemicals for DNT (Blum et al. 2023).
- Regulatory robustness has been addressed by performance estimates (>80% accuracy) for the IVB, based on 45 negative/positive controls.
- Concentration-response data for 120 compounds have been obtained for 10 tests covering altogether 21 endpoints.
- Gaps of the IVB have been analysed, and recommendations for the use of the IVB for regulatory testing have been put forward.

The Benchmark concentrations (BMC) for specific hits assessed in the DNT-IVB for Pb and Me-Hg is shown in Table 25 (Blum et al., 2023):

Table 25 Benchmark concentrations (BMC) for specific hits assessed in the DNT-IVB for Pb and Me-Hg

Compound	UKN2	UKN4	UKN5	NPC2a [72h]	NPC2a [120h]	NPC3	NPC4 [length]	NPC4 [area]	NPC2-5 [# of cells]	final Compound classification
Lead(II) acetate trihydrate	26,20	no hit	no hit	no hit	no hit	no hit	no hit	no hit	no hit	specific hit
Methylmercury(II) chloride	4,69	0,09	0,38	0,60	0,46	0,52	0,21	0,48	0,73	specific hit

- UKN2: Human neural crest cells generated from induced pluripotent stem cells.
- UKN4: Neurite outgrowth in human central nervous system dopaminergic neurons
- UKN5: Human iPSC-derived immature dorsal root ganglia neurons at a stage of neurite growth
- NPC2: migration (a. radial glia; b. neurons; c. oligodendrocytes)
- NPC3: neuronal differentiation
- NPC4: neuronal morphology
- NPC5: oligodendrocyte differentiation
- NPC2-5: neural progenitor cell migration and differentiation

In vivo toxicity data can be predicted using PBK modelling-based reverse dosimetry of the above *in vitro* toxicity data (i.e., BMC).

Step 3. Derivation of endpoint-specific reference values (ESRVs). Since preliminary ESRVs are uncertain at this stage and these uncertainties will impact on the risk assessment results, follow-up actions/reasoning/research will be needed to reduce uncertainties. Provisional ESRVs have been

derived by Chatterjee & Kortenkamp (Brunel University) for the ATHLETE project (below these data for metal(oid) elements) are listed in Table 26.

Table 26 Provisional ESRVs derived for lead, methyl-mercury and inorganic arsenic.

	Type of data	Matrix/Effect	Endpoint-specific reference value	Other
Lead	Epidemiology	Blood	0.54 µg/kg d	EFSA 2010
Methyl Hg	Epidemiology	Hair → blood	0.1 µg/kg d	US-EPA 2001
iAs	Epidemiology	Urine	1.3 µg/kg d	Newer studies

The ESRVs are based on external doses, so it is necessary to define internal doses to directly link them to the HBM studies using forward dosimetry (Section 9.1.2). In addition, as mentioned above, BMDL data from *in vitro* studies (e.g., IVB) can be used to derive ESRVs using reverse dosimetry by developing and applying PBK models in close collaboration with WG3.

Step 4. Exposure assessment.

Populating CAG by including chemicals to which the population is exposed to (focussing on relevant chemicals, risk drivers etc.) will be performed in a later phase. The available HBM exposure data for the relevant metal(oid)s uploaded to MCRA will be used to perform MRA. Studies available in WG1 and the biomarkers they measured are reported in Table 27 (data from ESTEBAN survey).

Table 27 Percentage of samples with urine metal(oid) concentration above the limit of quantification in the ESTEBAN survey.

(µg/L)	% Quantified
Mn	76.4
As	100
Cd	100
Hg	87.3

Step 5. MRA.

In the short term we will perform a metal(oid) MRA using the MCRA tool and will assess the uncertainties. The MRA will build on the:

- available internal ESRVs derived from IQ decline data (Sprong, unpublished)
- metal(oid) data available from HBM studies performed in EU populations
- current (or developed) HBM-GV derived for IQ (or other DNT endpoints) reported by EU funded projects, open literature, or other sources. The mixture exposure results from the MCRA tool will be compared with those HBM-GVs.

For MRA, the concentrations of the metal(oid)s (selected in phase 1 and included in the CAG) for each individual will be multiplied with the respective internal ESRV for IQ of the metal(oid) compounds to

obtain metal equivalent (MEQ) blood levels. Thereafter, these MEQ will be summed to obtain the Σ MEQ blood level per individual, which will then be compared to the HBM-GV for specific effect. Since iAs is measured in urine, reverse dosimetry will be performed to estimate blood levels in collaboration of the WG3.

As a complementary approach, a forward dosimetry (also performed by WG3) will be applied to translate the ESRVs based on external doses (available as $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw per day) to an internal reference point (HBM-GV) that will subsequently be compared to the obtained from HBM data in order to assess their similarity.

To improve and extend the MRA methodology, new and relevant DNT hazard data other than IQ for the metal(oid)s selected will be searched for.

Another approach consists of using BMDL data from in vitro testing battery (DNT IVB) shown in Table 24. Reverse dosimetry could then be performed to estimate the corresponding blood levels in order to be compared with HBM-GV specific for DNT.

9.4.4. Preliminary results on HBM individual data

In relation to exposure assessment, the blood and/or urine levels of the selected metal(oid)s from HBM surveys are to be compared with internal ESRVs and/or used to calculate the Estimated Daily Intake (EDI) of each metal(oid) compound to be then compared to the corresponding TDI or ESRVs.

Conclusion

This document describes the progress that has been made in the first year of the PARC project Real-life mixtures. A strategy to perform mixture risk assessment (MRA) was successfully developed which includes three main steps: 1) Prioritisation of mixtures, 2) Collection and organisation of HBM and hazard data, and 3) Mixture risk assessment for prioritised mixtures and effects. Considering regulatory priorities, four chemical groups were prioritised for this project which include pesticides, metals, PFAS and mycotoxins, and six respective case studies related to their relevant effects were identified. These case studies will be addressed throughout the Real-life mixtures project. Great progress has been made regarding the collection, harmonisation and organisation of HBM in Europe, hazard and toxicokinetic data. Approaches to define internal toxicological values for MRA have also been addressed. The collected data and the developed approaches have begun to be integrated in the MCRA toolbox which is a web-based computational environment addressing chemical mixtures and their hazard, exposure and risk assessment for health effects. The development of MCRA in relation to the use of HBM data for MRA will continue to be advanced in the coming years. A deliverable is planned for each year of this project. It is expected that the next deliverables will present a continuation of the work already started, a refinement of the methods and strategy, and their application to the selected case studies.

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Appendix

Appendix 1. List of substances in prioritised chemical families

Case Study 1: Pesticides – Effects on nervous system, motor division (CAG-NAM)

- Triazophos
- Deltamethrin
- Omethoate
- Chlormequat
- Thiram
- Cypermethrin, beta-
- Cypermethrin, alpha-
- Cyhalothrin, lambda-
- Azinphos-ethyl
- Formetanate

Case Study 2: Pesticides – Effects on nervous system, brain and/or Ache inhibition (CAG-NAN)

- Chlorpyrifos
- Triazophos
- Omethoate
- Dichlorvos
- Carbofuran
- Pirimiphos-methyl
- Dimethoate
- Formetanate
- Methomyl
- Azinphos-ethyl

Case Study 3: PFAS -Effects on Immune system (CAG-INM)

- PFBA
- PFHxA
- PFHxS
- PFNA
- PFOA
- PFOS

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Case Study 4: Metals – Effects on kidney (CAG-RNL)

- As
- Cd
- Hg
- Pb

Case Study 5: Mycotoxins – Effects on hematopoietic system (CAG-HAE)

- Aflatoxins
- Alternaria toxins
- Deoxynivalenol
- Enniatins
- Fumonisin
- nivalenol
- Ochratoxin A
- T2/HT2 toxin
- Zearalenone

Case Study 6: Overarching for all chemical groups – Developmental neurotoxicity (CAG-DNT).

- Pb (lead)
- Me-Hg (methyl mercury)
- iAs (inorganic arsenic)

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Appendix 2. Main HBM studies listed in Data inventory

ESTEBAN, Etude de Santé sur l'Environnement, la Biosurveillance, l'Activité physique et la Nutrition (2016), France

ESTEBAN is a cross-sectional study conducted between 2014 and 2016 by Santé Publique France¹¹ on a representative sample of the French mainland population. ESTEBAN includes 1104 children aged from 6 to 17 and 2503 adults aged from 18 to 74. The aims of this study are to measure French exposure to certain environmental substances, to learn more about diet and physical activity, and to measure the importance of certain chronic diseases in the population. Participants answered a "questionnaire survey" to describe their food consumption habits, their physical activities, their environment, their health status (asthma, diabetes), and carried out a "health examination" comprising a series of measurements (anthropometric, blood pressure, functional respiratory exploration for adults) and biological samples (blood, urine, hair). Therefore, the bioconcentrations of more than one hundred environmental biomarkers have been analysed allowing the determination of impregnation levels of the French population (Balicco et al., 2017). Biomarkers of exposure measured in ESTEBAN were metals, bisphenols, pesticides (pyrethroids, carbamates, organotins, etc.), herbicides, dioxins, PCBs (polychlorinated biphenyls), phthalates, DINCH, mycotoxins, glycol-ethers, parabens, per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), and UV-filters. The full list of biomarkers is available in the data inventory. The biomarkers were analysed in subsets of individuals, i.e., these biomarkers were not studied in every individual.

FLEHS, the Flemish Environment and Health Study (2002-2020), Belgium

FLEHS is a cross-sectional HBM study that collects information on internal exposure to a broad range of environmental chemicals in the general population in Flanders, the Northern region of Belgium (Schoeters et al., 2017, 2022). Four successive campaigns of the FLEHS have recruited and sampled in total 6253 participants between 2002 and 2020 (FLEHS I: 2002–2006, FLEHS II: 2007–2011, FLEHS III: 2012–2015, FLEHS IV: 2016-2020). Cord samples from new-borns (FLEHS I-III), urine and blood samples from 14 to 15 years old adolescents (FLEHS I-IV) and from adults between 20 and 40 years (FLEHS II) and 50 and 65 years old (FLEHS I & III) were analysed in geographical representative samples of the Flemish population. Targets were set to include participants from different socio-economic statuses and the degree of urbanisation of their residential neighbourhood. The aim was to measure exposure to hazardous chemicals in a geographically representative sample of the Flemish population. Additional participants were recruited in three hot spot areas in FLEHS II and FLEHS III. Biomarkers of exposure measured in FLEHS I were persistent pollutants (dioxin-like compounds, PCBs, DDE, HCB), heavy metals (lead, cadmium), and benzene and PAH metabolites. Later campaigns also included newer emerging chemicals. In FLEHS IV, a total of 80 exposure biomarkers belonging to eight different chemical classes were measured, including regulated compounds and substitutes that replace

¹¹ <https://www.santepubliquefrance.fr/>

regulated and banned compounds: biomarkers related to exposure to chlorinated and newer pesticides, brominated and organophosphate flame retardants (BFR/OPFR), polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), bisphenols, phthalates and alternative plasticizers, per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), benzene, metals and trace elements. Additionally, relevant effect markers were measured in blood/urine or health effects were assessed through questionnaires (e.g., hormone levels, DNA damage, renal function, asthma, allergy, neurobehavioral outcome, fertility, puberty development). Allowing to investigate the relation between environmental pollution and human health (Section 5.2.1).

BIOAMBIENT.ES (2009-2010), Spain

BIOAMBIENT.ES is a cross-sectional study designed to recruit a representative sample of the Spanish workforce. The study was conducted between 2009 and 2010 and includes 1880 participants aged from 18 to 65. All participants completed a self-administrated epidemiological questionnaire containing basic socio-demographic questions and related to diet, lifestyle and medical determinants. A specific clinical form was also designed to be filled in by the doctors responsible for performing the health exams of the workers included, in order to gather basic clinical information for all participants in a uniform manner. In addition, participants were asked to grant access to their clinical records to have both the complete results of the occupational health exam as well as to obtain the data needed to assess possible occupational exposures. Biomarkers of polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), organochlorinated pesticides, metals and trace elements, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), phthalates and DINCH, brominated flame retardants (BFRs) and per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) have been analysed in BIOAMBIENT.ES samples, in different biological matrices (blood, urine and hair). Network analysis was performed in a subset of 163 participants for metals, i.e., mercury (Hg), cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb), thallium (Tl), and cobalt (Co), phthalates (DMP, DEP, BBzP, DiBP, DnBP, DEHP, DiNP, and DiDP), DINCH, and PFASs (PFHxS, PFOA, PFOS, PFNA, and PFDA). Samples of BIOAMBIENT.ES are biobanked at the National Centre for Environmental Health of the Instituto de Salud Carlos III.

DEMOCOPHES-SPAIN DEMONstration of a study to COordinate and Perform Human Biomonitoring on a European Scale (2011-2012), Spain

DEMOCOPHES in Spain is a cross-sectional study performed within DEMOCOPHES study, a harmonised European study involving mother/child pairs in 17 European countries. A total of 144 pairs (18-45y mothers; 6-11 y children) were recruited in two different locations (rural and urban). All participants completed an epidemiological questionnaire to gather information related to habits and lifestyles, as well as health information (self-reported BMI and illness) and donated a first morning urine and hair samples. Levels of total mercury and methylmercury in hair and cotinine, cadmium, phthalates and DINCH metabolites, bisphenol A in urine were measured in all samples. Samples of DEMOCOPHES - SPAIN are biobanked at the National Centre for Environmental Health of the Instituto de Salud Carlos III.

DEMOCOPHES-SLOVENIA, DEMONstration of a study to COordinate and Perform Human Biomonitoring on a European Scale (2010-2012), Slovenia

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DEMOCOPHES in Slovenia is a cross-sectional study performed within the European-wide DEMOCOPHES study, a harmonised study involving mother/child pairs in 17 European countries. A total of 155 pairs of mothers (18-45 years) and their children (6-11 years) were recruited in two different locations (rural and urban). All participants completed a questionnaire to gather information related to habits and lifestyles, as well as health information (self-reported BMI and chronic disease) and donated first morning urine, peripheral blood and scalp hair samples. Levels of total mercury in hair and cotinine in urine, trace elements (Cd, Pb, Hg, As, Se, Zn, Cu) in blood and urine, phthalate metabolites (MEHP, OH-MEHP, oxo-MEHP, MEP, MBzP, MnBP, MiBP, MnBP), bisphenol A, parabens (MeP, EtP, iPrP, PrP, iBuP, BuP, BzP) and triclosan in urine were measured in all samples (n=155). The overall results are published by Den Hond et al. (2015).

BEA, Biomonitorización en adolescents (2017-2018), Spain

BEA is a cross-sectional study, aligned with the HBM4EU studies (n=300), performed in 11 Spanish cities with more than 150,000 inhabitants with a total sample size of 499 individuals. Participants were adolescents aged from 12 to 17 years that were recruited from 22 secondary schools. They provided samples of hair, urine, blood (optional), and completed a guided self-administered questionnaire about lifestyle, environment and diet. They reported BMI and self-reported diagnosed illness. Levels of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), arsenic species, bisphenols, phthalates and DINCH metabolites and UV-filters were measured, as well as potential effect biomarkers (creatinine, SG, FSH, estradiol, insulin, SHBG, FT4, FT3, TSH, testosterone, cholesterol, triglycerides, glucose, HDL, LDL-C, adiponectin, leptin, LH, kisspeptin, BDNF, 8-OHdG). Samples of BEA are biobanked at the National Centre for Environmental Health of the Instituto de Salud Carlos III.

HBM4EU-mom, Methylmercury-control in expectant Mothers through suitable dietary advice for pregnancy, (2021-2022), Spain

HBM4EU-mom is an intervention study performed in five countries (Cyprus, Greece, Spain, Portugal and Iceland) with high consumption of seafood. It was designed as a randomised control trial and employed harmonised tool in all the stages of the study. In Spain, 133 women were recruited in early pregnancy (up to week 20) through their health care provider and distributed into a control group (not receiving dietary advice for fish consumption) and an intervention group (receiving the HBM4EU-MOM advice for fish consumption in pregnancy). In phase 1, each participant provided a scalp hair and dried blood spot (DBS) sample and answered a questionnaire via an assisted personal interviewer. In phase 2, after delivery, they provided again samples of hair and DBS, completed the questionnaire and additionally, some of them provided samples of hair and DBS from their new-borns. All participants gave access to clinical information of the new-borns at birth (i.e., weight, length, head circumference, Apgar score). Samples of HBM4EU-mom are biobanked at the National Centre for Environmental Health of the Instituto de Salud Carlos III.

Doetinchem Cohort Study (1987-), the Netherlands

The Doetinchem Cohort Study in the Netherlands is a prospective longitudinal study on lifestyle and other determinants of health and disease as they develop over the life course and during ageing. The Doetinchem Cohort Study is carried out by the National Institute for Public Health and the Environment

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(RIVM) in collaboration with the Municipal Health Service in Doetinchem and supported by the Dutch Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport. See also at: <https://www.rivm.nl/en/doetinchem-cohort-study> The Doetinchem Cohort Study runs since 1987 and currently consists of approximately 3000 participants (53% males, 47% females), aged between 50-90 years, originally sampled from the general population (Verschuren et al., 2008; Picavet et al., 2017). Doetinchem is located in a rural area in the eastern part of the Netherlands (Gelderland).

In 2018, blood and urine samples have been collected for the human biomonitoring of toxic metals. In 2019, samples were analysed for exposure and effect biomarkers of cadmium and lead. In 2023, samples will be analysed for exposure biomarkers of arsenic and mercury. All these metals have relatively long half-lives and accumulate in the human body. This means that a relatively high internal exposure is expected in the elderly (i.e., in this cohort) which may lead to negative health effects. As all participants have been followed in this cohort for over 30 years, information regarding their health status is available since 1987. Especially information about their smoking habits is of importance, as smoking can add considerably to the level of exposure to cadmium and, to a lesser extent, to lead. At the beginning of the Doetinchem cohort, approximately 36% of the cohort were smokers, 27% ex-smokers and 37% non-smokers (never-smokers) (Verschuren et al., 2008).

SPECIMEN, (2019-2020), Latvia, Hungary, Czech Republic, Spain and the Netherlands

Specimen is a suspect-screening based study to describe the probability of (concomitant) exposure to a set of pesticide profiles in five European countries (Latvia, Hungary, Czech Republic, Spain and the Netherlands). It explored whether living in an agricultural area (compared to living in a peri-urban area), being a child (compared to being an adult), and the season in which the urine sample was collected had an impact on the probability of detection of pesticides (metabolites).

In total 2,088 urine samples were collected from 1,050 participants (525 parent-child pairs) and were analysed through harmonised suspect screening by five different laboratories. Forty pesticide biomarkers (either pesticide metabolites or the parent pesticides as such) relating to 29 pesticides were identified at high levels of confidence in samples across all study sites. Most frequently detected were biomarkers related to the parent pesticides acetamiprid and chlorpropham. Other biomarkers with high detection rates in at least four countries related to the parent pesticides boscalid, fludioxonil, pirimiphos-methyl, pyrimethanil, clothianidin, fluazifop and propamocarb. In 84% of the samples at least two different pesticides were detected. The median number of detected pesticides in the urine samples was 3, and the maximum was 13 pesticides detected in a single sample. The most frequently co-occurring substances were acetamiprid with chlorpropham (in 62 urine samples), and acetamiprid with tebuconazole (30 samples).

The SPECIMEN-Control group (non-agricultural location) in Spain consists of 53 parent- (37-55y) child (6-11 y) pairs. All participants provided urine samples and completed a harmonised epidemiological questionnaire in each of the 2 seasons. A pesticide suspect screening methodology was applied to analyse all samples. The 212 samples of SPECIMEN-Control group in Spain are biobanked at the National Centre for Environmental Health of the Instituto de Salud Carlos III.

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EXHES-Greece, (-2023), Greece

In the context of Health and Environment-wide Associations based on Large population Surveys (HEALS) project, the Exposure and Health Examination Survey (EXHES) aims at recruiting and following-up in time (3 years at maximum) pairs of mothers and children, both singleton and twins, in order to dispose of the data to build internal and external exposome of major chronic diseases. EXHES Greece collected samples from mother and fathers and whenever possible from the children at the age of 1 years old. A total 100 urine samples were collected, 60 from the mothers and 40 from the fathers from where metals analysis was performed. Additionally, from the mothers, 60 blood (serum and plasma) samples and 30 breastmilk samples were collected, and from the fathers around 20 blood (serum and plasma) samples were collected. Samples related to the children are fewer with 13 cord blood and 7 blood (serum and plasma) samples were collected.

Samples were aliquoted and biobanked at the HERACLES research centre for further analysis for the next period.

CROME (2020-2021), Greece

The CROME study (Cross-Mediterranean Environment and Health Network) collected samples in Greece (Thessaloniki) between July 2020 and March 2021 (Gilles et al., 2022; Govarts et al., 2023). The CROME study was initiated as a parent-children cohort investigating the levels of environmental pollutants and biochemical indicators of exposure. Participants were invited through bilateral meetings and word of mouth due to the Covid-19 pandemic, i.e., to take place through the school structures was not feasible. The CROME study includes the recruitment of children and adolescents as well as the whole of their family and parents. For children the ages were between 6-11, adolescents were between 12-18 and adults were from 19-68 years. A total of 560 participants were recruited. From CROME, 161 children and 150 teenagers were included in the HBM4EU survey sample. A blood sample was collected for only some of the children (N = 55) and teenagers (N = 52). Furthermore, around 250 urine samples from adults (the parents) were collected, whereby 90 participants also provide blood samples.

Levels of per-and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) were quantified in teenager's samples (Jergovic et al., 2010; Richterová et al., 2023; Bil et al., 2023b), FBFRs in children's samples (van der Schyff et al., 2023) and phthalates and DINCH metabolites for all the 560 samples (Gerofke et al., 2023; Lange et al., 2022) as well as potential effect biomarkers (creatinine, SG for all the urine samples and cholesterol, triglyceride, ferritin, and blood creatinine for those provide blood sample).

Samples were aliquoted and biobanked at the HERACLES research centre for further analysis for the next period.

CELSPAC (1991–2023), RECETOX, the Czech Republic

The CELSPAC population studies (Central European Longitudinal Studies of Parents and Children) include several epidemiological cohorts from the Central Europe region. The cohorts are designed to identify important exposome factors and their effects on population health.

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The probands provide different biological matrices: blood (venous, cord, capillary), urine, breast milk, meconium/stool, and buccal swabs. Samples are aliquoted and biobanked at the RECETOX research centre of Masaryk University, the Czech Republic, for further analysis for the next period. The biological samples could be linked with data from the self-administered questionnaires about health, lifestyle, environment and diet, as well as data from the medical records. The levels of effect biomarkers as well as biomarkers of exposure are available for most of the participants.

CELSPAC: Young Adults (CELSPAC: YA) represents a follow-up study of the longitudinal ELSPAC study initiated as a birth cohort between 1991 to 1992 in the Czech Republic (N = 5,151) (Piler et al., 2017). The CELSPAC: YA is an ongoing study that follows ELSPAC children, their siblings, and spouses (age 17 to 45 years) from 2019 up to now. Nearly 1000 participants completed questionnaires, donated biological material (venous blood, urine, buccal smear), and underwent examination (anthropometry, blood pressure, spirometry, body composition, cognitive test).

CELSPAC: School Children and CELSPAC: Teenagers studies (CELSPAC: SC/TE) were conducted as cross-sectional studies in the South Moravia schools in the Czech Republic between 2019 to 2020 and included children aged from 6 to 11 years (N = 200) and teenagers from 12 to 17 years (N = 365). The main aim of this was to assess the multiple factors potentially affecting the physical fitness of teenagers. Probands completed questionnaires, underwent examinations (anthropometry, fitness test) and donated urine.

Subsets of 300 individuals from CELSPAC: YA and from CELSPAC: TE were included in the HBM4EU aligned studies. Levels of different substances included in the first HBM4EU analysis sets were measured: pesticides (DDTs, PeCB, HCB; 3-PBA, 4F3-PBA, t/c-DCCA, DEP, DETP, DEDTP, TCPY, DMP, DMTP, DEET, IMPY, MDA, PNP, CMHC, DMA, Pethoxamid, Pethoxamid MET42, Chlormequat chloride, Phthalamic acid, Phthalic acid, Fipronil sulfone, Carbendazim), phthalates and DINCH metabolites (metabolites MEP, MBzP, MiBP, MnBP, MCHP, MnPeP, MEHP, 5OH-MEHP, 5oxo-MEHP, 5cx-MEPP, MnOP, OH-MiNP, cx-MiNP, OH-MiDP, cx-MiDP, MiNP, oxo-MiNP, MCPP, oxo-MiDP), bisphenols (BPA, BPS, BPF), per- and polyfluorinated alkyl substances (PFPA, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnDA, PFDoDA, PFBS, PFHxS, PFHpS, PFOS), metals (Sb, As, Cr, Mo, Mn, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd, Hg, Tl, Pb, Se, species) and others such as polybrominated flame retardants HBCDs, PBDEs, syn DP, Anti DP, DBDPE, polychlorinated biphenyls PCBs, OH-PAHs, OPFR met., as well as potential effect biomarkers (creatinine, SG, lipid biomarkers, hepatic markers, glucose, TSH and CRP).

SLO-HBM, National HBM program (2008-2014), Slovenia

The program was initiated to provide data on exposure of the residents of Slovenia to chemicals and related health impact throughout Slovenia, reference (background) values, and spatial differences in exposure including rural, urban environments and potentially contaminated sites, to allow assessing exposure and risk for health. The cross-sectional study covered 12 areas of Slovenia and was conducted in two phases, between 2007 and 2009 (pilot phase); and between 2011 and 2014 to cover all study areas. It included 536 lactating women of childbearing age and 548 men of the same age range (19-49 years). Measurements of trace elements (Pb, Cd, Hg, As, Mn, Cu, Se, Zn) are available in random spot urine, peripheral blood and scalp hair (n = 1084), and in breast milk (n = 536) (Snoj Tratnik et al., 2019).

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Measurements of persistent organic pollutants were performed in pooled maternal milk and men's plasma (PCDD/Fs, PCB105, PCB114, PCB123, PCB126, PCB156, PCB157, PCB167, PCB169, PCB189, PCB77, PCB81, PCB118, ΣPBDEs), as well as in individual samples of maternal milk and men's serum (PCB28, PCB52, PCB101, PCB138, PCB180, PCB153, OCPs: PP_DDT, OP_DDT, OP_DDE, PP_DDD, HCB, aldrin, endrin, dieldrin, HCHs, heptachlor, chlordane, cis-HCE, trans-HCE) (Runkel et al., 2021). Measurements of phthalate metabolites (MEP, MBzP, MiBP, MnBP, MCHP, MnPeP, MEHP, OH-MEHP, oxo-MEHP, McxEPP, MnOP, cx-MINP, OH-MIDP, OH-MINP), DINCH metabolites (OH-MINCH, oxo-MINCH), bisphenols A, F, S, parabens (MeP, EtP, iPrP, PrP, iBuP, BuP, Bzp) and triclosan are available in spot urine of a subset of the original study population, including 304 women and 299 men (Runkel et al., 2022), as well as measurements of PAH metabolites (1+9-OH-phenanthrene, 2-OH-phenanthrene, 3-OH-phenanthrene, 4-OH-phenanthrene, 1-OH-pyrene, 2+3-OH-fluorene, 2-OH-naphthalene) (Joksić et al., 2022). The chemical measurements are accompanied by haemogram, creatinine and specific gravity measurements, as well as questionnaire data including general information (age, body weight, education and occupation), basic residential characteristics, basic health conditions, smoking and nutritional habits.

SLO-PHIME, Public health impact of long-term, low-level mixed element exposure in susceptible population data (2007-2011), Slovenia

Epidemiological study PHIME included birth cohorts from Italy, Slovenia and Croatia representing Northern Adriatic and Greece (Aegean Sea) recruited between 2007 and 2009. The overall aim of the Mediterranean study was to assess association between exposure to low-to-moderate levels of Hg and neurodevelopment of prenatally exposed children (Barbone et al., 2019). In addition to Hg, other elements were measured (Pb, Cd, Mn, As, Se, Zn, Cu). In the Slovenian sub-cohort, measurements of the listed trace elements are available in cord blood collected at birth, breast milk and Hg in maternal scalp hair (n=433) from mother-child pairs residing in the central area of Slovenia. Chemical measurements are accompanied by questionnaire data including general information (age, body weight, education and occupation), basic health conditions (chronic disease, pregnancy problems, medications), smoking and detailed information on nutritional habits, with emphasis on seafood consumption.

SLO-CROME, Cross-Mediterranean Environment and Health Network (2014-17), Slovenia

SLO-CROME study is the follow up of the Slovenian PHIME cohort, the aim of which was to assess the association between prenatal and childhood exposure to potentially neurotoxic elements and neurobehavior, considering genetic susceptibility. Children of the PHIME cohort from Slovenia were followed up at 7-8 years of age (sampling took place in 2016). At that time, random spot urine, scalp hair and peripheral blood samples were collected from children and their mothers. Concentrations of trace elements (Pb, Cd, Hg, As, Mn, V, Cr, Co, Ni, Mo, Sn, Se, Zn, Cu, etc.) were determined in whole blood, plasma, urine and hair, while organophosphorus pesticides and pyrethroids (DEAMPY, IMPY, MDA, PNP, TCPY, CMHC, 3-PBA, 4F-3-PBA) in urine of 178 mother-child pairs from central Slovenia region. Some results for trace elements, with focus on arsenic are published by Stajniko et al. (2019), and for pesticides by Bravo et al. (2020).

SLO-CRP (2016-2019), Slovenia

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This cross-sectional study was conducted within the national project '*Exposure of children and adolescents to selected chemicals through their habitat environment*' to identify the level of exposure of children and adolescents to substances that pose a risk to their health, to identify possible sources of exposure in relation to the living environment, to provide support for the adoption of political decisions on measures to reduce the exposure of the Slovenian population to selected chemicals, and to support the employment of the Action Plan for the implementation of the Strategy of Health of children and adolescents in relation to the environment 2012-2020 (Government of the Republic of Slovenia, July 2015). The study population included 7 to 10 years old children and 12 to 15 years old adolescents recruited in 2018 from the rural region of Prekmurje in the north-eastern part of Slovenia. This study population was also part of the HBM4EU Aligned Studies survey. Sample collection included first morning urine, peripheral blood and scalp hair. Concentrations of trace elements (Pb, Cd, Hg, As, Mn, V, Cr, Co, Ni, Mo, Sn, Se, Zn, Cu, etc.) were determined in whole blood, plasma, urine and hair; brominated flame retardants (HBCDs and PBDEs) and PFAS (PFPA, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnDA, PFDODA, PFBS, PFHxS, PFHpS, PFOS) in plasma, while metabolites of phthalates (MEP, MiBP, MnBP, MnPeP, MCHP, MBzP, MnOP, MEHP, OH-MEHP, oxo-MEHP, cx-MEPP, OH-MiNP, cx-MiNP, OH-MiDP, cx-MiDP), DINCH (OH-MINCH, cx-MINCH), bisphenols (BPA, F and S), parabens (MeP, EtP, iPrP, PrP, iBuP, BuP, BzP), triclosan, organophosphorus flame retardants (BDCPP, DPHP, BCEP, BCPP), PAHs (1+9-OH-phenanthrene, 2-OH-phenanthrene, 3-OH-phenanthrene, 4-OH-phenanthrene, 1-OH-pyrene, 2+3-OH-fluorene, 2-OH-naphthalene), glyphosate and AMPA, and organophosphorus pesticides and pyrethroids (DEAMPY, IMPY, MDA, PNP, TCPY, CMHC, 3-PBA, 4F-3-PBA) in urine. The chemical measurement data is accompanied by standard clinical measurements (haemogram, creatinine, SG, kidney damage biomarkers) and questionnaire data including general information (age, body weight and height, parental education and occupation), basic health conditions (chronic disease, medications), residential environment and detailed information on nutritional habits. Some results are published by Stajnik et al. (2020), Tkalec et al. (2021), Runkel et al., (2023), and by the HBM4EU consortium.

EuroMix, (2016-2017), Norway

The Norwegian EuroMix biomonitoring (BM) study is a part of the "European Test and Risk Assessment Strategies for Mixtures" project (EuroMix, 633172-2) which was funded by the Horizon 2020 (H2020) program.

The EuroMix BM study investigated the exposure to chemical mixtures from foods and personal care products (PCPs) for two non-consecutive days (with 2-3 weeks in between). The study recruited 144 participants: 44 men (25 - 72 years old) and 100 women (24 - 72 years old). They were recruited from governmental institutes and universities in the counties of Oslo and Akershus in Norway between September 2016 and November 2017. All the participants completed the first day of the study, while 140 participants completed the second day (43 men and 97 women). The participants recorded their weighed food consumption and their use of PCPs for the two days in a diary. They also completed a validated food frequency questionnaire (FFQ) that covered the total diet the previous year, and a questionnaire on socio-demographic and lifestyle characteristics, including sex education, age, weight,

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height, and smoking habits. Participants collected each urine void in separate containers during the 24-hour periods of recording and marked these with time and date. Blood (in total 70 mL per participant per study day) was collected at the end of each 24-hour period at the Norwegian Institute of Public Health (NIPH), to obtain serum, plasma, white and red blood cells, as well as RNA/DNA extracted from total blood.

Several contaminants in blood and urine have been measured: twenty-five PFASs (6:2PAP, 8:2PAP, 6:2diPAP, 8:2diPAP, PFHxPA, PFOPA, PFDPA, PFBS, PFHxS, PFHpS, PFOS, PFDS, PFPeA, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnDA, PFDoDA, PFTTrDA, PFTeDA, PFOSA, MeFOSA and EtFOSA) were quantified in the serum, eleven different phthalate metabolites, MEP, MiBP, MnBP, MBzP, MEHP, MEHHP, MEOHP, MECPP, MMCHP, oh-MiNP, oxo-MiNP, cx-MiNP, oh-MPHP and two metabolites of DINCH (oh-MINCH), (oxo-MINCH), metals Hg, Pb and Cd in urine, four parabens (methyl paraben (MEPA), ethyl paraben (ETPA), propyl paraben (PRPA) and butyl paraben (BUPA)), five bisphenols (BPA, BPS, BPF, BPB and BPAF), and some other phenols OXBE, TCS and TCC, mycotoxins DON and T2/HT2 in urine, pesticides acetamiprid, carbendazim, flonicamid, imidacloprid, pirimiphos-methyl, tebuconazole, thiacloprid, cyprodinil, fluopyram, imidacloprid, pyrimethanil, pyrimethanil, thiabendazole, trifloxystrobin, DBCA, cisDCCA, transDCCA, 3PBA, boscalid and imazalil.

NEB II, The Norwegian Environmental Biobank (2016-2017), Norway

The Norwegian Environmental Biobank (NEB) is a longitudinal study initiated to assess exposure to environmental chemicals and related health impact(s). Participants of NEB were recruited from a subset of participants from the Norwegian Mother, Father and Child Cohort Study (MoBa). NEB II was conducted in 2016-2017, and blood and spot urine samples of triads mothers, fathers and children were collected. Also, mothers and fathers completed a self-administrated questionnaire including questions on their and their child's diet, socio-demographic and lifestyle characteristics. The total study included 671 children and teenagers in the age group 7-14 years. For children between 7-11 years, a sub selection of 300 children was included in the HBM4EU aligned studies sample. While for teenagers between 12-14 years, all 181 NEB II participants were included in the HBM4EU aligned studies sample. Phthalates and DINCH (MEP, MiBP, MnBP, MBzP, MnPeP, MCHP, MnOP, MEHP, MEHHP, MEOHP, MECPP, MMCHP, oh-MiNP, oxo-MiNP, cx-MiNP, oh-MPHP, oh-MINCH) have been reported in the samples from both children and teenagers, flame retardants (PBDE-47, PBDE-153, DP-syn, DP-anti, DPHP, BDCIPP) and acrylamide metabolites (AAMA, GAMA) were determined in samples of children, PFASs (PFBS, PFHxS, PFHpS, PFOS, PFDS, PFBA, PFPeA, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnDA, PFDoDA) were determined in samples of teenagers. In addition, the following biomarkers of effect have been determined in samples of children and teenagers (HDL cholesterol, LDL cholesterol, apolipoprotein A1, lipoprotein A, apolipoprotein B, leptin, adiponectin, insulin, TSH), while kisspeptin 54 was determined in samples of teenagers and BDNF in samples of children.

ACCEPT (2010-2015), AU-PH

The Greenlandic ACCEPT birth cohort established in 2010-2015, include approximately 600 pregnant women (aged 18-43 years) from all Greenlandic regions. At inclusion, the participants completed a

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food frequency questionnaire regarding intake of traditional and imported food, and a lifestyle questionnaire with baseline information (age, pre-pregnancy BMI, self-reported smoking status, education, alcohol intake, reproductive factors, etc.). Blood data are available for persistent organic pollutants (POPs) and metals including 11 organochlorine pesticides (OCPs), 14 polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), 10 flame retardants, 16 perfluoroalkylated substances (PFAS), and 13 metals. The full list of biomarkers is available in the data inventory.

Furthermore, data on extracted serum real-life mixtures (lipPOP and PFAS) and the effect of the functions on the estrogen-, androgen-, and aryl hydrocarbon receptors was collected. In 2019-2020, a follow-up on 100 families was conducted with questionnaires (diet, lifestyle and child development) and exposure data (similar as in mentioned above) on the mother, father and child (Bank-Nielsen, Long and Bonefeld-Jørgensen, 2019; Hjermitsev et al., 2020; Kornvig et al., 2021; Long, Wielsøe and Bonefeld-Jørgensen, 2022; Wielsøe et al., 2022).

FETOTOX-ABC (2008–2013), AU-PH

As part of the international FETOTOX project, 1533 pregnant women from the Aarhus Birth Cohort Biobank (ABC), Denmark were randomly included. During pregnancy, the women completed questionnaires on maternal characteristics. Blood data are available for persistent organic pollutants (POPs) and metals. For 800 participants included in 2011-2013, 16 perfluoroalkylated substances (PFAS) were measured. Lipophilic POPs data are available for 197 of the 800 participants including 11 organochlorine pesticides (OCPs), 14 polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), 10 flame retardants, and 13 metals. The full list of biomarkers is available in the data inventory. Furthermore, data on extracted serum real-life mixtures (lipPOP and PFAS) and the effect of the functions on the estrogen-, androgen-, and aryl hydrocarbon receptors was collected (Bjerregaard-Olesen et al., 2019).

BOC-DNBC (1996-2002), AU-PH

Danish prospective case-control cohort of pregnant women at blood sampling (1996-2002) with follow-up on diagnosis of breast cancer 10-15 years later. The data set include 250 controls (21-42 years of age) and 233 cases (20-42 years of age). Questionnaires on maternal characteristics at pregnancy (including breast cancer risk factors: diet, height, weight, diseases in the family, smoking, and alcohol intake, total number of gravidities, oral contraceptives (OC) use, age of menarche, maternal education, and physical activity). Serum measurement of 16 perfluoroalkylated substances (PFAS) were performed (Bonefeld-Jørgensen et al., 2014). The full list of biomarkers is available in the data inventory.

BOC-GRL (2000-2014), AU-PH

The Greenlandic case-control study included 84 controls (19-75 years of age) and 77 cases (29-81 years of age) sampled in 2000-2003 and 2011-2014. At inclusion, the participants completed a food frequency questionnaire regarding intake of traditional and imported food, and a lifestyle questionnaire with baseline information (breast cancer risk factors: age, BMI, self-reported smoking status, education, alcohol intake, reproductive factors, etc.). Blood data are available for persistent organic pollutants (POPs) and metals including 11 organochlorine pesticides (OCPs), 14 polychlorinated

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biphenyls (PCBs), 10 flame retardants, 16 perfluoroalkylated substances (PFAS), and 13 metals. The full list of biomarkers is available in the data inventory. Furthermore, data on extracted serum real-life mixtures (lipPOP and PFAS) and the effect of the functions on the estrogen, androgen, and aryl hydrocarbon receptors is available (Bonefeld-Jørgensen et al., 2011; Wielsøe, Kern and Bonefeld-Jørgensen, 2017; Wielsøe et al., 2018).

Occupational data sets: HBM4EU chromate study and E-waste study

For occupational MRA, two relevant data sets with data from several European countries were identified. These include the HBM4EU chromate study dataset and HBM4EU E-waste study dataset.

HBM4EU chromate study dataset (Santonen et al., 2022) contains biomonitoring data from 9 countries on exposure to Cr, Ni, Mn and PFASs from the metal industry. The worker groups covered were metal surface treatment workers, of which largest group were chrome bath platers, and welders. PFASs were measured primarily from chrome bath platers who may have used PFASs as mist suppressants. The countries involved in the chromate study were Finland, UK, Belgium, Luxembourg, France, Italy, Portugal, Poland and the Netherlands. The total number of exposed workers studied was 399. The study also included 203 controls. Individual data on each worker is available for risk assessment. The dataset is co-controlled by all partners involved in the conduct of the study.

HBM4EU E-waste study (Scheepers et al., 2021) contains biomonitoring data from 8 countries on exposure to metals (Hg, Cd, Pb, Cr) and flame retardants (both organophosphate and brominated flame retardants) and phthalates. The exposed workers were performing different tasks related to the E-waste processing. The countries involved in the E-waste study were Finland, UK, Belgium, Luxembourg, Portugal, Poland, Latvia and the Netherlands. Total number of exposed workers studied was 195. The study also included 73 controls. Individual data on each worker is available for risk assessment. The dataset is co-controlled by all partners involved in the conduct of the study.

GerES studies (continuous since 1980s), Germany

The German Environmental Survey (GerES) is a representative cross-sectional study carried out to determine the exposure to pollutants of the general population in Germany. The study has been conducted by the German Environment Agency since the mid-1980s.

GerES IV is the first environmental survey focusing exclusively on children by determining, on a representative basis, the body burden of pollutants and the exposure to pollutants at home. GerES IV is a module of the German Health Interview and Examination Survey for Children and Adolescents (German acronym: KiGGS baseline) and was carried out in close cooperation with the Robert Koch Institute (RKI). The GerES IV was performed with a randomly selected sub-sample of the KiGGS population consisting of 1,790 children aged 3 to 14 years and living in 150 different sampling locations. GerES V investigated children and adolescents by determining, on a representative basis, the body burden of pollutants and the exposure to pollutants at home. GerES V is a module of the Second Wave of the German Health Interview and Examination Survey for Children and Adolescents (German acronym: KiGGS Wave 2) and was carried out in close cooperation with the RKI. GerES V was performed

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in a randomly selected sub-sample of the KiGGS population consisting of 2,294 children and adolescents aged 3 to 17 years and living in 167 different sampling locations.

GerES V-sub (unweighted) is the data set provided for and according to the criteria of the HBM4EU Aligned Studies consisting of a sub-sample of 300 children and 300 adolescents from GerES V with some additional analyses (specific gravity in adolescents and flame retardants in children).

INMA-Asturias (2004-present), Spain

This is a multicenter population-based mother child cohort. It was constituted by recruiting pregnant women visiting the San Agustin Hospital (Aviles, Asturias, Spain) for their first prenatal care visit at 12-14 weeks of pregnancy from 2004 to 2007. Deliveries between October 2004 and February 2008. Eligibility criteria and withdrew or loss of follow-up are described in detail (Fernández-Somoano et al., 2011; Fernández-Somoano and Tardon, 2014). Pregnant women completed two detailed questionnaires on anthropometric and sociodemographic characteristics and lifestyle variables conducted face-to-face by trained personnel. Deliveries took place between October 2004 and February 2008. The median maternal age and height were 31 years and 163 cm, respectively. 26% of the pregnant women were overweight or obese, 25.6% smoked during pregnancy and 42.6% were passive smokers during pregnancy. No disorders or genital malformations were observed in the children enrolled in this study. A total of 485 children were born. Follow-up at 7-8 years was carried out to 416 children via questionnaires on environmental health data, diet, and sociodemographic characteristics. Pediatricians examined the children, collected blood samples, and recorded anthropometric measures and sexual development. Among whom anogenital distance was measured in 362 children (Garcia-Villariño et al., 2018; 2020; 2021). Participants provided written informed consent prior to inclusion and then they signed a second consent after birth to enroll the children into the INMA project. The analyses of organochlorine pesticides, PCBs and polybromodiphenyl ethers in maternal serum (n = 308), cord blood serum (n = 308) and placenta (n = 50) are available (Vizcaino et al., 2014a; 2014b). Analyses of metals and creatinine in urine of four-year-old children are available (n = 334) (Junque et al., 2020; 2022). Analyses of pyrethroids and organophosphates in four-year old children are available (Gari et al., 2019). Analyses of bisphenols, phthalates and PFOS/PFAS in the collected urine of the volunteers (4 and 8 year-old) will be performed. Sampling and analysis will continue until collection of young adults (19-20 year-old).

ESB (continuous since 1980s), Germany

The environmental specimen bank (ESB) is an archive for samples that can be used to document and assess the quality of the environment in which we live. Specimens from typical ecosystems all over Germany, including HBM, are collected at regular intervals and stored in the German Environmental Specimen Bank. Human specimens (blood and urine) are collected from student volunteers at four different sites. All compiled specimens are tested for the presence of a wide variety of chemical substances (including heavy metals, PFAS, phthalates) before being deep-frozen and consigned to storage. The Environmental Specimen Bank serves as a vital instrument of Germany's environmental policy, because it not only provides documented evidence of the current state of the environment but

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also keeps past specimens available for verifying the effectiveness of policy measures and for investigating unanticipated later questions.

Appendix 3. Descriptive statistics template

Survey description

Survey name	Survey code	Description	Number of individuals in survey	Number of samples	Location	Start date of sampling	End date of sampling
						YYYY	YYYY

Human monitoring individual statistics

Property	Number of individuals	Mean	p25	Median	p75	Min	Max	Missing
Age	-							
Body weight	-							
Gender F		-	-	-	-	-	-	
Gender M		-	-	-	-	-	-	
Other ...								

Human monitoring individual concentrations by substance

Biological matrix	Sampling type	Substance name	Substance code	Individuals with positive concentrations	Percentage individuals with positive concentrations	All individuals ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$)				Individual positive concentrations ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$)				
						Mean	Median	p25	P95	Mean	Median	p25	P95	

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Appendix 4. Steps to perform Mixture Analysis with MCRA

The following steps summarise how to perform Mixture Analysis with MCRA.

- a. Upload the data to MCRA
- b. Create an MCRA Exposure mixtures action
- c. Choose initial action settings for human biomonitoring data
 - i. Risk type 'Chronic'
 - ii. Internal concentration 'Human monitoring concentrations'
 - iii. Substance weighting 'Standardized'
- d. Link HBM data
- e. Choose action settings for imputation and mixture analysis
 - i. Choose setting how to handle censored values (e.g., as $0.5 * \text{LOR}$, where the LOR (limit of reporting) means LOQ if that is provided, or else LOD).
 - ii. Choose how to impute any missing values (e.g, 'impute from data', 'set as zero', no imputation').
 - iii. Set Method to 'SNMU + hierarchical clustering' to first select mixtures by SNMU and subsequently identify population sub-groups with similar exposure to the mixtures.
 - iv. Adapt the SNMU settings for 'SNMU: number of mixtures' and 'Sparseness parameter'
 - v. Subsequently specify how many population sub-groups to identify by selecting 'Determine number of clusters automatically'.
- f. Inspect the results:
 - i. On 'Substance contributions to mixtures' to show the SNMU mixture selection results. A table with statistics for each mixture such as number of substances involved and explained variance is given. Additionally, the relative contribution of each substance to the mixture is presented in the heatmap. The pie-chart and table in the subsections per mixture offers more detailed information about the relative contributions of substances.
 - ii. A graph shows the evolution of the residual square error with the number of mixtures.
 - iii. The analysis should be adapted based on these results by changing the number of mixtures in step and the sparseness parameter.

Appendix 5. Preliminary results of mixture identification applying SNMU approach on ESTEBAN subset: Composition of mixtures 2 to 10

Pie Chart - Mixture 2, composition:

Pie Chart - Mixture 3, composition:

Pie Chart - Mixture 4, composition:

Pie Chart - Mixture 5, composition:

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Pie Chart - Mixture 6, composition:

Pie Chart - Mixture 7, composition:

Pie Chart - Mixture 8, composition:

Pie Chart - Mixture 9, composition:

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Pie Chart - Mixture 10, composition:

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